

Tigemaxo (Bozo) texts recorded 2022 in Dia village (Mali),
with a catalog of other Tigemaxo/Tiéyaxo recordings

Jeffrey Heath
University of Michigan

2025

Language Description Heritage Library (at Zenodo)
backup at Deep Blue Documents (U Michigan Libraries)

author's emails
schweinehaxen@hotmail.com
jheath@mich.edu

Contents

Introduction and catalog	i
The 2022 Tigemaxo recordings	i
The 2024 Tigemaxo recordings	ii
2024 audio files: interviews	iii
2024 audio files: tales.....	iv
The 1989 Tigemaxo/Tiéyaxo recordings	viii
The 2021 Tiéyaxo recordings	ix
Relevant documentary videos.....	ix
Funding.....	x
Transcription of 2022 Tigemaxo texts from Dia.....	1
Text 2022-02 Women’s life then and now.....	1
Text 2022-03 Tale of the hunchbacked girl.....	21
Text 2022-05 Tale of hare and hyena	34
Text 2022-06 Origins of Dia village; marriage	41
Text 2022-07 Fishing	82
Text 2022-09 Farming.....	104
Text 2022-10 Coming-of-age rites and marriage	117

Introduction and catalog

This document contains a catalog of audio files in Tigemaxo/Tiéyaxo (the two varieties are dialects of the same language), and a transcription and translation of the 2022 Tigemaxo recordings. It is designed to be used in conjunction with *A grammar of Tigemaxo of Dia (Bozo family, Mali)* and the accompanying Tigemaxo lexical spreadsheet.

The 2022 Tigemaxo recordings

The texts transcribed here constitute most of a session recorded in Dia village in 2022. (For another body of recordings from 2024 see below.) The longer recordings in the 2022 session feature the men Alfa Boubacar Karabenta and Seni Yalouta, the latter acting chiefly as interviewer-moderator. There were also two tales in Tigemaxo, with song segments in Bambara, narrated by the women Fada Songomo and Koono Kouanda. Texts 02, 03, 05, 07, 09, and 10 have been transcribed. Other segments were recorded but were unsuitable for transcription for one reason or another (interrupted, brevity, poor sound quality). The key native-speaker assistant for the text transcriptions, as for the grammar and lexicon, was Oumar Dienta of Dia village, who worked with Heath during several long stays at Heath's base in Bobo Dioulasso in neighboring Burkina Faso.

The recording session was organized and the microphone hand-held by longtime project manager Minkailou Djiguiba (not a Bozo). Because of a glitch with the digital microphone, the first 12 to 28 seconds of each audio file were over-recorded and unintelligible, so the transcribed portion of each text begins immediately after this point. The bad sections have been silenced before archiving.

The inventory is as follows. Information about speakers and more details about content are given at the beginning of each text.

text	duration	transcribable	seconds	title
2022-02	05:38	00:16 - 05:38	322	Women's life then and now
2022-03	05:23	00:28 - 05:23	295	Tale of the hunchbacked girl
2022-05	02:12	00:05 - 02:12	127	Tale of hare and hyena
2022-06	13:04	00:08 - 13:04	776	Origins of Dia village; marriage
2022-07	07:14	00:19 - 07:14	415	Fishing
2022-09	04:44	00:19 - 04:44	265	Farming
2022-10	08:08	00:12 - 08:08	476	Coming-of-age rites and marriage

The audio files will be deposited at Deep Blue Data (University of Michigan Libraries) and will be open access and available for download online.

The transcriptions are presented in small chunks, often of two lines of Tigemaxo, with interlinear glosses, a free English translation, and (where relevant) additional comments in

italics. Each chunk begins with a time marking which will allow end-users to work with the audio and the transcription side by side. The comments at the end of each chunk often include references to sections (§) of the grammar.

The 2024 Tigemaxo recordings

Although the 2022 recordings were sufficient for purposes of producing a grammar-text-lexicon documentation of Tigemaxo, by 2024 the author had realized the value of making additional recordings and archiving them as an open-access audio library of the language for native and foreign end-users.

Project manager Djiguiba again visited Dia in 2024, and this time the (new) digital microphone worked! The 2024 recordings include some additional ethnohistory, along with comments about natural species (mainly fish and edible grasses), and a large body of tales. The ethnohistory and natural-species texts are interview-style. Each of the tales is presented in two versions, the original Tigemaxo version and a French summary translation made immediately after each tale recording by Oumar Dienta. Each audio file for a tale has a title consisting of the personal name and surname of the narrator, a number (beginning 01 for each narrator), and a simple title. An example is “Fada Songomo 01 beautiful girl hides to avoid capture by the king.wav” The paired French summary translation is labeled “Fada Songomo 01tr traduction française par Oumar Dienta.wav” The author listened to these recordings with Oumar Dienta, identifying new lexical items for the lexical spreadsheet. The author has no plans to transcribe the 2024 audio files; others are welcome to do so. Like the 2022 audio files, these will be archived at Deep Blue Data, an online repository at the University of Michigan Libraries. Others are welcome to archive them elsewhere for safekeeping.

The inventory of 2024 audio files is the following, divided into interviews and tales. The time markings like 04:48 indicate the duration of the file. Some tales include songs, either in Bambara or Tigemaxo, and this is indicated for each file. All audio files were recorded in, and are deposited in, .wav format.

2024 audio files: interviews

Mama Sienta (male, born c. 1940), interviewed by **Oumar Dienta**:

Mama Sienta 01 comments on fish species part 1

19:22

būgā *Hemichromis* (01:02), fúlù *Tetraodon* (04:14), fúúŋ-júʒⁿ (general term) & wōrō & wālā trunkfish (Mormyridae) spp. (06:27), gómbèlé & tánamááyā *Chrysichthys* (08:15), jáwā *Alestes dentex* (09:24), kómbōⁿ & kíérē & kóⁿyóŋ xòðⁿ carp (Cichlidae) spp. (10:46), kóndòⁿ *Heterotis* (11:50), kóⁿyòⁿ (general term) & tūlā carps (13:54), kóónó *Protopterus* (14:22), kūnā *Brycinus nurse* (16:53), léè *Brycinus leuciscus* (17:53)

Mama Sienta 02 comments on fish species part 2

21:44

continuation of léè *Brycinus leuciscus* (00:01), nūmbō *Malapterurus* (00:20), follow-up on léè (01:45), nús xóóⁿ *Lates* (02:48), sámū *Bagrus* (05:22), sélè *Hydrocynus brevis* (06:14), sáŋà *Gymnarchus* (07:26), sónómò *Clarias* (08:27), fīénē *Schilbe* (11:05), fúólé & gómbò *Distichodus* (12:27), táámúⁿ *Heterobranchus* (13:22), túndúùŋ-xéèlé *Synodontis* (14:41), xóbó *Labeo* (15:25), xóómó fiⁿ *Synodontis nigrita* (16:42), xóró-xòrò *Auchenoglanis* (17:39), xóómò *Synodontis* spp. (18:32), xwééⁿ *Polypterus* (19:26), sáánááⁿ *Hydrocynus forskahlii* (20:48)

Mama Sienta 03 comments on locally extinct fish species

03:46

continuation of sáánááⁿ *Hydrocynus forskahlii* (00:01), núde-nááŋ-gòógāā *Tylochromis* (00:20), xáwrāā *Ctenopoma* (01:12), diurnal versus nocturnal fish spp. (02:05)

Mama Sienta 04 comments on edible herbs (seeds and water lilies)

03:14

boy-juʒⁿ *Eragrostis* (00:14), gáráxásāā *Brachiaria lata* (00:35), múⁿyāāⁿ *Brachiaria mutica* (00:49), pádíri (00:57), máxá-jùðⁿ fódómó *Pycneus* (01:07), fómbó *Nymphaea* (01:42), fíéwà *Oryza* (wild) (02:12)

Mama Sienta 05 comments on, edible herbs (tubers)

01:59

jíémú fíiⁿ *Cyperus* sp. (00:01), ségé *Eleocharis* & kólòbádì *Cyperus articulatus* (00:49)

Mama Sienta 06 colonial times

13:42

Mama Sienta 07 famine and colonial taxes

04:21

Mama Sienta 08 disease epidemics and remedies

04:07

Mama Sienta 09 construction of houses in the past

06:29

Mama Sienta 10 construction of granaries in the past

05:02

Mama Sienta 11 land and river transportation in the past

03:45

Mama Sienta 12 male female relations in the past

10:33

(Mama Sienta 13 does not exist)

Mama Sienta 14 schooling and work in the past

05:49

Mama Sienta 15 making fishing gear

16:05

fishtrap kíénè (00:35—), fishing spears tínáāⁿ & búxāā & nāgī (03:21—), types of fishnet séw (05:30—)

2024 audio files: tales

Fada Songomo (female, born c. 1976)

Fada Songomo 01 beautiful girl who hides to avoid capture by king

04:48

song in Bambara at 04:15

Fada Songomo 02 girl and female genie

02:25

song in Bambara at 01:35

Fada Songomo 03 hyena and hare try to sell their mothers to buy cows

01:57

no songs

Fatoumata Wandja (female, born c. 2010)

Fatoumata Wandja 01 hunter with ten wives meets crowned crane

03:10

song at 01:24 in Tigemaxo

Fouba Salamanta (female, daughter of Malado Komina, born c. 1990)

Fouba Salamanta 01 two girls compete in beauty

03:32

song at 00:31 in Bambara and repeats

Fouba Salamanta 02 girl is sworn to silence by sorceress but is forced to speak

04:19

song at 02:04 in Bambara

Fouba Salamanta 03 man wants to marry his daughters who escape helped by hippo

06:58

song at 00:58 in Tigemaxo and repeats

(cf. Sadan Farota 01)

Fouba Salamanta 04 magic gourd eats everything in royal courtyard including people

04:22

song at 00:51 in Bambara and repeats

Fouba Salamanta 05 girl takes basket to dump garbage but dog steals basket

03:36

no songs

Fouba Salamanta 06 cobra enters stomach of gardener to escape hunter

04:09

no songs

Fouba Salamanta 07 pond where fishing is prohibited on Mondays

01:17

no songs

Fouba Salamanta 08 his son is a bigger liar than he is

03:45

no songs

(repeat of Malado Komina 01)

Fouba Salamanta 09 three gluttons are expelled from their villages

03:16

no songs

Hadja Dienta (female, born c. 1991)

Hadja Dienta 01 three suitors of girl turn back into trees and sand

02:11

song at 01:19 in Bambara

Koma Farota (male, born c. 1980)

Koma Farota 01 frog beats ostrich in race

02:29

no songs

Koono Konta (female, born c. 1979)

Koono Konta 01 hyena and nannygoat with nine kids

03:09

song in Tigemaxo at 00:16 and several repeats

Koono Konta 02 girls magically kill a beautiful girl whose mother gets revenge

05:32

song in Bambara at 02:45 and several repeats

Koono Konta 03 girl wooed by youths then by animals in human guise

06:38

song in Tigemaxo at 02:58 and several repeats

Malado Komina (female, born c. 1970, has daughters Tina Wandja and Fouba Salamanta)

Malado Komina 01 trickster taught to lie by father ends up as king

10:43

noisy background; no songs

(basically identical to Fouba Salamanta 08)

- Malado Komina 02 goat kid hyena and monster
 04:35
 no songs
- Malado Komina 03 hare monster and squacco heron
 02:13
 song in Tigemaxo at 00:42
- Malado Komina 04 hare refuses to join animals in digging a well
 04:25
 no songs
- Malado Komina 05 sorceress eats her own son by mistake
 04:48
 brief songs in Tigemaxo repeated
- Malado Komina 06 two young men their dog and genie girl
 02:59
 brief songs in Tigemaxo repeated
- Malado Komina 07 fisherman & son with monsters and white stork
 03:31
 no songs
- Malado Komina 08 princess puts gold in tree as test to suitors won by leper
 08:15
 no songs
- Malado Komina 09 mistreated orphan girl with lutefish and golden shoes
 08:28
 no songs
- Malado Komina 10 girl mistreated by elder sister is saved by warthog
 06:01
 song in Tigemaxo at 03:15
- Malado Komina 11 king with favorite and disfavored wives and their daughters
 02:38
 song in Tigemaxo at 00:27
- Malado Komina 12 humble donkey driver transforms himself into a heroic warrior
 04:29
 no songs
- Malado Komina 13 seven brothers go to the fields each with a genie woman
 04:15
 no songs
- Malado Komina 14 singing dog warns farmer his wife is unfaithful
 01:40
 song at 00:51 in Tigemaxo mixed with Jenaama/Sorogaama
- Malado Komina 15 evil woman makes stepdaughter wash ladle in river
 06:43
 song at 00:51 in mix of Tigemaxo and Bambara

- Malado Komina 16 son of fisherman is friendly with monster
05:00
no song
- Malado Komina 17 hyena with its family and a cream of millet ball
03:14
no songs
- Malado Komina 18 eight girls enter tree hyena_s lair and escape by singing
01:57
song in Bambara at 00:30
- Malado Komina 19 stubborn girl resists marriage but is tamed by a trick
01:56
no songs
- Malado Komina 20 beautiful girl detested by others is saved from python
03:14
song in Tigemaxo at 00:35
- Malado Komina 21 his sisters incite his foolish wife to burn his child
03:48
no songs
- Malado Komina 22 she won_t pronounce brother_s name after he snubs her
01:38
song at 00:50 in Tigemaxo with some Bambara
- Malado Komina 23 jealous girls push a girl of royal family into a well
05:41
song at 02:20 in Tigemaxo and repeats

Mama Wandja (male, born c. 1940)

- Mama Wandja 01 Fulbe herder Bozo fisher and don't consume milk and catfish together
06:05
no songs
- Mama Wandja 02 herder fisher and farmer
07:39
much background chatter; no songs
- Mama Wandja 03 hunter fisher and fish eagle
05:35
no songs

Oumar Dienta (male, born 1995)

- Oumar Dienta 01 village always loses boat race due to water sprites
03:33
no song
- Oumar Dienta 02 beautiful girl refuses to marry any man who has a scar
04:34
song at 02:51 in Bambara and repeat

Sadan Farota (female, born c. 1920, Oumar's maternal grandmother, mother of Mama Wandja)

Sadan Farota 01 man who wanted to marry his two daughters

01:42

consists mostly of songs beginning @ 00:26 in Tigemaxo, she forgot some of the tale (cf. Fouba Salamanta 03)

Sadan Farota 02 orphan girl cruel stepmother two forests and *Khaya* tree

04:38

song @ 00:23 in Tigemaxo and repeats

Sadan Farota 03 monkeys lion and sycamore fig tree

03:12

song @ 01:41 in Tigemaxo

Tina Wandja (female, born c. 2002, daughter of Mama Wandja and of Malado Komina)

Tina Wandja 01 lazy son sent away by father comes back rich

02:22

no songs

Tina Wandja 02 orphan girl made crazy by magic visits elder sister

06:00

song at 02:04 in Bambara and repeats

Tina Wandja 03 orphan girl forced to wash hands in oil before meals

03:00

no songs

The 1989 Tigemaxo/Tiéyaxo recordings

Around 1989-1991, while working chiefly on Songhay languages, I took advantage of opportunities to make recordings on cassette tape in various other languages for future study. Typically two speakers would be invited to record themselves speaking in dialogue form on topics of their choice. Two of these tapes involve Tigemaxo-Tiéyaxo. The cassette contents were later digitized. Each tape was recorded without breaks or divisions except for momentary pauses to turn the cassette over. The total times including A and B tracks are about one hour each.

1989-01 tracks A and B

recorded in Mopti

speakers are Barkaba Kouante (BK) and Kemare Kouanta (KK)

Tiéyaxo dialect of Nouh-Bozo area on the Niger R.

1989-02 tracks A and B
recorded in Gao
speaker is Alfa Moussa (AM)
Tigemaxo dialect of Dia area

The Malian government agency involved in native-language research was then called DNAFLA (it has since morphed into AMALAN, the Académie Malienne des Langues Nationales). Mama Kouata, at the time the Bozo specialist at DNAFLA, was commissioned to transcribe them and translate them into French. His handwritten manuscripts are easily readable, and the combination of the manuscripts and recordings constitute a useful corpus for further study of both Tigemaxo and Tiejaxo, as well as containing rich ethnohistorical and cultural material.

For basic linguistic purposes, tape 1989-01 is especially useful for bringing out dialectal differences between Tiejaxo of the Niger R. area and Tigemaxo of Dia as described in this work and its supplements. Tape 1989-02, by contrast, is linguistically idiosyncratic, including many borrowed words and phrases from other languages (Gao is Songhay-speaking with contingents of Fulfulde, Tamashek, and Hassaniya Arabic speakers). It reflects the colorful speaking style and ethnohistorical content of a veteran marabou (holy man).

The recordings and Mama Kouata's handwritten transcriptions are archived at Deep Blue Data, University of Michigan Libraries at this link:

https://deepblue.lib.umich.edu/data/concern/data_sets/6682x500d?locale=en

The DOI is <https://doi.org/10.7302/c8ar-6855>

The 2021 Tiéyaxo recordings

A few recordings in what appears to be Tiéyaxo were made opportunistically by project manager Djiguiba in Bamako in 2021. They have not been studied by the author but will be deposited in Deep Blue along with the other audio files.

2021-01 fishing
03:53
2021-02 circumcision and marriage
03:33
2021-03 hippo hunt
02:50
2021-04 boat building
05:28

Relevant documentary videos

Some users of these recordings may be mainly interested in the cultural content, including Bozo material culture. Among the many short documentary-style videos that have been produced by

the author and project manager Djiguiba, the most relevant to the audio recordings are those on boat-building and fishing. These can easily be found in the collection “Mali documentary videos from 2023”, DOI 10.7302/4851-2c52. The url is this:

<https://deepblue.lib.umich.edu/data/dashboard/collections/70795840p?locale=en>

Funding

The fieldwork on Tigemaxo was part of a project involving four Bozo languages. The other three Bozo languages studied have been Cliffs Jenaama, Jenaama/Sorogaama of Djenné, and Kelenga. The project was funded by National Science Foundation, Documenting Endangered Languages program, grant PD-1941828 (2020-2025).

Transcription of 2022 Tigemaxo texts from Dia

Text 2022-02

Women's life then and now

recorded in Dia, 2022

file 180103_0023

duration 05:38

transcribable portion 00:16 – 05:38

speakers and their abbreviations in order of appearance:

Koono Kouanda (K), female

Fada Songomo (F), female

topics:

00:16-01:12	initiation rituals then and now
01:12-02:30	guarding orchards and gardens
02:30-04:05	girls before marriage
04:05-05:38	garments of newly married women

(00:16) K ... sólè, sáálì kóyɲ-jùḏⁿ-yè ná bày,
... cook, until initiation-child-Pl Sbjn exit(v).Pfv,
gúrúfú [yé gùrúfú], [kóyɲ-jùḏɲ kḏḏn] túùn dì lóḏ,
group.& [and group], [initiation-child alone] Past IpfvNeg enter.Ipfv,
K: '... cook. Eventually the initiated children emerge, by groups. A single initiation novice would not go in.'

[initiation (circumcision/excision) novices emerged after a 15-day recovery period; children were initiated in groups, not individually; gúrúfú < Fr. groupe]

(00:20) K [wáy ɲà] yá= à ná àn lèmà,
[today QTop] if 3Sg if.Pfv 2Sg please.Pfv,
[áj gá [àɲ jùḏɲ kḏḏn-sìrè] lóḏ]
[2Sg Ipfv [2Sg child by.oneself] put.in.Ipfv]

K: 'These days, if you-Sg like, you-Sg (will) put in (=initiate) your child by him-/her-self.'

[lémá 'please' as transitive, §17.4.5.3; kóón-síré, §19.3.2.4]

(00:22) K [áj gá à fáy-nī [áj jāⁿ]],
 [2Sg Ipfv 3Sg sit-Caus.Ipfv [2Sg house]],
 [dépààⁿsí fí] dī yēē,
 [expense any] not.be.Loc therein,
 K: ‘You-Sg (will) have him/her sit (=stay) in your-Sg house. There are no costs therein.’

[Fr. dépense; jāⁿ triggers (H)L-to-(L)H Shift; so does yēē but not here due to LH-tone before dí]

(00:25) K [yé fààà] dí kòóⁿ nī
 [and firstly] not.be.Cop one it.is
 F [ŋōròò tí] gá á xààyî ↑,
 [Dem.Def meaning] Ipfv 3Sg show.Ipfv,

K: ‘(Today) and in the old days were not the same.’

F: ‘That shows it, (that) ...’

[understood left conjunct omitted, §7.1.5; kòóⁿ as predicate nominal, §4.6.1.1; tīⁿ]

(00:29) F sāw̄, [kóyn-lòy]-gù gáánà fùòrì-yà,
 now, [initiation]-Def Pfv be.lightweight-Inch.Pfv,
 bí xèlè, [ján-sìgè-gù gā],
 Seq pass, [marriage-Def Dat],

F: ‘... now(adays), the initiation rite has become lightweight (=neglected), more than the marriage rite.’

[fúórí-yá inchoative (variant of fúóra) cf. modifying adjective fúóríⁿ ; bí xèlè, §12.1.1.2]

(00:34) F [ján-sìgè-gù rōò] cìè-nà
 [marriage-Def Foc] become.heavy.Pfv

K àywà yà= [á ñà fìèⁿ] yàà [dé sàdà rōò] nī,
 well if [3Sg QTop all] become.Pfv [for herd Foc] it.is,

F: ‘It’s the marriage (rite) [focus] that has become heavy (=more significant).’

K: ‘Well, if they (initiation and marriage rites) have both become major events, ...’

[-gù rōò, §13.1.1; sádá ‘herd, big group’, here referring to the large number of attendees and consequent costs of feeding]

(00:39) K a! yé [fò máàn] kì lááfíé-nì,
 ah if [thing Rel] 1PlIn relax-Caus.Pfv,
 kí gú lò [[ŋōòòò lòò] fáà].
 1PlIn Fut enter.Pfv [[DemDef entrance] by],

K: ‘Ah, if (there is) something that gives us relief, we (inclusive) will enter (it) by that entrance.’

(00:58) K [àlì yé nà bày]
 [even 3Pl Sbjn exit(v).Pfv]
 [àlá= àⁿ nà [múò tòn] lò]
 [even 2Sg if.Pfv [person ten] put.in.Pfv]
 K: ‘Even if they emerge, even if you-Sg initiate ten people (=children), ...’
 [*‘even if’ (see also @ 01:07 below), §16.2.1*]

(00:59) K [áj gá [yé ʃìèⁿ fáy-nà= [áj jāⁿ]]
 [2Sg Ipfv [3Pl all] sit-Caus.Ipfv [2Sg house]]
 [áj gá à sólṣṣ]
 [2Sg Ipfv 3Sg cook.Ipfv]
 K: ‘... you-Sg will lodge them all at your-Sg house (that night). You will cook it (=food).’
 [*Ipfv fáy-nī*]

(01:00) K [áj gá jìè láà [à gà] [áj jāⁿ],
 [2Sg Ipfv food give.Ipfv [3Sg Dat] [2Sg house],
 ŋūḍn dí màá mēē [[ján-sìgè rṓḍ] níṅī],
 DemDef IpfvNeg be.able.Ipfv be.done.well.Ipfv [[marriage Foc] inside],
 K: ‘You-Sg will give food to him/her at your house. That can’t be done (=doesn’t happen) in marriage ceremonies.’
 [*Ipfv lāā, Ipfv māā*]

(01:04) K [wáy ṅà] [[ján-sìgè rṓḍ] yáà [dé sàdà nī]]
 [today QTop] [[marriage Foc] become.Pfv [for herd it.is]]
 [yá= á dì ŋūḍⁿ nī] [fánááⁿ húnùⁿ]
 [if 3Sg not.be.Cop DemDef it.is] [firstly Top]
 K: ‘Nowadays it’s marriage rites [focus] that have become major events. Otherwise, as for the old days, ...’

(01:07) K [kóyn-lòy rṓḍ] túùṅ gá sàdà nī,
 [initiation Foc] Past be.Cop herd it.is,
 [àlì yé [áj jùḍⁿ] fâà [bì kóyn-lòy]
 [even if [2Sg child] as [Seq do.initiation.Pfv]
 K: ‘... the initiation rite used to be the major event. Even when they were scheduled to initiate your-Sg child, ...’
 [*fâà plus sequential, §15.2.16; kóyn-lòy ‘initiation’ as verb, §9.5.7*]

(01:09) K [áj gá à sóxòláàⁿ],
 [2Sg Ipfv 3Sg worry.Pfv],
 [[ján-sìgè ród] túùg gá [kúù jíyòⁿ nī]
 [[marriage Foc] Past be.Cop [day three] it.is]
 K: ‘... you-Sg would be worried (about the expense). A marriage ceremony was
 (only) three days, ...’
 [sóxòláàⁿ ‘worry (n)’ as verb, §9.5.7]

(01:12) K [kóyn-lòy gá [kúù táⁿ-yη-kólòⁿ nī
 [initiation be.Cop [day ten-and-five] it.is
 F ηūòⁿ ná bày yēē, ηgàáyèè sāw,
 DemDef if.Pfv exit(v).Pfv therein, like now,
 K: ‘... (whereas) an initiation rite was fifteen days.’
 F: ‘After (=aside from) that, like now(adays), ...’
 [past morpheme túùⁿ omitted in K’s turn because the time frame was established in the
 preceding segment; Pfv bày → bày before yēē, §3.1.3.5.3]

(01:17) F [kí xày] [[cìe-sèwè ród] níjīī] sāw,
 [1PIIn Prsntv] [[field-matter Foc] inside] now,
 cìe-gù, fánááⁿ, cìe-gù gá ìη kóórì [míénàà nód],
 field-Def, firstly, field-Def Ipfv Refl enclose.Ipfv [how? Foc],
 F: ‘Here we are, (talking) now on the subject of fields (=farming). The field, in the
 old days, how was the field enclosed (fenced off)?’
 [presentative xāy, §4.4.3.1; míénāā, §13.2.2.6]

(01:24) F yé [sāw kóórì-m-béénàà],
 and [today enclose.VblN-Link-manner],
 ηūòⁿ-yà= á kòòⁿ-yè níⁿ nà
 DemDef-Pl be.Cop one-Pl it.is Q
 F: ‘(That) and the (type of) enclosure of now(adays), were those the same?’
 [kōōⁿ ‘one’ as predicate nominal, here pluralized, §4.6.1.1]

(01:27) K yè dí kòòⁿ nī, fánááⁿ,
 3Pl not.be.Cop one it.is, firstly,
 [[lémú nód] gá ìn lēē]
 [[matting Foc] Ipfv Refl pick.up.Ipfv]
 K: ‘They weren’t the same. In the old days, it was straw matting [focus] that was
 taken (=used).’

(01:30) K [áj gá [àn cíè] kóórī],
 [2Sg Ipfv [2Sg field] enclose.Ipfv],
 [áj gá [àn xàyɲ ʃìèŋ] xáyⁿ,
 [2Sg Ipfv [2Sg work(n) all] work(v).Ipfv,
 K: ‘You-Sg would enclose (=fence off) your field (with it). You would do all your work.’
[verb xáyⁿ ‘work’, Ipfv here “reset” from xāyⁿ to xáyⁿ]

(01:32) K ńkàà ñūðm bàárà [xáy òì [kú-nú jìrì-jùðŋ-gìè]
 but DemDef find.Pfv [1PlIn IpfvNeg [Dem-Link tree-child-Pl]
 tìbî tèmè], áⁿ ná júó-jùðŋ tìbì ↑,
 transplant.Ipfv also], 2Sg if.Pfv onion transplant.Pfv
 K: ‘But it happened then that we (inclusive) didn’t use to transplant these saplings. If you-Sg transplanted onions, ...’
[saplings of mango, jujube, etc.]

(01:36) K [júó-jùðⁿ ná xàlè]
 [onion if.Pfv pass.Pfv]
 múðⁿ [kóóŋ-kòðⁿ nóð lámà] túùŋ gá jìrì tìbî,
 1PlEx [Iter-one Foc only] Pat Ipfv tree transplant.Ipfv,
 K: ‘When onion (season) was over, we (exclusive) used to transplant trees only occasionally [focus].’
[kóóŋ-kòðⁿ, §4.6.1.7]

(01:40) K [[wáy ñà húnù] [dùⁿyààŋ ʃìèⁿ ↑], báy wáy]
 [[today QTop Top] [world all], exit(v).Pfv today]
 ʃíéŋ gá [nàkóó ród] xāyⁿ,
 all Ipfv [garden Foc] work(v).Ipfv,
 K: ‘These days, everyone has exited (=abandoned transplanting). Everyone works (=cultivates) gardens.’
[dry-season gardens (nàkóó) contain fruit trees and vegetable crops; they use water from wells or they are set up in receding floodplains]

(01:44) K [àlá = à túùⁿ ná àn lèmà]
 [even 3Sg Past if.Pfv 2Sg please.Pfv]
 [fànààⁿ án dá = á sàndòò]
 [firstly 2Sg IpfvNeg 3Sg fence(v).Ipfv]
 K: ‘If you liked, in the old days you wouldn’t fence it off.’
[sàndó ‘fence off (garden, field)’; fencing off gardens was formerly not obligatory since there were few sheep and goats and little theft by people; lémá ‘become sweet, pleasing’, here treated like stative léⁿ ‘be sweet’ and so combinable with past túùⁿ]

(01:46) K fòy dī bààⁿyî yēē,
 nothing IpfvNeg be.ruined.Ipfv therein
 [wáyè àlì yá= àⁿ nà á sàndò]
 [today even if 2Sg if.Pfv 3Sg fence(v).Pfv]
 K: ‘Nothing would be damaged in it (=garden). Nowadays, even if you-Sg fence it off, ...’

(01:48) K [[bááⁿyí-fó ródò] gà á bààⁿyî]
 [[damage-thing Foc] Ipfv 3Sg ruin.Ipfv]
 F yé kòrìnààm-bóló-giè ná bè [kòrì [xà gā]],
 if help(n)-mate-Pl if.Pfv come.Pfv [help.Pfv [2Pl Dat]],
 K: ‘... something harmful will damage it.’
 F: ‘If helpers come and help you-Pl, ...’
[irregular compound < kórí ‘help’ and bólò]

(01:53) F yá= á [fòⁿ máàṅ-giè] láà [xà gá] gù,
 3Pl Ipfv [thing Rel-Pl] give.Ipfv [2Pl Dat] Def,
 [xá gá mēé ródò]—, yà= á—,
 [2Pl Ipfv agree.Ipfv Foc] —, (false start)—,
 F: ‘... the things that they give to you-Pl, do you-Pl make an agreement?’
[refers to NGO or government projects; definite gú at end of relative clause, §14.1.2; clause-final focus ródò in interrogative (see also the next segment)]

(01:56) F [yè gá— á bààⁿyî [xà fáà] rà]
 [3Pl Ipfv— 3Sg ruin.Ipfv [2Pl by] Q]
 [tì yé gà míé-nī [xà fáà] ródò]
 [or 3Pl Ipfv be.well.done-Caus.Ipfv [2Pl by] Foc]
 F: ‘Do they damage it on you-Pl? Or do they do it well for you-Pl?’
[tì ‘or’ (in questions), §13.2.1.4]

(02:00) K yè= é nà bà= [á là [xà gá]] rà,
 if 3Pl if.Pfv come.Pfv [3Sg give.Pfv [2Pl Dat]] Q,
 F àⁿhóⁿ
 yes
 K: ‘When they come and give it to you-Pl?’
 F: ‘Uh-huh.’

(02:02) K xá bàánà-giè
 2Pl only-Pl
 F pándóòⁿ [yé [ɪŋ ʃìì-giè]]
 panel [and [Refl complement-Pl]]

K: ‘You-Pl exclusively.’

F: ‘A (solar) panel and so forth.’

[K and F overlap here; bàánà, §19.3.2.5; Fr panneau solaire]

(02:04) F yè= é nà bà= [á là [xà gā]],
 if 3Pl if.Pfv come.Pfv [3Sg give.Pfv [2Pl Dat]],
 yé→ jìrì-jùòŋ-gíé [yé [ɪŋ ʃìì-giè]]
 and tree-child-Pl.& [and [Refl complement-Pl]]

F: ‘When they come and give it to you-Pl. Along with saplings (for transplanting) and so forth.’

(02:07) F [yá= [àŋ jìrì-jùòⁿ] nà méè]
 [if [2Sg tree-child] if.Pfv be.sweet.Pfv]
 ā nà síŋè [néfêè mā],
 3Sg if.Pfv arrive.Pfv [benefit against],

F: ‘If your-Sg (fruit) tree turns out well, and it leads to a benefit, ...’

[néfêè]

(02:09) F óòⁿ, [sáálà= àⁿ ná àŋ kírè]
 uh.huh, [until 2Sg if.Pfv 2Sg get.Pfv]
 [yé gà síŋēē [à má] rà]
 [3Pl Ipv arrive.Ipv [3Sg against] Q]

F: ‘Uh-huh, by the time you-Sg are finished, do they get to it (=tree)?’

[kírè ‘get’, as reflexive verb ‘be finished’; ‘they’ here means animals, thieves, etc., who consume the fruit before it can be harvested]

(02:11) F tì yé dī síŋā= [à mā]
 or 3Pl IpvNeg arrive.Ipv [3Sg against]
 K yá= àⁿ ná [àŋ cíè] kóórì némēēⁿ,
 if 2Sg if.Pfv [2Sg field] enclose.Pfv a.lot,

F: ‘Or do they not get to it?’

K: ‘If you-Sg have fenced your field thoroughly, ...’

(02:15) K [áj gá á xàyⁿ [xééré níjī]]
 [2Sg Ipfv 3Sg work.Ipfv [well.being inside]]
 [áj gá á bàà [xééré níjī]]
 [2Sg Ipfv 3Sg take.out.Ipfv [well.being inside]]
 K: ‘... you-Sg (will) work it in comfort (=without trouble), you (will) pick it (=fruit) in comfort.’
 [Ipfv xāyⁿ and bāā ; xééré]

(02:17) K [yá= á dì ŋūðⁿ nī] [fánááⁿ húnù]
 [if 3Sg not.be.Cop DemDef it.is] [firstly Top]
 àlì yá= àn dà= á sàndòð,
 even if 2Sg IpfvNeg 3Sg fence.Ipfv,
 K: ‘Otherwise (=by contrast), in the old days, even if you-Sg didn’t fence it off, ...’

(02:20) K fòy dà= à kírēē, [wáy húnù]
 nothing IpfvNeg 3Sg get.Ipfv, [today Top]
 yá= àⁿ [àⁿ fàà] xàri ródò,
 if 2Sg [2Sg belt] tie.Pfv Foc,
 K: ‘... nothing would get it (=fruit). Nowadays if you-Sg tie on your belt (=buckle up to work), ...’
 [clause-final focus particle]

(02:22) K [[áⁿ fàà] xàri] [áⁿ ná á sàndò némēē],
 [[2Sg belt] tie.Pfv] [2Sg Sbjn 3Sg fence.Pfv a.lot],
 [áj gá á lòð [xééré ý]]
 [2Sg Ipfv 3Sg put.in.Ipfv [well.being Loc]]
 K: ‘Tie on your belt and fence it (garden) in thoroughly. (Then) you-Sg (will) put it in (=plant it) in comfort, ...’
 [subjunctive clause as second imperative, §10.4.1.2]

(02:24) K [áj gá á bàà [xééré ý]],
 [2Sg Ipfv 3Sg take.out.Ipfv [well.being Loc]],
 ŋōròð nī
 DemDef it.is
 K: ‘... and you-Sg (will) take it out (=pick the fruit) in comfort. That’s it.’

(02:30) F àywà [ŋūðn tèmè xwáà] à ná bày yēē,
 well [DemDem also again] 3Sg if.Pfv exit.Pfv therein,
 fánááⁿ, yáálú-ńúóⁿ miyòðŋ-giè, gúrúfú-gù,
 firstly, woman-Dimin small-Pl, group-Def,
 F: ‘Well, when that too has passed (=aside from that), in the old days, young (=unmarried) girls, a group (of them).’
 [Pfv bày → bàý before yēē, §3.1.3.5.3]

(02:34) F xónómòṅṅò [à =á bàáràà [xónómòṅṅò gá gṵ]],
 old.person [3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv [old.person be.Loc there.Def]],
 yà= =á sàà [[ṅúó-ní xòṅmòṅṅò kóṱⁿ] fāⁿ],
 3Pl Ipfv lie.down.Ipfv [[DemDef-Link old.person one] chez],
 F: ‘An old person (=old woman), there happened to be an old woman there. They
 (=girls) would go to bed at the place of that one old woman ...’
[Ipfv sãā (here as simple intransitive rather than reflexive)]

(02:40) F sáálà= àli yè ján-sìgè, yé [=è ján-sìgè]
 until until 3Pl marry.Pfv, if [3Pl marriage]
 fâà [bì síṅè],
 as [Seq arrive.Pfv],
 F: ‘... until they got married. As their marriage was about to arrive, ...’
[fâà plus sequential VP, §15.2.17]

(02:42) F à =á bàáràà [ṅúó-ní xòṅmòṅṅò-gù máàⁿ]
 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv [DemDef-Link old.person-Def Rel]
 [yē tū̀ṅ gá [[ṅúó-ní xòṅmòṅṅò-gù máàⁿ] fáj] gù],
 [3Pl Past be.Loc [[DemDef-Link old.person-Def Rel] chez]
 Def].
 F: ‘... it would happen that that old woman, that old woman at whose place they
 used to be, ...’
[< fāⁿ, with definite gú at end of relative clause]

(02:45) F yà= á tààsá lēē ↑,
 3Pl Ipfv bowl pick.up.Ipfv,
 yē gá sá= [á là [ṅū̀ṅ gā]],
 3Pl Ipfv go.Ipfv [3Sg give.Pfv] [DemDef Dat],
 F: ‘... they would take a bowl, and they would go and give it (=bowl) to that one
 (=old woman).’
*[táásā ; < jóò á là ; the girls would give the old woman one of the bowls they had
 received as wedding gifts]*

(02:47) F yē gá á sēē wāā [xá yé xàⁿ],
 3Pl Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv hello! [2Pl and work(n)],
 [áⁿ [mú̀ṱ jù̀ṱⁿ] mārà] [wáy ṅū̀ṅ gá [mìénàà nó̀ṱ]]
 [2Sg [1PlEx child] raise.Pfv] [today DemDef be [how? Foc]]
 F: ‘They would say, “hello, you-Pl and work! (=thank you!) You-Sg have raised
 our (exclusive) child.” How is that (situation) today?’
*[wāā before another greeting, §19.5.1; “you-Pl and work(n)” as greeting, §19.5.3;
 mìénā ‘how?’, §13.2.2.6]*

(02:51) K [inaudible, then:] [fánaáⁿ húnù] hósóláárí-yá túùŋ gá gō,
 [firstly Top] trust(n) Past be.Loc there.Def,
 múḍ-gìè, à =á bàáràà [yáálú-ǰúsⁿ mìyḍḍⁿ]
 person-Pl, 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv [woman-Dimin small]
 K: ‘In the old days there used to be trust. The people. It would happen that the young girls, ...’
 [hósóláárí-yá with abstractive suffix, < Fulfulde hoolaare]

(02:56) K [múḍ táⁿ-ỳŋ-kólòⁿ] [múḍ tàṁ-àndèèⁿ]
 [person ten-and-five] [person ten-two]
 [ā ʃìèŋ] gá sàá [gèrè ñ-kóòⁿ],
 [3Sg all] Ipfv lie.down.Ipfv [place Link-one],
 K: ‘... fifteen (or) twenty (of them), all of them would go to bed in one (=the same) place.’

(02:59) K [[[xá ʃíéŋ] gùrùfú-gù] gá bày bólēē]
 [[[2Pl all] group-Def] Ipfv exit.Ipfv together]
 [[xá ʃíéⁿ] =á lòò bólēē],
 [[2Pl all] Ipfv enter.Ipfv together,
 K: ‘The group of you all (=you all as a group) would go out together, (and) you-Pl would go in together.’
 [Ipfv bāy, l55]

(03:02) K wáy sáá-xóó ʃî, bá= [á sàbàbù] yáà]
 today lie.down.VbIN-house get.up.Pfv, Seq [3Sg reason] put.Pfv]
 múḍ-gìè kónà,
 person-Pl fear(v).Pfv,
 K: ‘Nowadays the sleeping room (for the girls) has been lifted (=is no longer practiced), for the reason that the people became afraid.’
 [sáá-xóó; sáábū (possessed sàbàbù)]

(03:06) K [áⁿ ñá] [[áŋ júóⁿ] ná bày wáy]
 [2Sg QTop] [[2Sg child] if.Pfv exit(v).Pfv today]
 kónà gá [àn tē],
 fear(n) be.Loc [2Sg Dat],
 K: ‘As for you-Sg, if your child (=daughter) goes out these days, you-Sg are afraid.’

(03:19) K [wáy yáálà= àⁿ ná à gàrdí],
 [today must 2Sg Sbjn 3Sg watch.over.Pfv],
 η̄n̄d̄d̄ bè [[η̄n̄d̄n̄ ʃìén] tííⁿ],
 DemDef.Foc come.Pfv [[DemDef all] under],
 K: ‘You must watch over her. That (situation) is what has brought all that (about).’
 [yáálì plus subjunctive, §17.4.6.2]

(03:22) K fánááⁿ η̄á húnù yór̄d̄, [hóóláárí-yá ráà=] =á bō,
 firstly QTop Top self, [trust-Abst Foc] be.Loc here,
 [[yáálú-ńúóⁿ mìȳd̄d̄n̄ ʃià=] =á bày bóìēē]
 [[woman-Dimin small all] Ipfv exit.Ipfv together]
 K: ‘In the old days, there was trust here. Young girls would go out together, ...’
 [ʃyéⁿ ‘all’; Ipfv bāy]

(03:26) K [kyá= =á ʃíégèè bóìēē] [kyá= =á bóìd̄ làd̄î],
 [1PIIn Ipfv return.Ipfv together] [1PIIn Ipfv Recip advise.Ipfv],
 [ʃíéŋ gá ìŋ kúnāā
 [all Ipfv Refl swear.Ipfv
 [[ìŋ [ján-síégé]-tàà] ìⁿ má jāyⁿ],
 [[Logo [marriage]-day] Logo Proh be.shamed.Pfv],
 K: ‘... (and) we (inclusive) would come back together. Everyone would swear that
 she would not be shamed (=dishonored) on her marriage day.’
 [< kí gá ‘all’; Ipfv bāy]

(03:30) K [wáy η̄n̄d̄d̄ bày gō]
 [today DemDef.Foc exit(v).Pfv there.Def]
 [yà= á nà bàárà wáy]
 [if 3Sg if.Pfv happen.Pfv today]
 K: ‘Nowadays that [focus] has exited (=disappeared). If it happened (to take place)
 nowadays, ...’
 [dubitative conditional antecedent]

(03:33) K [[àl wáy] η̄n̄d̄— η̄n̄d̄n̄ gá gō]
 [[until today] DemDef— DemDef be.Loc there.Def]
 [ʃìèŋ gá [ìŋ [[ján-síégé]-tàà] sóxòlààⁿ],
 [all Ipfv [Refl [[marriage]-day] worry(n)],
 K: ‘... (so that) even now that (behavior) was there (=was practiced), (and) every
 (girl) worried about her marriage day, ...’
 [sóxòlààⁿ ‘worry (n)’ with implied verb]

(03:36) K bááⁿyín túùn dì bì bé yēē,
 damage Past IpfvNeg Fut come.Pfv therein,
 [fánaáⁿ [yáálú-ṗúśⁿ mỳdòḏⁿ nòḏ] gá àlá ṅḏḏréè]
 [firstly [woman-Dimin small Foc] Ipfv God beg.Ipfv]
 K: ‘... then trouble would not come (=arise) there. In the old days, young girls used to pray to God.’
 [á]lā]

(03:39) K àywà kí xóró-yá [bólò má] dè,
 well 1PlIn difficult-Inch.Pfv [Recip on] Emph,
 [kí [ján-sígé]-tàà] [[kí náⁿ] má jāyⁿ],
 [1PlIn [marriage]-day] [[1PlIn mother] Proh be.shamed.Pfv],
 K: ‘Well, we sure were hard on each other, lest (on) our marriage day our mother(s) be shamed.’
 [prohibitive clause as ‘lest’]

(03:43) K [kí [ján-sígé]-tàà] kí— [[kí [hóró-yá]-m-bóló-yè máà =]
 [1PlIn [marriage]-day] 1PlIn— [[1PlIn [noble-Abstr]-Link-mate-Pl Rel
 á [[kì xórò] y]] [[yé tòmó] mà íṅ jùúni],
 be.Loc [1PlIn back] Loc]] [[3Pl head] Proh Refl lower.Pfv],
 K: ‘(On) our marriage day, our (inclusive) freeborn companions who were behind (=younger than) us, their head(s) must not be lowered (in shame).’
 [i.e. if a girl is shamed on her marriage day, the shame extends to the other girls in her group; tómō]

(03:46) K [[kyá = =á sàà [máàáṅ jāⁿ]] tòmó]
 [[1PlIn be.Loc lie.down.Ipfv [Rel house]] head]
 mà íṅ jùúni, wáy ṅūḏm bày gō,
 Proh Refl lower.Pfv, today DemDef exit.Pfv there.Def,
 K: ‘The head of the one (=old woman) in whose house we would go to bed must not be lowered (in shame). Today that has gone out there (=no longer exists).’
 [headless possessor relative]

(03:50) K fáán dí yèè xwáà, [kū-ṅūḏn dí yēē]
 caring(n) not.be.Loc therein again, [whatchamacallit not.be.Loc therein]
 [kyá = =á bólò súúrdāāⁿ [à xúmà]],
 [1PlIn Ipfv Recip cover.up.Ipfv [3Sg on]],
 K: ‘There is no caring therein (=about it) any more. There is no whatchamacallit therein. We cover each other up about it.’
 [‘no longer’, §19.3.1.3]

(03:53) K η̄r̄d̄d̄ gáánà bè [dùⁿyààm bàⁿyìⁿ],
 DemDef.Foc Pfv come.Pfv [world ruin.Pfv],
 [yá= á dì η̄ūⁿ nī] fánááⁿ
 [if 3Sg not.be.Cop DemDef it.is] firstly
 K: ‘That [focus] is what has come and ruined the world. By contrast, in the old days,
 ...’

(03:55) K [yè [máàn túùⁿ ná lò [[lèéfù η-kóóⁿ] ȳ]]
 [if [Rel Past if.Pfv enter.Pfv] [[shame(n) Link-one] Loc]]
 [mó-ǰì múròò tèmè] dì [àⁿ mā]
 [person-any need also] not.be.Loc [2Sg against]
 K: ‘... if there was anyone (=you) who went into (=suffered) a humiliation, nobody
 had any need for you-Sg.’
[2Sg agreement for generic referent; mó-ǰì < múd ǰì]

(03:59) K wáy η̄ñd̄d̄ bày gō, [η̄ñd̄d̄ nī]
 today DemDef.Foc exit(v).Pfv there.Def, [DemDef.Foc it.is]
 álá má dùⁿyàm bàⁿyìⁿ [kì xúmà]
 God Proh world ruin.Pfv [1PlIn on]
 K: ‘Nowadays that has exited there (=disappeared). That’s it. May God not ruin the
 world on us!’

(04:05) F àywà [η̄ūⁿ tèmè] ná bày yēē, fánááⁿ—
 well [DemDef also] if.Pfv exit(v).Pfv there.Def, firstly—
 fánááⁿ, yá= àⁿ nà ján-sìgè,
 firstly, if 2Sg if.Pfv marry.Pfv,
 F: ‘Well, aside from that, in the old days, when you-Sg got married, ...’

(04:09) F yè gá [bòlòbà ród̄] làá [àη gā],
 3Pl Ipfv [sleeveless.boubou Foc] give.Ipfv [2Sg Dat],
 áη gá á sāā [[àη xààⁿ] ȳⁿ]
 2Sg Ipfv 3Sg put.on.Ipfv [[2Sg neck] Loc]
 F: ‘... they would give you-Sg a sleeveless boubou (=garment). You-Sg would wear
 it on your neck (=over your body).’
*[bólóbá (< Bambara), sleeveless garment with open sides, worn by pulling it down over
 one’s head; [àⁿ xààⁿ] ȳⁿ, §8.2.4.5]*

(04:13) F [yè xwáà ná ìṅ kírè] [yè xwáà =á bì
 [3Pl again if.Pfv Refl finish.Pfv] [3Pl again Ipfv Fut
 júú-màṅèèrè-ṅúòṅ lèwà= [àn tē],
 garment-design-Dimin sew.Pfv [2Sg Dat],
 F: ‘When they had finished (doing that), they would proceed to sew a garment with
 a design for you-Sg.’
 [júú-màṅèèrè (*design often embroidered*); léwé]

(04:17) F á= =á bì ṅūḍⁿ— wⁿóyéⁿ— júú—
 2Sg Ipfv Fut DemDef— new.wife— garment—
 á= =á bì [ṅūḍṅ tèmè] lò [[ṅūḍm bùú] tīⁿ],
 2Sg Ipfv Fut [DemDef again] put.in.Pfv [[DemDef rear] under],
 F: ‘You-Sg would put that (garment) on under that one (=sleeveless boubou).’
 [*the first part of this segment is garbled*]

(04:20) F á= =á bì bòlòbà-gù lò [à xúmà],
 2Sg Ipfv Fut sleeveless.boubou-Def put.in.Pfv [3Sg on],
 á= =á bì kóbá-tààbè là= [à mā],
 2Sg Ipfv Fut wrap(n) put.in.Pfv [3Sg against],
 F: ‘You-Sg would put the sleeveless boubou on over it. They would put a *koba* wrap
 over it.’
 [*kóbá-tààbè, traditional woman’s wrap (táábè) in cotton, directly woven by weavers*]

(04:23) F sāw ṅūḍṅ gá mienāā
 now DemDef be.Cop how?
 K wáy xáy ṅūḍⁿ yáà [[gáwá-yà ród] nī],
 today 1PlIn DemDef put.Pfv [[hick-Abstr Foc] it.is],
 F: ‘Nowadays, how is that?’
 K: ‘Nowadays we (inclusive) consider that to be country-hick behavior.’
 [*gāwā ‘hick, country bumpkin’ (out of date with modern times)*]

(04:26) K xáy ṅūḍⁿ yáà dē, yá= àⁿ nà—
 1PlIn DemDef put.Pfv for, if 2Sg if.Pfv—
 [[máàṅ ṣìèⁿ] ná ṅūḍṅ lò wáy]
 [[Rel all] if.Pfv DemDef put.in.Pfv today]
 F: ‘We (inclusive) consider that as, if you-Sg—, (if there was) anyone who wore
 that nowadays, ...’

(04:28) K yē wō [kù húnù] dì— dúⁿyááⁿ fáàmúùⁿ,
 3Pl said [Dem Top] IpfvNeg world understand.Ipfv,
 wáȳ [àlì yá= àⁿ nà= á là [[àṅ jùḍṅ] gā]]
 today [even if 2Sg if.Pfv 3Sg give.Pfv [[2Sg child] Dat]]
 K: ‘They would say, that (person) doesn’t understand the (modern) world.
 Nowadays, (even) if you-Sg gave it to your child (=daughter), ...’
[prequotative wō, §17.1.2]

(04:31) K ā dì bà= á sàà [[ìṅ xààⁿ ȳⁿ],
 3Sg IpfvNeg Fut 3Sg put.on.Pfv [[Refl neck] Loc],
 [yá= á dì ṅūḍⁿ nī] fánááⁿ
 [if 3Sg not.be.Cop DemDef it.is] firstly
 K: ‘... she wouldn’t put it on (over her head). By contrast, in the old days, ...’

(04:34) K [bólóbá [yé ìṅ kájààwá]]
 [sleeveless.boubou [and Refl tunic]]
 [á= =á ṅṛḍḍ sàá [[àṅ xààⁿ ȳⁿ]]
 [2Sg Ipfv DemDef.Foc put.on [[2Sg neck] Loc]]
 K: ‘... the sleeveless boubou and the tunic, that [focus] is what you would put on,
 ...’
[kájààwá, sleeveless with open sides like bólóbá, but only came down to the waist, §7.1.5]

(04:36) K [àli [[àṅ kándìⁿ] só bày [tàà máàⁿ]],
 [until [[2Sg bridesmaid] go.Pfv exit.Pfv [day Rel]]],
 [jíéṅ gú à tóó-yà] [kwá= =á [wⁿḍyèⁿ nód] nī],
 [all Fut 3Sg know-Inch.Pfv] [Dem be.Cop [new.wife Foc] it.is],
 K: ‘... until the day (when) your bridesmaid leaves. (Then) everyone will recognize
 that this one is a newly married woman [focus].’
*[another unmarried girl attended the bride for two weeks after the wedding, after which
 the bride was recognized as a legitimate newly married woman; tóó-yà, §9.3.4.1]*

(04:39) K wáȳ ṅūḍⁿ dì gō, [wáȳ àⁿ ná wⁿḍyèṅ xáȳ]
 today DemDef not.be.Loc there, [today 2Sg if.Pfv new.wife see.Pfv]
 àlì àn dí
 even 2Sg IpfvNeg
 [yé [yààlù-ṅúóⁿ mìyḍḍⁿ-yè] nàám] bāā,
 [and [woman-Dimin small-Pl] between] take.out.Ipfv,
 K: ‘Nowadays that doesn’t exist. Nowadays, when you-Sg see a newly married
 woman, you-Sg don’t (=can’t) even distinguish between her and young
 (=unmarried) girls.’
[understood left conjunct omitted, §7.1.5]

(05:03) K tómó-xóló-nì, yé kì wō [kyá= =á bì
 head-big-Caus.VblN, if 1PlIn said [1PlIn Ipfv Fut
 kí yáà [dē, fɔ̃ⁿ nī]]
 1PlIn transform.Pfv [for, thing it.is]]
 K: ‘Arrogance, if we (inclusive) say (=think), “we (inclusive) will turn ourselves
 into a thing, ...’
[reflexive construction]

(05:05) FK [álá dí [fɔ̃ⁿ máàⁿ] wàlè]
 [God PfvNeg [thing Rel] do.Pfv]
 ηḡnḡḡ bè [[séwè-gù]ién] tīⁿ]
 DemDef.Foc come.Pfv [[matter-Def all] under]
 K: ‘... something that God didn’t make. That [focus] is what has brought about the
 whole matter (=situation).’

(05:06) K [yá= á dì ηḡḡⁿ nī] [àl wáy]
 [if 3Sg IpfvNeg DemDef it.is] [until today]
 yé kì nà]íégè [[in láàndá-gù] mā]
 if 1PlIn if.Pfv return.Pfv [[Refl custom-Def] against]
 K: ‘Otherwise, as of nowadays, if we return to our traditional custom, ...’

(05:09) K dúⁿyááj gú mēè
 world Fut be.well.done
 F àywà [ηḡḡⁿ ηáj] kì—, ηḡḡn dí [kì dámbèèⁿ] nī wù,
 well (false start)—, DemDef not.be.Cop [1PlIn tradition] it.is alas,
 K: ‘... the world will be turn out well.’
 F: ‘Well, that—, that is not our traditional way, alas.’
[clause-final emphatic wú ‘alas!’, §19.4.1.7]

(05:13) F [ηḡḡⁿ ηà] dí [kì dámbèèⁿ] nī,
 [DemDef QTop] not.be.Cop [1PlIn tradition] it.is,
 [[kí dámbèèⁿ] gá [fɔ̃ⁿ máàⁿ] nī]
 [[1PlIn tradition] be.Cop [thing Rel] it.is]
 F: ‘That is not our traditional way. The thing that is our traditional way, ...’

(05:16) F [kyá= =á]íjì [ηḡḡnḡḡ fáà]],
 [1PlIn Ipfv walk.Ipfv [DemDef.Foc by]],
 ηḡnḡḡ léj [kì tē],
 DemDef.Foc be.sweet [1Pl Dat],
 F: ‘... by that (way) [focus] we walk. That [focus] is what we like.’
[< lēⁿ]

(05:19) F [kú rà =] = à—, xóónó xúàⁿdá, xúàⁿdá wàà [xá [yá xàyⁿ]]
 (false start)—, [K's name] [name] (greetings)
 ĩ̃ bà = — [ɛ̃ròò lāā],
 1Sg come.Pfv— [DemDef.Foc Purp],
 F: 'That's—. Koono Kouanda, Kouanda, thank you. That (information) is what I
 came for.'
 [*< ĩ̃ bè àⁿ— (somewhat garbled, restarted below); greetings §19.5.1*]

(05:22) F ĩ̃ bà = àn tèle [[[kú-nú xàbàrì-yà-gú] ròò] gā],
 1Sg come.Pfv 2Sg ask.Pfv [[[Dem-Link information-Def] Foc] Dat],
 xá [yá xàyⁿ]
 (greeting)
 F: 'This information [focus] is what I came to ask you-Sg about. Thank you.'

(05:25) K àywà fádá sǒǒmò, xá [yá xàyⁿ]
 well [F's name], (greeting)
 K: 'Well, Fada Songomo, thank you.'

recorded in Dia, 2022

file 180103_0025

duration 05:23

transcribable portion 00:36 – 05:23

speakers and their abbreviations in order of appearance:

Koono Kouanda (K)

Fada Songomo (F)

after some initial confusion, K begins the tale at 01:01

(00:34) K sélé-gú, sélé-gú gá [bàmbàrà-xóó ród] nī
 song-Def, song-Def be.Cop [Bambara-language Foc] it.is
 F ðⁿhⁿ
 uh.huh

K: ‘The song is in Bambara language [focus]

F: ‘Uh-huh.’

[they are discussing whether and how to tell the tale]

(00:38) K [in Bambara:] kó [á dòⁿglî nî] yè [[bámánáŋ kááⁿ] yî]
 said [3Sg song Def] be [[Bambara language] in]
 F [á dòⁿglî nî] yè [[bámánáŋ kááⁿ] yî]
 [3Sg song Def] be [[Bambara language] in]

K: ‘She (=F) said that its song is in Bambara language.’

F: ‘Its song is in Bambara language.’

[they speak in Bambara to Minkailou who is holding the microphone]

(00:40) K ā wā= [áⁿ ná á sè],
 3Sg said [2Sg Sbjn 3Sg say.Pfv],
 ā wā= [áⁿ ná á sè]
 3Sg said [2Sg Sbjn 3Sg say.Pfv]

K: ‘He said for you to say (=tell) it. [pause] He said for you to say it.’

(00:42) F àywà [dòⁿglî nî] yè [[bámánáŋ kááⁿ] yî]
 well [song Def] be [[Bambara language] in]

K ā wā= [áⁿ ná á sè]
 3Sg said [2Sg Sbjn 3Sg say.Pfv]

F: ‘Well, the song is in Bambara language.’

K: ‘He said for you to say (=sing) it.’

(01:03) K ò ná à ságà [à mā],
 1Sg Sbj/Obj 3Sg put.Pfv [3Sg against],
 né bìnà [à dá] mìnè
 1Sg Fut [3Sg begin] catch

K: I have put it (=tale) on her. [to Minkailou, in Bambara:] I am starting it (=tale).'
 [ná à ságà [X mā] 'I have put (?) it on X' is another story-telling formula that specified
 the main character; other sense of ságà is 'chop' but here it may be an obsolete variant
 of sá 'put'; 'catch X's mouth' is widespread regionally in the sense 'begin X']

(01:04) K *ní jìnè-ná [[à tá] kò],*
 Dem forget-Pfv [[3Sg possession] Dat],
 máánā
 meaning

K: '[to Minkailou, in Bambara:] 'She has forgotten hers. Here's a tale!'
 [K repeats the formula for beginning a tale]

(01:06) F *nààm*
 uh.huh
 K *ná = à ságà,* [[xáíú-ńúóŋ kòòⁿ] mā],
 1Sg.Pfv 3Sg hang.Pfv, [[man-Dimin one] against],
 F: 'Uh-huh.'

K: 'I have hung it (=tale) on a young man.'

(01:10) K [ā rōò] *tágà-máyⁿ* [[nóòŋ xàlù-giè jìèn] tē]
 [3Sg Foc] beautiful [[village man-Pl all] Dat]
 àywà, [xóò ráà = =á [làá-tèé]-nà [á lāā],
 well, [house Foc] be.Loc [shut]-Ppl [3Sg Purp],

K: 'He [focus] was the most elegant of all the men in the village. Well, a house was
 shut for (=enclosing) him.'

[he was kept locked up in a house; láá-téé, §9.5.1]

(01:15) K *mú-jíí dà = à tóò,* à =á gō,
 person-any IpfvNeg 3Sg know.Ipfv, 3Sg be.Loc there.Def,
 ìkàà àlì yá = àⁿ nà xéèn làà-jéⁿ,
 but even if 2Sg if.Pfv door open.Pfv,

K: 'Nobody knew that he was there. But even if you-Sg opened the door, ...'

[láá-jéⁿ, §9.5.1]

(01:19) K [ā yèrèⁿ nódò] gà múd-giè xè-néè,
 [3Sg light(n) Foc] Ipfv person-Pl fall-Caus.Ipfv,
 [xéèŋ jíèni ráà=] =á [làá-tèé]-nà [á lāā],
 [door seven Foc] be.Loc [shut]-Ppl [3Sg Purp],
 K: ‘His (blinding) light would knock people down. Seven doors [focus] shut him in.’

[xé-né ‘knock down’, irregular causative of xéⁿ ‘fall’, §9.1.2]

(01:25) K [ŋūðn sáàⁿ] yà= á sè
 [DemDef time] 3Pl 3Sg say.Pfv
 [[nódòⁿ yààlù-ŋúóⁿ mìyòðŋ ʃièn] tē],
 [village woman-Dimin small all] Dat],
 K: ‘So then they said to each (unmarried) young girl of the village, ...’

(01:28) K yē wō [ʃièⁿ ná bè], à ná bè,
 3Pl said [all Sbjn come.Pfv], 3Sg if.Pfv come.Pfv
 yè [máàŋ ʃièⁿ] nà [á tòò] tóó-yà,
 if [Rel all] if.Pfv [3Sg name] know-Inch.Pfv,
 K: ‘They told everyone to come. When he came, if there was anyone (=any girl) who discovered his name, ...’

[tóó ‘name’, ā tóó ‘his/her name’; inchoative tóó-yà, §9.3.4.1]

(01:31) K à= =á bì yáà [dé [ŋūðŋ kàndù] nī],
 3Sg Ipfv Fut become.Pfv [for [DemDef husband] it.is],
 àywà, [ŋūðn sáàŋ] [xúru-túú]-ŋúòŋ gá gō,
 well, [DemDef time] [hump-owner]-Dimin be.Loc there.Def,
 K: ‘... he would become her husband. Well, at that time there was a hunchbacked child (=girl).’

[xúru ‘hump’, xúru-tùù ‘hunchback’, §5.1.6.1]

(01:36) K mó-ʃì túùn dí [ŋūðⁿ ɲá] fūō,
 person-any Past IpfvNeg [DemDef QTop] like.Ipfv,
 àywà, [ā ɲà ródò] gà [á tòò] tóò,
 well, [3Sg QTop Foc] Ipfv [3Sg name] know.Ipfv,
 K: ‘Nobody liked her. Well, it was she [focus] who knew his name.’

[QTop ɲá combined with focus particle]

(01:41) K [ŋũðŋ sáàⁿ] yē xàlè [bólò gā],
 [DemDef time] 3Pl pass.Pfv [Recip Dat],
 yē xàlè [bólò gā] [ŋõròð ÿ],
 3Pl pass.Pfv [Recip Dat] [DemDef.Foc Loc],
 K: ‘Then they went past each other. In that (situation) [focus] they went past each other.’
[xálé variant of xélé ‘pass’]

(01:45) K [nóðⁿ múð-giè ʃièŋ] gá ìŋ xééⁿyèé biè,
 [village person-Pl all] Ipfv Repl get.ready.Ipfv come.Ipfv,
 yà= =á biè, [ŋũðŋ sáàⁿ] [máàŋ ʃièⁿ] nà síŋè,
 3Pl Ipfv come.Ipfv, [DemDef time] [Rel all] if.Pfv arrive.Pfv,
 K: ‘All the villagers were getting ready (i.e. getting dressed up) to come. They were coming. Then everyone who arrived ...’

(01:50) K ŋũðŋ gà á sèè fááyélémè, ā dì jíémũ,
 DemDef Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv F (name), 3Sg IpfvNeg speak.Ipfv
 àywà [nóðⁿ múð]—, àyí [máàŋ ʃièⁿ] ná bè,
 well [village person]— no! [Rel all] if.Pfv come.Pfv,
 K: ‘That one (=a girl) would say, “(his name is) Faayeleme.” He would not speak. The villagers— No! Anyone who came, ...’
[the other girls would try various names, without success; the names are sung; K mistakenly uses the real name fááyélémè here (see @ 03:09 below), hence the ‘no!’ as she restarts this segment; Ipfv sēē]

(01:57) K ŋũðŋ gà á yà= [[á tòð róð] ʃíáxũ],
 DemDef Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv [[3Sg name Foc] S],
 yè gá bàáràá [à dí ŋũðⁿ nī],
 3Pl Ipfv happen.Ipfv [3Sg not.be.Cop DemDef it.is],
 K: ‘That (other) one said, “his name [focus] is Sékou.” They would find that it (=his name) wasn’t that.’
[Ipfv yēē variant of sēē]

(01:59) K bólò gá biè [[á tòð róð] máàmá
 other Ipfv come.Ipfv [[3Sg name Foc] M
 yà= =á bàáràá [à dí ŋũðⁿ nī],
 3Pl Ipfv happen.Ipfv [3Sg not.be.Cop DemDef it.is].
 K: ‘Another would come (and say) “his name [focus] is Mama.” They would find that it wasn’t that.’

(02:02) K bólò gá biè [[á tòò róò]— [à xáy], béérémá,
 other Ipfv come.Ipfv [[3Sg name Foc]— [3Sg Prsntv], B,
 yà= =á bàáràá [à dí ηūðⁿ nī],
 3Pl Ipfv happen.Ipfv [3Sg not.be.Cop DemDef it.is],
 K: ‘Another would come (and say) “his name [focus] is—, here it is! Ibrahime.
 They would find that it wasn’t that.’
 [K briefly had to search for the name Ibrahime]

(02:07) K [ηūðŋ fòðⁿ] [nóðⁿ [yààlù-ńúóⁿ mỳyððⁿ] húnù fìèⁿ],
 [DemDef time] [village [woman-Dimin small] Top all],
 [máàŋ fìèⁿ] ná ìŋ xééⁿyè biè,
 [Rel all] if.Pfv Refl prepare.Pfv come.Ipfv,
 K: ‘At that time, all of the (other) young girls of the village, if there was anyone
 who got ready (=got dressed up) to come, ...’

(02:11) K bólò ná bè, ηūðŋ gà á= =à [á tòò róò]
 other if.Pfv come.Pfv, DemDef Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv [3Sg name Foc]
 mòdìbó, yà= =á bàáràá [à dí ηūðⁿ nī],
 M, 3Pl Ipfv happen.Ipfv [3Sg not.be.Cop DemDef it.is],
 K: ‘... when another came, that one would say, “his name is Modibo.” They would
 find that it wasn’t that.’
 [< gà á yèè á, here reduced to gààáá]

(02:15) K àywà [kú-nú yààlù-ńúðŋ-gù] [ηūðŋ sààⁿ]
 well [Dem-Link woman-Dimin-Def] [DemDef time]
 yààlù-ńúðŋ gà fáy-nà [fìè-g= ì],
 woman-Dimin be.Loc sit-Ppl [road-Def Loc],
 K: ‘Well, that young girl— then (the) girl was sitting on the road.’

(02:18) K [máàⁿ fáá =á xàléè] [à gà= á sēē]
 [Rel as Ipfv pass.Ipfv] [3Sg Ipfv 3Sg say]
 [án dí [[ín tòmó-ð] xómò] tónòó [ín té] rà,
 [2Sg IpfvNeg [[Logo head-Def] louse] look.at.Ipfv [Logo Dat] Q,
 K: ‘As anyone was going past, she would say, “won’t you-Sg look at the lice of
 (=on) my head for me?”’
 [women often pick lice from the heads of other women; < fáà gá ; < tòmó-gù]

(02:20) K ηṽðŋ gà á =à
 DemDef Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv
 [áⁿ má xàlè [báy [nóð tīⁿ]]],
 [2Sg Proh pass.Pfv [exit(v).Ipfv [village under]]],
 K: ‘That one (=girl who was passing by) would say, “don’t-2Sg leave the vicinity of the village!” ’
[this use of the prohibitive corresponds pragmatically to the suggestion ‘why don’t you ...’ (there is a similar construction in Bambara); Ipfv báy after another verb, §15.1.1.5; tīⁿ ‘under’ or ‘near’, §8.2.7.5.1]

(02:22) K [[múð rá=] =à jóò kàndùⁿ-mènè]
 [[1PIEx Foc] Ipfv go.Ipfv husband-look.for.VblN]
 [[áⁿ nóð] fðⁿ nùxáá-nà] =à fáy-nà bō],
 [[2Sg Foc] thing be.dirty-Ppl] be.Loc sit-Ppl here],
 K: ‘We (exclusive) are going to seek a husband, (whereas) you [focus] dirty thing are (just) sitting here.’
[‘go’ plus perfective VP, §15.1.2.1; the focalized ‘you-Sg’ appears to be appositional to ‘dirty thing’]

(02:25) K àywà, [ā tèmà=] =á ηṽðⁿ-yè tóy, jáà
 well, [3Sg too] Ipfv DemDef-Pl leave.Ipfv, lo!
 ā gà á fùð [bà= [á tóó ród] sè [yè tē]],
 3Sg Ipfv 3Sg like.Ipfv [Seq [3Sg name Foc] say.Pfv [3Pl Dat]],
 K: ‘Well, she (=hunchback) for her part let those ones (alone). Lo, she wanted to tell them his name.’
[fūð, §15.2.7.1]

(02:29) K àywà [ηṽnðð níŋī], [kádáá ká] [ηṽnðð y],
 well [DemDef.Foc inside], [day a.certain] [DemDef.Foc Loc],
 [yáálú sèré kà] wá= [à tē],
 [woman old a.certain] said [3Sg Dat],
 K: ‘Well, in that situation, one day in that situation a certain old woman said to her, ...’
[kádáá ‘day’ attested only in the phrase kádáá ká ‘one day’, §6.3.2.1]

(02:33) K ā wā= [áj gá á sēē]
 3Sg said [2Sg Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv]
 áŋ gá bì [xàlù-gù tód] sè [yè tē],
 2Sg Ipfv Fut [man-Def name] say.Pfv [3Pl Dat],
 K: ‘She (=old woman) said, “you-Sg say that you-Sg will tell them the man’s name.” ’
[direct quotation (without pronominal adjustment)]

(02:35) K [án táamá] gá [yáálù ród] nī,
 [2Sg also] be.Cop [woman Foc] it.is,
 ā wō e→ [yè xáy] máàn séè gù,
 3Sg said oh [3Pl Prsntv] Rel say.Ipfv Def,
 K: '(Old woman:) "You too are a woman." She (=girl) said, "Well, the one whom
 here they are saying (=talking about), ..." '
 [*< yē xāy, presentative subject (§4.4.3.1) in object relative*]

(02:38) K [ṅūðⁿ múròò] ò dì bì yáà [[ṅ húnù] má] dè,
 [DemDef need(n)] IpfvNeg Fut be.put.Pfv [[1Sg Top] against] Emph,
 ā wō àyí [án gá [yáálù ród] nī gòy],
 3Sg said no! [2Sg be.Cop [woman Foc] it.is Emph],
 K: '(Girl:) "... that one surely won't be interested in me." She (=old woman) said,
 "no! You-Sg are a woman." '
 [*mūrōò, §11.2.5.6; clause-final emphatics dé (admonitive) and góy, §19.4.1.1 and §19.4.1.3*]

(02:41) K ā wō [yé àṅ gá [à tód] tód],
 3Sg said [if 2Sg Ipfv [3Sg name] know.Ipfv,
 ā wō [áⁿ má á sè [mó-ḿì tē]]
 3Sg said [2Sg Proh 3Sg say.Pfv [person-any Dat]]
 K: 'She (=old woman) said, "if you-Sg know his name," she said, "don't tell it to
 anyone!" '

(02:44) K [bé [ṅ gá bì [àn tómó-gù] xàrì]],
 [come.Pfv [1Sg Ipfv Fut [2Sg head-Def] tie.Pfv]],
 [áⁿ ná sò],
 [2Sg Sbjn go.Pfv],
 K: '(old woman:) "Come! I will braid your head (=your hair) and you will go.'
 [*subjunctive clause added to future clause that functions pragmatically as a suggestion
 or command*]

(02:46) K ā sò [[yáálù sèré-gù] fāⁿ]
 3Sg go.Pfv [[woman old-Def] chez],
 [[yáálù sèré-gù] gáànà [á tòmò] xàrì, àlá= à méè,
 [[woman old-Def] Pfv [3Sg head] tie.Pfv, until 3Sg be.well.done,
 K: 'She (=girl) went to the old woman's place. The old woman braided her hair
 nicely.'

(02:50) K [ɲūðn sáàⁿ] á ìŋ xééⁿyè, ā bè,
 [DemDef time] 3Sg Refl prepare.Pfv, 3Sg come.Pfv,
 ā bè [ŋɔ̀rò̀̀ níŋíí →],
 3Sg come.Pfv [DemDef.Foc inside],
 K: ‘Then she got ready (=dressed up). She came. (As) she came in that (situation), ...’

(02:53) K [[ká máàŋ ʃìèŋ] gà á sèè] yē wō
 [[a.certain Rel all] Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv] 3Pl said
 [mú̀̀ ò̀̀ ɲà̀̀nà̀̀mà̀̀ⁿ-yè tèmè] dá= à kírè
 [person respectable-Pl too] PfvNeg 3Sg get.Pfv
 K: ‘... various (people) were all saying, “(even) our respectable ones for their part have not gotten (=succeeded), ...”’
 [ɲánámáⁿ ‘serious, genuine, respectable’ (< Bambara)]

(02:56) K wō→ [jòŋ́-ɔ̀-ààdá [áⁿ nó̀] xúru-tù̀]
 (said) [a.fortiori [2Sg Foc] hump-owner]
 ʃíéŋ gá á tàbî [báy gɔ̀],
 all Ipfv 3Sg push.Ipfv [exit.Ipfv there.Def],
 K: ‘(They) said: “... never mind you-Sg (the) hunchback!” Everyone pushed her away there.’
 [wō→ seems to extend a quotation; jòŋ́-ɔ̀-ààdá, §7.3; tábî ‘push’]

(03:00) K ʃíéŋ gá á tàbî [báy gɔ̀],
 all Ipfv 3Sg push.Ipfv [exit.Ipfv there.Def],
 álá =á fù̀̀ [ŋɔ̀rò̀̀ níŋíí],
 God 3Sg like.Pfv [DemDef.Foc inside],
 K: ‘Everyone pushed her away there. God willed it at that time, ...’
 [K repeats a sentence since interlocutor F was distracted by a passerby’s greeting]

(03:03) K yē wō [sā̀w húnù] [ká-réé ìn t̀y]
 3Pl said [now Top] [a.certain-Pl Refl leave.Pfv]
 [kí ʃíéŋ] gá á tàbî, [mó-ʃí dì xà̀lù-gù kírè]
 [1PlIn all] Ipfv 3Sg push.Ipfv, [person-any PfvNeg man-Def get.Pfv],
 K: ‘They said now, some (of them) spoke up, “we all are pushing her, (but) nobody has gotten the man.”’

(03:06) K [xá dá= á t̀y] [á tèmè] ná l̀ r̀à,
 [2Pl IpfvNeg 3Sg leave.Ipfv] [3Sg also] Sbjn enter.Pfv Q,
 [ā tèmè] só [ìn táà],
 [3Sg also] go.Pfv [Refl stop.Pfv],
 K: ‘“Won’t you-Pl let her go in also?” She (=hunchback girl) went and stopped.’

(03:09) K [xéèŋ jíèni ñá ród] gà [á lāā], à só [in táà]
 [door seven QTop Foc] be.Loc [3Sg Purp], 3Sg go.Pfv [Refl stop.Pfv],
 [kó fááyélémè], [xálu-gú à jáwààwì [núùⁿ fáà]],
 [said F], [man-Def 3Sg reply.Pfv [interior by]],
 K: ‘Seven doors [focus] were (shutting) him in. She went and stopped (at the
 outermost door). She said (singing), “Faayeleme!” The man answered her from
 the interior.’
 [kó ‘said’ (Bambara); jáwààwí]

(03:16) K *cièn dō maama, í sīgì-lén dō [dúmaⁿ-wòlò mááⁿ] dè káⁿ,*
 truth it.is M, 2Sg sit-Ppl be [sweetness-skin Rel] be on,
cièn dō maama, foro-foro dāmá dèbì [é bòlò],
 truth it.is M, ?? only be [2Sg having],
 K: ‘(the man sings in Bambara:) “It’s true (=correct), Mama!” (Girl:) “The skin of
 sweetness that you are sitting on.” (Man:) “It’s true, Mama!” (Girl:) “You have
 foroforo.”’

(03:24) K *cièn dō maama, sáñá-ñóñóⁿ té,*
 truth it.is Mama, peer not.be,
 [xééŋ kódⁿ] ñŋ xòyè,
 [door one] Refl break,
 K: ‘(Man:) “It’s true, Mama.” (Girl:) “There is no equal!” One door broke.’

(03:27) K *ā xwāà ìn túláá-nì [jóò [bólò mā]],*
 3Sg again Refl become.short-Caus.Pfv [go.Ipfv [other against]],
 K: ‘Again she went and approached another (door).’

(03:29) [*kó fááyélémè*] *kó cièⁿ dō maama,*
í sīgì-léⁿ dō [[dúmaⁿ-wòlò mááⁿ] dè káⁿ] *cièⁿ dō maama,*
foro-foro dāmá dèbì [é bòlò] *cièⁿ dō maama,*
sáñá-ñóñóⁿ té

(03:42) K [xééŋ kóm bólò] ñŋ xòyè, ā xwāà
 [door one other] Refl break.Pfv, 3Sg again
 ìn túláá-nì [jóò [[bólò-gù tèmè] mā],
 Refl become.short-Caus.Pfv [go.Ipfv [[other-Def also] against],
 K: ‘One other door broke. Again she went and approached yet another (door).’
 [‘other’ follows numeral, §6.1.1]

(03:45) K [[ā yèrèŋ] gá múù-giè kòrì]
 [[3Sg light(n)] Ipfv person-Pl hit.Pfv]
 [[ká máàŋ ʃìèŋ] gá= á sēē èé→],
 [[a.certain Rel all] Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv huh?],
 K: ‘His light struck (=illuminated) the people. Several of them were saying,
 “huh?”’

(03:47) K [kú rɔ̀̀] gá bì xàlù-gù kírè ↑,
 [Dem Foc] Ipfv Fut man-Def get.Pfv,
 [ā xwā̀ à ìn túláá-ni [ʃò̀̀ [bólò mā]],
 [3Sg again Refl become.short-Caus.Pfv [go.Ipfv [other against]],
 K: ‘(people:) “This one will get the man!” She went and approached another
 (door).’

(03:51) [*kó fááyélé̀̀mè̀̀*] *kó cieⁿ dò maama,*
í sìgì-léⁿ dò [[dú máⁿ-wò̀̀lò mááⁿ] dè káⁿ] *cieⁿ dò maama,*
foro-foro dàmá dè̀̀bì [é̀̀ bò̀̀lò] *cieⁿ dò maama,*
sáŋá-ŋóŋóⁿ té

(04:03) K [xéém bólò] ìŋ xòyè, ʃíyòn dí xèⁿ nà,
 [door other] Refl break.Pfv, three PfvNeg fall.Pfv Q,
 ā ìn tíni [ʃò̀̀ [náára-nàà mā]],
 3Sg Refl approach [go.Ipfv [four-Ord against]],
 K: ‘Another door broke. Have not three (doors) fallen? She went and approached a
 fourth (door).’

[*rhetorical question; tíni ~ téⁿ (reflexive) ‘approach’*]

(04:07)K ā wò̀̀ [*fááyélé̀̀mè̀̀*] *kó cieⁿ dò maama,*
í sìgì-léⁿ dò [[dú máⁿ-wò̀̀lò mááⁿ] dè káⁿ] *cieⁿ dò maama,*
foro-foro dàmá dè̀̀bì [é̀̀ bò̀̀lò] *cieⁿ dò maama,*
sáŋá-ŋóŋóⁿ té

(04:19) K náára-nàà ìŋ xòyè,
 four-Ord Refl break.Pfv,
 ā ìn túláá-nì ʃò̀̀ [kóló-nàà mā],
 3Sg Refl become.short-Caus.Pfv go.Ipfv [five-Ord against],
 K: ‘The fourth (door) broke. She went and approached a fifth (door).’

(04:22)K [*kó fááyélé̀̀mè̀̀*] *kó cieⁿ dò maama,*
í sìgì-léⁿ dò [[dú máⁿ-wò̀̀lò mááⁿ] dè káⁿ] *cieⁿ dò maama,*
foro-foro dàmá dè̀̀bì [é̀̀ bò̀̀lò] *cieⁿ dò maama,*
sáŋá-ŋóŋóⁿ té

(04:34) K ā ìn túláá-nì jòò [túúmí-nàà mā],
 3Sg Refl become.short-Caus.Pfv go.Ipfv [six-Ord against],
 yéréŋ gá múò-giè kòrî,
 light Ipfv person-Pl hit.Ipfv,

K: 'She went and approached a sixth (door). The light struck the people.'

(04:37)K [kó fááyéléémè] kó cieⁿ dò maama,
 í sìgì-léⁿ dò [[dúamáⁿ-wòlò mááⁿ] dè káⁿ] cieⁿ dò maama,
 foro-foro dàmá dèbì [é bòlò] cieⁿ dò maama,
 sáŋá-ŋóŋóⁿ té

(04:50) K ā ìn túláá-nì jòò [jíení-nàá-gù mā],
 3Sg Refl become.short-Caus.Pfv go.Ipfv [seven-Ord-Def against],
 [ŋūòñ tèmè]
 [DemDef also]

K: 'She went and approached the seventh (door), that one too.'

[here the speaker uses the definite form of the ordinal]

(04:52) K ā ìn túláá-nì jòò [[ŋūòñ tèmè] mā],
 3Sg Refl become.short-Caus.Pfv go.Ipfv [[DemDef also] against]

K: 'She went and approached that one too.'

(04:54)K ā wò [fááyéléémè] cieⁿ dò maama,
 í sìgì-léⁿ dò [[dúamáⁿ-wòlò mááⁿ] dè káⁿ] cieⁿ dò maama,
 foro-foro dàmá dèbì [é bòlò] cieⁿ dò maama,
 sáŋá-ŋóŋóⁿ té

(05:06) K jíení-nàá-gù ìŋ xòyè,
 seven-Ord-Def Refl break.Pfv,
 [[ā yèrèŋ-gú ròò] yáálú-ŋúòñ tìŋè]
 [[3Sg light-Def Foc] woman-Dimin carry.on.head.Pfv]

K: 'The seventh (door) broke. His light [focus] lifted the girl up'

(05:09) K [bá= á xè-nè], [ā xūrù-gù ìŋ kàlà],
 [Seq 3Sg fall-Caus.Pfv], [3Sg hump-Def Refl shatter.Pfv],
 [yáálú-ŋúòñ-gù húnù] yáà [dè [múò tàgà-màýⁿ] nī],
 [woman-Dimin-Def Top] become.Pfv [for [person beautiful] it.is],
 K: '... and dropped her down. Her hump was shattered. The girl became a beautiful person.'

(05:13) K yà= [á fòròŋ] xàrà= [à tē],
 3Pl [3Sg bag] tie.Pfv [3Sg Dat],

K: 'They confirmed her marriage to him.'

[xàri 'tie'; 'tie her bag to him' = 'confirm her marriage to him' (ordinarily by completing bridewealth payments)]

(05:15) K [máàŋ-giè wà= [á dì lóò] gù]
 [Rel-Pl said [3Sg IpfvNeg enter.Ipfv] Def]
 ŋũðⁿ-yè yáà [dà= [á bàràŋ-júðⁿ-yè] nī],
 DemDef-Pl become.Pfv [for [3Sg work-child-Pl] it.is],

K: 'Those who had said that she would not go in, those ones became her servants.'

(05:17) K [ñ náŋ kàmáán lèè [gèrè máàⁿ]]
 [1Sg Sbj/Obj tale pick.up.Pfv [place Rel]]
 [ñ ná à yáà gō]
 [1Sg Sbj/Obj 3Sg put.down.Pfv there.Def]

K: 'The place where I picked up a tale, I have put it (back) down there.'

[standard tale ending; kámáāⁿ 'tale']

recorded in Dia, 2022

file 180103_0030

duration 02:12

transcribable portion 00:05 - 02:12, tale begins at 00:12

speakers and their abbreviations in order of appearance:

Fada Songomo (F), female, narrator

Koono Kouanda (K), female

note: includes song segments in Bambara language (italicized)

(00:08) F (in Bambara:) *súrgú* *nì—*
hyena and
[à xáy] *gónóy-jùsⁿ*, yé *tòlòⁿ*
[3Sg Prsntv] hare.&, and hyena

F: ‘Hyena and—. Here they are, hare and hyena.’

[speaker started to speak Bambara (“hyena and—“), then corrected herself; gónóy-jùsⁿ is a diminutive compound in form but it can denote an adult hare]

(00:12) K *mààná-mààná*
(tale opening)
F *mààná-mààná*, [n táⁿ] *mààná*,
(tale opening), [1Sg elder.sib] meaning,
K: ‘Once upon.’

F: ‘Once upon a time. My elder sibling the tale.’

[K prompts the narrator F to say mààná-mààná (cf. máánā ‘meaning, explanation’), the formula to begin a tale; the full form of the formula is given by F, with a variant of ñ tōⁿ ‘my elder sibling’, since the tale is older than the narrator]

(00:16) F *gónóy-jùsⁿ* [yé *tòlòⁿ*]
hare.& [and hyena]

K *náám*

yes

F: ‘Hare and hyena.’

K: ‘Yes!’

[-jùsⁿ becomes LH-toned before conjunction ‘and’, §7.1.2; náám is the standard backchannel response by the listener, as also in a mosque; from here on, routine backchannel náám is omitted from transcriptions]

(00:17) F góḡóy-jùḡⁿ, ḡḡḡḡ ḡá, ē→, kū-ḡḡḡm bāā,
 hare, DemDef Ipfv, uh, whatchamacallit remove.Ipfv,
 kámáāⁿ, ḡḡā = á [ḡḡḡḡ kámáám] bāā,
 peanut, DemDef Ipfv [alien peanut] remove.Ipfv,
 F: ‘Hare, that one was taking away whatchamacallit, peanuts. That one was taking
 away someone else’s peanuts.’
 [kū-ḡḡḡⁿ ‘whatchamacallit’, §4.4.4; ḡḡḡḡ⁽ⁿ⁾ ‘someone else’ (French *autrui*)]

(00:23) F tólóⁿ, ḡḡā = á xèléè,
 hyena, DemDef Ipfv pass.Ipfv
 ā bāārà [góḡóy-jùḡḡ ḡá kámáám bāā],
 3Sg happen.Pfv [hare Ipfv peanut remove.Ipfv],
 F: ‘Hyena, that one was passing by. It happened that hare was taking peanuts away.’

(00:26) F ā ìḡ tḡy [ḡḡḡḡḡḡ níḡḡ], ā wḡ hḡḡⁿ,
 3Sg Refl let.Pfv [DemDef.Foc inside], 3Sg said oh!,
 góḡóy-jùḡḡ, ìḡ—
 hare, (false start)
 F: ‘He (=hyena) intervened (=spoke up) then. He said, “oh my! Hare, ...”’
 [reflexive of tḡy ‘let.Pfv’ means ‘intervene; speak up’]

(00:31) F [áⁿ húnù] ðì fḡy míé-nīi
 [2Sg Top] IpfvNeg anything be.good-Caus.Ipfv]
 [yá = à dí [[ḡḡḡḡ-kámáám]-bèè],
 [if 3Sg not.be.Cop [[alien-peanut]-remove.Antip.VblN],
 F: ‘“...you-Sg do nothing but take someone else’s peanuts away.”’
 [fḡy ‘nothing’, §6.3.2.4; ‘not X except Y’ meaning ‘only Y’, §19.3.2.7; verbal noun with
 incorporated object, §5.1.5.1]

(00:33) F ā wḡ [[án témé] ðì fḡy míé-nīi
 3Sg said [[2Sg too] IpfvNeg anything be.good-Caus.Ipfv]
 [yá = à dí [[ḡḡḡḡ-nàà]-[xààḡ-xḡyè]],
 [if 3Sg not.be.Cop [[alien-cow]-[throat-break.Antip.VblN]],
 F: ‘He (=hare) in turn said, “you-Sg for your part do nothing but slaughter someone
 else’s cows.”’

(00:35) F ā wā = [á = =á ḡḡḡḡ sèé [nḡḡ ḡá] rà],
 3Sg said [2Sg Ipfv DemDef say.Ipfv [1Sg.Foc Dat] Q],
 [àlá = àⁿ nà kálè] [án dá = [á ḡḡḡⁿ] wàléè].
 [even 2Sg if.Pfv die.Pfv] [2Sg IpfvNeg [3Sg all] do.Ipfv],
 F: ‘He (=hyena) said, “are you-Sg saying that to me? Even if you-Sg die, you won’t
 do all that again!”’
 [standard scolding formula, usually addressed to children]

(00:38) F [ā wāy sàà [[à xóórò] xúmà]]
 [3Sg as.soon.as follow.Pfv [[3Sg back] on]]
 [[kú témé] tórí], à só tàⁿ, [jìrì xúmà],
 [[Dem too] jump.Pfv], 3Sg go.Pfv ascend.Pfv, [tree on],
 F: ‘As soon as he (=hyena) pursued him (=hare), that one (=hare) for his part jumped. He went up into a tree.’
 [wāy ‘as soon as’, §17.2.3]

(00:43) F [ŋūðn sáàⁿ nòð]
 [DemDef time Foc]
 (sings in Bambara:) à nà-nà = áⁿw sòró→
 3Sg come-Pfv 1Pl find.Pfv
 F: ‘At that time [focus]: (sings:) “He came and found us.” ’
 [the first of several other animals passes by and sees hare and hyena; all Bambara transcriptions and glosses are approximate]

(00:46) F [òⁿ, gónóy-jùðŋ, [xá [yé tòlòⁿ]] máà— tòlòⁿ [máà ród],
 [ah, hare, [2Pl.& [and hyena]] what?— hyena [what? Foc],
 [áⁿ [máà ród] yáà [tòlòⁿ mā],
 [2Sg [what? Foc] put.Pfv [hyena against],
 F: ‘(passerby:) “Hey hare, you-Pl and hyena, what— What did you-Sg do to hyena?’
 [it turns out that there are multiple hares up in the tree]

(00:50) F ā wò (sings:) à nà-nà = áⁿw sòró→
 3Sg said 3Sg come-Pfv 1Pl find.Pfv
 ká= ám bí [nògón kùùⁿ] filè là,
 Seq 1Pl Ipfv [Recip head] look.at.Ipfv (?),
 F: ‘He (=hare) sang (in Bambara), “He came and found us, we were looking at each other.” ’

(00:54) F à kò [ʔáw ní cé→]
 3Sg said [2Pl and work(n)]
 [màà-ní tìgè bá] wárábá-w,
 [person-small peanut remove] lion-Pl,
 F (Hare sings in Bambara:) ‘He said, “greetings to you-Pl! The little one takes out (=digs up) peanuts, (like) lions.” ’

(00:57) F [áwⁿ yèré] kò [á ní cé]
 [1Pl too] said [2Sg and work(n)]
 [[fíláw ká mǐfì kááj] káírí-báà,
 [[Fulbe of cow] neck] snap-Agent,
 F (Hare sings in Bambara:) “We too said, “greetings to you-Sg! The breaker of the neck(s) of the cows of the Fulbe.” ’
 [Fulbe is the ethnicity of cattle herders]

(01:00) F à wílílá páw! [ká= á bí nà [áwⁿ mà] sègèrè],
 3Sg get.up.Pfv [Infin 3Sg Seq come.Pfv [1Pl against] rejoin.Pfv],
 [áwⁿ yèré] wílílá páw! [ká [[yírí-bá nì] mà] sègèrè],
 [1Pl too] get.up.Pfv [Infin [[tree-big Dem] against] rejoin.Pfv],
 F (Hare sings in Bambara:) “He got up to come and join up with us. We too got up to join up with that big tree.” ’
 [páw! is an interjection-like expressive adverbial]

(01:06) F óðⁿ, [ŋ húnù] gú xà kòrì [ǎl xà kálè],
 hey, [1Sg Top] Fut 2Pl hit.Pfv [until 2Pl die.Pfv],
 [ŋ húnù] gú [xà xààŋ] xòyè,
 [1Sg Top] Fut [2Pl neck] snap.Pfv,
 F: ‘(Hyena:) “Hey, I will hit you-Pl, until you-Pl have died. I will break your-Pl neck(s).” ’
 [< àlì ‘until’]

(01:10) F óðⁿ, áà tólóⁿ, áŋ gáána= à tóⁿyààⁿ,
 hey, ah! hyena, 2Sg Pfv 3Sg assault.Pfv,
 tólá= áŋ gáána yè tóⁿyààⁿ,
 hyena 2Sg Pfv 3Pl assault.Pfv,
 F: ‘(Passer-by:) “Hey hyena! You-Sg assaulted him (=hare). Hyena, you-Sg assaulted them (=hares).” ’
 [gáána, marked perfective particle, §10.2.1.1.2]

(01:14) F tólá= áŋ gáána yè tóⁿyààŋ gòy,
 hyena 2Sg Pfv 3Pl assault.Pfv Emph,
 bólbó gá xèlèè,
 mate Ipfv pass.Ipfv,
 F: ‘(Passer-by:) “Hyena, you-Sg sure assaulted them!” The other one was passing by.
 [góy, §19.4.1.1]

(01:17) F [[bólò tèmà =] = á xèléè]
 [[mate too] Ipfv pass.Ipfv]
 yē bàárà [kwá = = á [jìrì xúmà]]
 3Pl happen.Pfv [Dem be.Loc [tree on]]
 F: ‘Another one (=animal) was passing by. They (=passers-by) noticed that this one (=hare) was (up) in a tree ...’
 [bàárà ‘happen to find; notice’]

(01:19) F [kú =à táá-nà [jírì-bùú tīⁿ], yē wō hóòⁿ, tólóⁿ,
 [Dem be.Loc stand-Ppl [tree-base under], 3Pl said oh!, hyena,
 [máà ródò] gáánà lè [[xá [yè góṅóy-jùòⁿ-yé]] nāāⁿ,
 [what? Foc] Pfv enter.Pfv [[2Pl.& [and hare-Pl]] between],
 F: ‘... (and) that one (=hyena) was standing at the base of the tree. They (=passers-by) said, “hey, hyena! What has entered (=happened) between you-Pl and the hares?”’
 [deictic demonstrative kú occurs twice to distinguish hare from hyena]

(01:24) F ðⁿhóⁿ yē tèle sínè wā,
 hey 3Pl ask.Pfv first(adv) Emph,
 [yē [fðⁿ máàⁿ] wàlè] [=è gá à tódò],
 [3Pl [thing Rel] do.Pfv] [3Pl Ipfv 3Sg know.Ipfv],
 F: ‘(Hyena:) “Hey, ask them first! What they have done, they know it!”’
 [wā emphatic with imperatives, §19.4.1.9; functionally stative tódò, §11.2.5.1]

(01:28) F yē tèle sínè, [yē [fðⁿ máàⁿ] wàlè]
 3Pl ask.Pfv first(adv), [3Pl [thing Rel] do.Pfv]
 [=è gá à tódò], óòṅ góṅóy-jùòⁿ,
 [3Pl Ipfv 3Sg know.Ipfv], hey hare,
 [máà ródò] gáánà lè [[xá [yé tólóⁿ]] nāāⁿ,
 [what? Foc] Pfv enter.Pfv [[2Pl.& [and hyena]] between],
 F: ‘(Hyena:) “Ask them (=hares) first! What they have done, they know it!” (Passer-by:) “Hey hare! What has entered (=happened) between you-Pl and hyena?”’

(01:33) F (sings in Bambara) à nà náán sòró→
 3Sg come-Pfv 1Pl find.Pfv
 ká= ám bí [ndgón kùùⁿ] filè là,
 Seq 1Pl Ipfv [Recip headamong] look.at.Ipfv (?),
 F: ‘(Hare sings:) “He came and found us, we are looking at each other.”’

(01:36) F à kò [ʔáw ní cé→]
 3Sg said [2Pl and work(n)]
 [màà-ní tìgè bá] wárábá-w,
 [person-small peanut remove] lion-Pl,
 F (Hare sings in Bambara:) ‘He said, “greetings to you-Pl! The little one takes out (=digs up) peanuts, (like) lions.” ’

(01:39) F [áwⁿ yèré] kò [á ní cé]
 [1Pl too] said [2Sg and work(n)]
 [[fíláw ká mifî kááj] ká-rí-báà,
 [[Fulbe of cow] neck] snap-Agent,
 F (Hare sings in Bambara:) “We too said, “greetings to you-Sg! The breaker of the neck(s) of the cows of the Fulbe.” ’

(01:42) F à wílílá páw! [ká= á bí nà [áwⁿ mà] sègèrè],
 3Sg get.up.Pfv [Infin 3Sg Seq come.Pfv [1Pl against] rejoin.Pfv],
 [áwⁿ yèré] wílílá páw! [ká [[yírí-bá nì] mà] sègèrè],
 [1Pl too] get.up.Pfv [Infin [[tree-big Dem] against] rejoin.Pfv],
 F (Hare sings in Bambara:) “He got up to come and join up with us. We too got up to join up with that big tree.” ’

(01:47) F óòn tólóⁿ, áŋ gáánà yè tóⁿyààⁿ,
 hey hyena, 2Sg Pfv 3Pl assault.Pfv,
 [ŋūðŋ gá à nī] [áŋ gá hìnî [yè té rōð],
 [DemDef be.Cop 3Sg it.is] [2Sg Ipv be.able.Ipv [3Pl Dat Foc],
 F: ‘(Passer-by:) “Hey hyena! You-Sg assaulted them! It is (like) that. You-Sg are stronger than they [focus] (are).” ’
 [hínî ‘be able (to)’ with VP, but ‘be stronger than’ with dative PP]

(01:52) F [ŋūðŋ gá ìn tòlò [[ŋ fíèⁿ fáà],
 [DemDef Ipv Refl go.away.Pfv [[Refl road] by],
 [ā gùlà=] [á gùlà=] [á gùlà] [á gùlà],
 [3Sg become.hot.Pfv] (repetitions),
 F: ‘That one (=passer-by) went on his merry way. It (=conflict) was getting more and more heated.’
 [tóló (reflexive verb) ‘go away, depart’; iteration of clause including subject, §9.6.3]

(01:55) F [góŋóy-jùðŋ ŋá] wāārāāⁿ,
 [hare QTop] be.clever.Stat,
 góŋóy-jùðŋ gáánà ìn tỳ [ŋōròò níŋī],
 hare Pfv Refl let.Pfv [DemDef.Foc inside],
 F: ‘Hare was indeed clever! Hare intervened (=spoke up) at that point.’
 [QTop, §19.1.2]

(01:58) F [ā tòrì bìè] [[tòlòn tòmò] níṅī] [yé páw],
 [3Sg jump.Pfv come.Ipfv] [[hyena head] inside] [bang!],
 [à ná ìṅ kírè] [ā kī]
 [3Sg if.Pfv Refl finish.Pfv] [3Sg get.up.Pfv]
 F: ‘He (=hare) came jumping (down) on hyena’s head with a thud. When he (=hare) had finished (jumping), he (=hare) got up.’
[yé páw onomatopoeia for the sound of hitting, slapping, etc., §11.4.3]

(02:01) F [ā xēèlè bírí-bírí-bírí-bírí],
 [3Sg run.Pfv (running swiftly)],
 [[tólóⁿ húnù] sàà [[à xóórò] xúmà =]
 [[hyena Top] follow.Pfv [[3Sg back] on]
 F: ‘He (=hare) ran swiftly. As for hyena, he (=hyena) pursued after him.’
[expressive adverbial bírí-bírí ‘running swiftly’, §11.4.3]

(02:03) F [ā sàà [[à xóórò] xúmà] [ā sà = [[à xóórò] xúmà]],
 [3Sg follow.Pfv [[3Sg back] on] (repetition)
 àlá = [à tóò] só [ìṅ xòyè [gèrè máàⁿ]],
 until [3Sg foot] go.Pfv [Refl break.Pfv [place Rel]],
 F: ‘... and he (=hyena) pursued him and he pursued him, until the point where his (=hyena’s) foot went and got broken.’
[pejorative ‘go and VP’, §15.1.2.1]

(02:06) F ā kōnò [bì [góṅóy-jùòⁿ húnù] xáy],
 3Sg fail.Pfv [Seq [hare Top] see.Pfv],
 F: ‘He (=hyena) was unable to see hare.’
[kónò variant of kóndò ‘fail (to VP)’]

(02:08) F [ṅ ná [ṅ kámáán] lèè [gèrè máàⁿ]]
 [1Sg Sbj/Obj [1Sg tale] pick.up.Pfv [place Rel]]
 [ṅ ná à yáà gō]
 [1Sg Sbj/Obj 3Sg put.Pfv there.Def]
 F: ‘Where I picked my tale up, I put it (back) down there.’
[standard tale-closing formula; kámáánⁿ]

recorded in Dia, 2022

file 180103_0034

duration 13:04

transcribable portion 00:08 - 13:04

transcribable portion begins a few seconds into a greeting sequence

topics: greetings; early history of Dia village (00:22); old-time marriage (11:00)

speakers and their abbreviations in order of appearance:

Seni Yalouta (S), male

Alfa Boubacar Karabenta (A), male, main narrator

(00:08) S àlhámdù-llàày
praise.God (< Arabic)

A (unintelligible)

S: ‘God be praised!’

A: (unintelligible)

(00:10) S [báásì húnù ʃí] dī gō
[trouble Top any] not.be.Loc there.Def

A báásì húnù ʃī
trouble Top any

S: ‘There is no trouble there?’

A: ‘(Not) any trouble.’

[báási ‘trouble’]

(00:11) S àlhámdù llàày
praise to God

A (unintelligible)

S: ‘God be praised!’

(00:12) S tāwāā [xá [yè bārāy]]
hello [2Pl.& [and reward]]
A xāwāā [xá [yè bándààⁿ]]
hello [2Pl.& [and fatigue]]

S: ‘Hello, you-Pl and (divine) reward?’

A: ‘Hello, you-Pl and fatigue?’

[tāwāā *idiosyncratic variant of xāwāā (greeting); noun bārāy ‘divine reward’; ‘you and X’ is common greeting formula, cf. ‘how’s the fatigue?’*, §19.5.2; 2Pl for singular addressee in polite greetings]

(00:14) S màràhàbá
welcome
A màràhàbá
welcome
S: ‘Welcome!’
A: ‘Welcome!’
[< Arabic ‘welcome’, but used in Tigemaxo to bring a long greeting sequence to a close]

(00:15) S xāwāā [xá [yè bārāy]]
hello [2Pl.& [and reward]]
A yáálú [yé xàlambèèⁿ-yè]
woman.& [and child-Pl]
S: ‘You-Pl and reward?’
A: ‘(Your) wife and children?’
[NP conjunction, §7.1.1; yáálù, xálámbééŋ-gíé]

(00:16) S [báásí húnù] dī [m̄ má] yà
[trouble Top] not.be.Loc [1Sg against] Emph
A (unintelligible)
S: ‘There’s no trouble against me.’
[< m̄ mā ; mild emphatic yá, §19.4.1.8]

(00:17) S k̀r̀í [bààsì húnù], xónóm̀ǹǹ-̀g̀ìè ̀ǹà
Q [trouble Top], old.person-Pl QTop
A [bààsì húnù] dī [yè mā]
[trouble Top] not.be.Loc [3Pl against]
S: ‘Is there (any) trouble? What about the old people?’
A: ‘There is no trouble against (=afflicting) them.’
[k̀r̀í clause-initial interrogative in greetings, §13.2.1.2; ̀ǹà interrogative topic, §19.1.2]

(00:19) S k̀r̀í báásí dī [yè mā], àl̀hám̀d̀ù-̀l̀l̀à̀y
Q trouble not.be.Loc [3Pl against], praise.God
A àmbàà
(greeting reply)
S: ‘There’s no trouble against them? God be praised!’
A: (greeting reply)

(00:22) S xāwāā [xá [yè bārāy]]
hello [2Pl.& [and reward]]

A yāàltá

Yaloutan

S: ‘You-Pl and reward?’

A: ‘Yaloutan’

[A pronounces S’s family name, this is normal at the end of a greeting cycle]

(00:24) S bon àlfáà [ṅ gá fùò [bá= àn tètè]],
okay Alfa [1Sg Ipfv want.Ipfv [Seq 2Sg ask.Pfv]],
kúmì, [xá témé] gá nóyààⁿ-yè nī,
like, [2Pl too] be.Cop native-Pl it.is,

S: ‘Okay, Alfa, I would like to ask you-Sg, as you-Pl (too) are old-time natives (here),’

[< French comme; nóyààⁿ ‘native, old-timer’, one who is deeply familiar with the local history]

(00:28) S xá [nóyààn tímíyòⁿ-yè] nī,
2Pl [native grandchild-Pl] it.is,

bon est-ce que á= =á màà→ wáxádí sèè [ń tē],
okay Q 2Sg Ipfv be.able.Ipfv time say.Ipfv [1Sg Dat],

S: ‘(And) you-Pl are grandchildren of a native. Okay, can you-Sg tell me (about) the time (period), ...’

[á=á contracted < áⁿ gá ; máá ‘be able’, §15.1.1.2; wáxádí]

(00:34) S [báy→ [jáà fáy] wàxàdú] [bìè [sāw má]] rà,
[exit.Ipfv [Dia sit.VblN] time] [come.Ipfv [now against]] Q,
yáàmbáárà [múò máàⁿ-yè] gáánà xèlè
whether [person Rel-Pl] Pfv pass.Pfv

S: ‘... from the time of the settling (=founding) of Dia down to the present? (I wonder) whether the people (=ancestors) who have passed ...’

[< jáà, fáy, wáxádū ; báy ... bíé ..., §8.2.8; yáàmbáárà, §17.1.5]

(00:39) S [jáà, fáy níṅī] [bíé kóri]
[Dia sit.VblN inside] [come.Ipfv hit.Pfv]
[[kí xáy] [gèrè máà] níṅí gù],
[[1PlIn Prsntv] [place Rel] inside Def],

S: ‘... (from) the settling of Dia all the way to the place (=situation) that we here (inclusive) are in (now).’

[kóri ‘hit.Pfv’ reinforcing bíé ‘come.Ipfv’ in ‘from X to Y’ construction, §8.2.8.3; kí xáy, §4.4.3.2; relativization on complement of postposition, §14.2.4]

(00:42) S yàambáàrà àŋ gá mǎā, fòn sèé [n té] yēē *quoi*,
 whether 2Sg Ipfv be.able.Ipfv, thing say.Ipfv [1Sg Dat] therein Ø
 [n tǒ́ rǒ̀] gá→, [ʃìèni yáàldáá] nī, bá̀y já̀à,
 [1Sg name Foc] be.Cop, [S Y] it.is, from Dia,
 S: ‘(I wonder) whether you-Sg can tell me something about it. My name is Huseini
 Yalouta, native of Dia (village).’
 [yēē ‘therein, in it’ after postverbal PP, §8.2.3.3; tǒ́ ‘name’, n tǒ́ ‘my name’, focalized
 n tǒ̀ rǒ̀; ʃíéní from Arabic Husein; bá̀y ‘exit.Ipfv’ as quasi-preposition, §8.2.8.1.1]

(00:50) S nǒ́n-tù̀ *conseiller*, bá̀y já̀à,
 village-owner councilor, from Dia,
 A [n tǒ̀ rǒ̀] gá [álfáá bù̀ùbàkár kàràbééntà],
 [1Sg name Foc] be.Cop [A B K],
 S: ‘(I am) councilor of the village chief.’
 A: ‘My name is Alfa Boubacar Karabenta.’

(00:57) A [mù̀dò rǒ̀] gá [já̀à nǒ́yààⁿ-yè] nī
 [1PIEx Foc] be.Cop [Dia native-Pl] it.is
 S némēēⁿ
 greatly
 A: ‘We (exclusive) are natives of Dia.’
 S: ‘Thoroughly.’

(01:02) A ì̀ gá à kírēē—
 1Sg Ipfv 3Sg find.Ipfv—
 [n nà̀ŋ] gá [fáámàdà xú̀ndáá] nī,
 [1Sg mother] be.Cop [F K] it.is,
 A: ‘I find (=inherit)—. My mother is Fatoumata Kouanta.’
 [‘find, encounter’ here in the sense ‘learn as child from parents and elders’]

(01:05) A [[[ŋ kà] tíŋáá] nà̀ŋ-gù̀]
 [[[1Sg father] possession] mother-Def]
 ŋù̀dŋ gá [nî [mḕèⁿsà xú̀ndáá]] nī,
 DemDef be.Cop [stepmother [M K]] it.is,
 A: ‘The mother of my father, that one (=she) is Stepmother Minsa Kouanta.’
 [cf. ì̀ kǎ ‘my father’, ŋ kǎ tíŋàà ‘of my father’; ‘stepmother (of X)’ usually means
 ‘cowife of mother (of X)’ whether the mother is living or dead, nîⁿ ‘stepmother’ here
 has become part of the name of the speaker’s father’s mother]

(01:09) A ńkàà kí gá màá
 but 1PlIn Ipfv be.able.Ipfv
 kà sèè [[jáà fáy-m-béénàà] níjīī],
 a.certain say.Ipfv [[Dia sit.VblN-Link-manner] inside],
 A: ‘But we (inclusive) can say something about the settling of Dia.’
 [ká specific indefinite, §6.3.2.1]

(01:14) A *parce que* yè gá bì jáà fáy-nì,
 because 3Pl Ipfv Fut Dia sit-Caus.Pfv,
 parce que [múò fèndeèⁿ nód] jáà fáy-nì,
 because [person two Foc] Dia sit-Caus.Pfv,
 A: ‘Because (when) they were about to found Dia, because it was two people
 [focus] who founded Dia.’
 [subject focalization, §13.1.4; focus marker ród nasalized to nód, §13.1.1]

(01:21) S yē gà á yèè xúòndáā→, tómódáà,
 3Pl Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv K.&, T,
 ńkàà yè [máàŋ ʃìèⁿ] nà á sè
 but if [Rel all] if.Pfv 3Sg say.Pfv
 S: ‘They say (=call them) Kouanta (and) Tomota. But if (there is) anyone (at all)
 who says ...’
 [yē for sē ‘say.Ipfv’ with 3Pl subject, §17.1.3; conjunction by juxtaposition, §7.1.11;
 relative clause combined with conditional antecedent]

(01:26) A [[kú ròò] kù ʃíámá]
 [[Dem Foc] Dem precede.Pfv]
 [kú kù ʃíámá], [ā tūù] ò téénè sè,
 [Dem Dem precede.Pfv], [3Sg owner] PfvNeg truth say.Pfv,
 A: ‘... (that) this one [focus] preceded that one, (or) that one preceded this one, the
 fellow (who said that) did not tell the truth.’
 [the two discourse-definite demonstratives denote one and the other of the two founding
 individuals]

(01:30) A á= à fáàmúⁿ nà, ɲūòm bààrà xúòndáà,
 2Sg 3Sg understand.Pfv Q, DemDef happen.Pfv K,
 [ā ròò] [jáà dùgú =ù] kàlà,
 [3Sg Foc] [Dia forest Def] break.Pfv,
 A: ‘Did you-Sg understand it? It happened that Kouanta, it was he [focus] who
 broke (=cleared) the forest of Dia.’
 [standard uptake check; bààrà ‘find, come across (a situation) ...’, §17.3.2.2; dúgū]

(01:36) A ā nṑ ò fáy-nì, [ŋū̀ò̀n sáàⁿ] à gá [à númāā],
 3Sg village sit-Caus.Pfv, [DemDef time] 3Sg be.Loc [3Sg in.mind],
 [íŋ kóón-síré ró̀ò] gá [[tò̀lò = ò] níŋī],
 [Logo alone Foc] be.Loc [[thicket Def] inside],
 A: ‘He founded the village. At that time, it seemed to him that he was alone by himself in the thicket.’
 [númāā ‘in mind’, §8.2.4.4; kóón síré ‘alone, by oneself’, §19.3.2.4; = tò̀lò-gù]

(01:41) A bà= á tṑy gólò-gólò, à =á fùlèè gṑ,
 Seq 3Sg find.Pfv G, 3Sg Ipfv fish.Ipfv there.Def,
 àywà [[fùlé gú] núù-g=] ì,
 well [[fishing(n) Def] interiorDef] Loc,
 A: ‘So it would find him in Gologolo (a pond), he would fish there. Well, during the fishing, ...’

(01:47) A [ā à xáy] [yá= à ná [ŋò̀ò máàn]
 [3Sg 3Sg see.Pfv] [if 3Sg if.Pfv [fish(n) Rel]
 tà-nì bá̀y [jì̀-gù níŋī]],
 ascend-Caus.Pfv exit.Ipfv [water-Def inside]],
 A: ‘... he saw that whatever fish he pulled up out from the water ...’
 [yé/yè ... ná/nà flanking the subject in a perfective conditional antecedent, §16.1.1; tá-ní ‘cause to ascend, take/bring up’, §9.1.2; bá̀y, §15.1.1.5]

(01:50) A ká gá bà̀y yēē, [à ná [fò̀n máàn]
 a.certain Ipfv exit.Ipfv therein, [3Sg if.Pfv [thing Rel]
 tà-nì] [ká gá bà̀y yēē],
 ascend-Caus.Pfv] [a.certain Ipfv exit.Ipfv therein],
 A: ‘... something was missing therein (=from the fish). Whatever (thing) he pulled out, there was something missing from it.’
 [< gá bà̀y]

(01:53) A ā wṑ ú̀!, ā wṑ [fò̀n ò̀ [í fàà]
 3Sg said oh!, 3Sg said [thing not.be.Loc [1Sg by]
 [tò̀lò-g= í] bṑ] [ŋ kò̀n-sìrè ró̀ò] gá bṑ,
 [thicket-Def Loc] here] [1Sg one-alone Foc] be.Loc here,
 A: ‘He said (=thought), “oh!” He said (=thought), “there is nothing with me here in the thicket, I am all by myself here.”’
 [1Sg instead of logophoric in direct thought quotation]

(01:56) A [ŋ fùs ɲà] gá tùnúù, ā bààrà
 [1Sg possession QTop] Ipfv disappear.Ipfv, 3Sg happen.Pfv
 [kìèrè-búú kà-rèè] gá [tìndìŋ-giè xúmà],
 [baobab-trunk certain-Pl] be.Loc [elevation-Pl on],
 A: ‘How come my possession (=fish) is disappearing? It happened that some
 baobab trees were on high spots.’
 [ɲá QTop, §19.1.2; kiererè ‘baobab (esp. fruit)’, kiererè-bùù ‘baobab tree’; tíndííⁿ
 ‘elevation, high ground’]

(02:01) A [ā kìèrè-búú-giè ságà] [à =á bùò],
 [3Sg baobab-trunk-Pl chop.Pfv] [3Sg 3Sg burn.Pfv],
 [à [ɲúó-ní bùy-nà-g=] í]
 [3Sg [DemDef-Link burn-Ppl-Def] Loc]
 [ɲṛṛḍḍ níŋííⁿ] [ā xòó fiḡi]
 [DemDef.Foc inside] [3Sg ashes strew.Pfv]
 A: ‘He felled the baobabs (by chopping), and burned it (=them). It having burned,
 at that point he scattered the ashes.’
 [the ashes were scattered in order to detect footprints; participial clause wutg -g= í
 (here and in the next segment), §15.4.3; búó and bóy-ná, §9.3.1.1, cf. detransitivized
 bóy ‘be burned’ @ 05:09 below; xóḡ]

(02:06) A [xóó-gù [ɲúó-ní fiḡi-nà-g= í]],
 [ashes-Def [DemDef-Link strew-Ppl-Def Loc]],
 ā sàà [ɲṛṛḍḍ ÿ] [júúŋ kélé]
 3Sg lie.down.Pfv [DemDef.Foc Loc] [year day.break.Pfv]
 [ā tṣṣ-m-bùòŋ xáy [xóó-w fáà] jóò,
 [3Sg foot-Link-trace see.Pfv [ashes-Def by]] go.Ipfv,
 A: ‘The ashes having been scattered, he lay down (to sleep) at that point. In the
 morning, he saw footprints going through the ashes.’
 [júúŋ kélé, §11.1.1.2; jóò Ipfv motion verb in supplemental VP, §15.1.1.4]

(02:11) A ā jògí [à fáà] jóò [ɲṛṛḍḍ níŋíí],
 3Sg pursue.Pfv [3Sg by] go.Ipfv [DemDef.Foc inside],
 àlà= à só fiémà, [[kíéŋ xòló-ò] má] gḡ,
 until 3Sg go.Pfv coincide.Pfv, [[hole big-Def] against] there.Def,
 A: ‘He went following it (tracks) at that point, until eventually he went and came
 upon the large pit.’
 [àli ‘until, all the way to’; fiémà, §10.1.3.3.3]

(02:17) A ā [in tòmó] fùúni [ɲɔ̀rɔ̀ ñíjī],
 3Sg [Logo head] lower.Pfv [DemDef.Foc inside],
 ā [in tòmó] fùúni [gèrè máàⁿ],
 3Sg [Logo head] lower.Pfv [place Rel],
 A: ‘He lowered his head (to look) at that point. Where (=when) he had lowered his head, ...’
 [tòmó ‘head’; fùúni, §9.1.2]

(02:21) A ā sò [múò róò] tàwà [kîɛŋ-g= ì],
 3Sg go.Pfv [person Foc] find.Pfv [hole-Def Loc],
 ā tòmó-ò, [ā tòmó-ò] túfà [ɲɔ̀rɔ̀ ÿ],
 3Sg head-Def, [3Sg head-Def] seize.Pfv [DemDef.Foc Loc],
 A: ‘He went and found a person (=Tomota) [focus] in the pit. His (=T’s) head, he (=K) seized his (=T’s) head at that point.’
 [“K” here refers to Kouanta; ā tòmó-ò ‘his (the other’s) head’]

(02:28) A à xwáà ìn tỳ [ɲɔ̀nòò ÿ]
 3Sg again Refl let.Pfv [DemDef.Foc Loc]
 [à =á fùúni xwáà],
 [3Sg 3Sg lower.Pfv again],
 A: ‘He (=K) acted again. He (=K) lowered it (=his own head) again.’
 [xwáà ‘again’, both post-subject and clause-final; ‘let oneself’ meaning ‘intervene (e.g., act, speak up)’]

(02:31) A [kú tòmó] ìn tỳ [à tē], ā wō húòⁿ
 [Dem too] Refl let.Pfv [3Sg Dat], 3Sg said oh!
 ā wo@2 xwáà rà, xwáà [gèrè máàŋ] gú rōò,
 3Sg said again Q, again [place Rel] Def Foc,
 A: ‘That one (=T) in turn acted (=spoke up) to him (=K), he (=T) said, “oh!” he said, “again?” It was then [focus] again (that ...)’
 [kú ‘this/that’ (deictic) in obviative function, §18.3.4.1]

(02:35) A [ɲɔ̀rɔ̀ lāā] yē gà =á yèè xúòndáá-gù,
 [DemDef Purp] 3Pl Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv K-Def
 [xúòndáá-yà gà kírēē] [ɲɔ̀rɔ̀ gà xúòndáá nī],
 [K-Abstr Ipfv find.Ipfv] [DemDef.Foc be.Cop K it.is],
 A: ‘Because of that they call it (=surname) that Kouanta, Kouanta-hood (=Kouanta clan) exists, that is Kouanta.’
 [folk etymology xúòndáá from xwáà rà ; definite -gu added to personal name, §4.1.6; abstractive -yà, §4.2.3.2]

(02:40) A [ā tòmò] ìn tỳ [ḡròò níḡī]
 [3Sg too] Refl let.Pfv [DemDef.Foc inside]
 [ā kōnà] máàḡ gù,
 [3Sg fear(v).Pfv] Rel Def,
 A: ‘He (=K) for his part acted. At the point when he became afraid, ...’
 [*K becomes fearful because of the man’s hostile question*]

(02:42) A ā wō hàywà kúúliḡ-gù [[á tòmò] táà],
 3Sg said well peek.VblN-Def [[3Sg too] stop.Pfv],
 àywà yē [kù tòmò-yòḡ] jíémù, yē wō tò mòdàà,
 well 3Pl [Dem too] speak.Pfv, 3Pl said T,
 A: ‘... he (=K) said, “all right, the spying (on you), it has stopped.” Well, they spoke
 (the name of) that one (=T) too, they said (=called him) “Tomota”.’

(02:48) A [ḡūòḡ sáàⁿ] ā bà= á bààrè [ḡròò níḡī],
 [DemDef time] 3Sg come.Pfv 3Sg remove.Pfv [DemDef.Foc inside}
 [bíé [fédé lāā]], yē bè [ḡ kúnà [bólò tē]],
 [come.Ipfv [outside Purp]], 3Pl come.Pfv [Refl swear.Pfv [Recip Dat]],
 A: ‘Then he (=K) came and brought him (=T) out at that point, (coming) outside
 (of the pit). They (came and) swore an oath to each other.’
 [*< ā bè ; fédé lāā, §8.3.2; motion verb plus perfective VP (twice), §15.1.2*]

(02:54) A [mó-ḡí tòrèèḡ-sèwè] ò síḡèè [bólò mā],
 [person-any pestering(n)-matter] IpfvNeg arrive.Ipfv [Recip against],
 [àlí ḡièn-sààntè] [lásáú-yà máàḡ] gà
 [until tomorrow] [origin-Abstr Rel] be.Loc
 [[káádó [yè tígé]] nāāⁿ],
 [[Dogon.& [and Bozo]] between],
 A: ‘Neither one’s trouble-making would arrive (=happen) against the other. Even
 tomorrow morning (=ever since then), the ancient bond between Dogon and Bozo
 (ethnicities),’
 [*refers to interethnic “cousinage” (joking encouraged but no intermarriage); mó-ḡí
 ‘anybody’ < múò ‘person’ and ḡí ‘any’; tórèèⁿ, séwè combine as compound tórèèḡ-
 séwé ; ḡièn-sààntè, §8.4.5.1; káádó*]

(03:00) A ḡròò gà [[xúàndáá, [yé tò mòdàá]] nāāⁿ],
 DemDef.Foc be.Loc [[K.&, [and T]] between],
 àli yá= àḡ gá bày [tò mòdàà níḡī]
 even if 2Sg Ipfv exit.Ipfv [T inside]
 A: ‘... that is (the relation) between Kouanta and Tomota. (Even) if you-Sg come
 from inside the Tomota (clan), ...’
 [*i.e. the two Bozo clans are in a cousinage relationship*]

(03:03) A yá= àⁿ ná= à yáà [xúàndáà mā]
 if 2Sg if.Pfv 3Sg put.down.Pfv [K against]
 áŋ gá à xéénēē,
 2Sg Ipv 3Sg see.Ipv,

A: 'If you-Sg (a Tomota) put it (=do anything) against the Kouanta, you-Sg (will) see it!'

[‘put down against’ = ‘do anything bad to’; ‘you will see it’ as warning, i.e. ‘you’ll be sorry’]

(03:05) A [ŋōròò gá [ŋūòñ lásálí-yà] nī,
 [DemDef.Foc be.Cop [DemDef origin-Abstr] it.is,
 bon [ŋōròò níŋī] [bí yé tòy [ŋōròò níŋī],
 okay [DemDef.Foc inside] [Seq 3Pl let.Pfv [DemDef.Foc inside],

A: ‘That is the origin of that (relationship). Okay, in that way, they having been left in that (situation), ...’

[sequential VP without a preceding main clause, §15.2.17, cf. @ 04:27 and 06:20 below; 3Pl pronominal is object of ‘let/leave’]

(03:10) A bon áŋ gá à tóò fáámàndáà
 okay 2Sg Ipv 3Sg know.Ipv F
 bon fáámàndáà [fáámàndáà jíyòⁿ nód] nī,
 okay F [F three Foc] it.is,

A: ‘Okay, you-Sg know Famanta (a Bozo clan). Okay, Famanta, it’s (really) three Famanta (clans).’

[as indicated below, Famanta clan inhabited Kuntolo, Yara-Bobon, and Yara-Xara (ancient, now abandoned settlements)]

(03:15) A kún-tóóló fáámàndáà, [ŋūòñ sáàⁿ]
 K F, [DemDef time]
 yè só ŋūòñ tàwá kùn-tòòlò,
 3Pl go.Pfv DemDef find.Pfv K,

A: ‘The Kuntolo Famanta. Then they (K and the man) went and found that one (F) at Kuntolo.’

[Kuntolo was located in what is now a quartier of Dia inhabited by Fulbe, called fílááⁿ-wálí, cf. noun tóóló ‘site with ruins of ancient village’]

(03:19) A [ɲúʒ-ní fàa— fáámàndáà↑, kùn-tòòlò fáámàndáà↑,
 [DemDef-Link (hesitation) F, K F.&,
 fáámàndáà yáará-bòbòɲ ʃì↑, fáámàndáà yáará-xàrà ʃì,
 F Y-B descendent.&, F Y-X descendent,
 A: ‘That Famanta, the Kuntolo Famanta. (The) Famanta descended from
 Yara-Bobon, (the) Famanta descended from Yara-Xara.’
*[conjunction (list) prosody with terminal high pitch ↑ marking incompleteness on
 nonfinal elements; ʃí ‘descendent (of sb)’]*

(03:28) A [ɲúʒ-ní fáámàndáà ʃíyòŋ-gú rōð] gà fáy-nà [kì fáà]
 [DemDef-Link F three-Def Foc] be.Loc sit-Ppl [1PlIn by]
 [[jáà tìndìŋ-gù] xúmà bō],
 [[Dia elevation-Def] on here],
 A: ‘It’s those three Famanta (groups) [focus] that are settled with us, on the high
 ground of Dia here.’
[definite suffix after numeral]

(03:32) A àywà [ɲūðn sáàⁿ], yē sò [ɲūðⁿ-yè tòmò]
 well [DemDef time], 3Pl go.Pfv [DemDef-Pl too]
 [xàlù ʃíyòŋ-gù] tàwá [[kùn-tòòlò dùgú-g=] ì],
 [man three-Def] find.Pfv [[K forest-Def] Loc],
 A: ‘Well, then they (=K&T) went and found those ones (F) too, the three men, in
 the forest of Kuntolo.’
[dúgū]

(03:36) A é! yē wō múð-yé xày bō, yē bày
 oh! 3Pl said person-Pl Prsntv here, 3Sg exit.Pfv
 [ɲōròð níŋī] [bí sàà [[[ɲūðⁿ-yè tòmò] xóórò] xúmà]],
 [DemDef.Foc inside] [Seq follow.Pfv [[[DemDef-Pl too] back] on]],
 A: ‘“Oh,” they (K&T) said. “Look! People are there!” They (K&T) set off then to
 follow behind those ones (=F).’
*[presentative xāy, §4.4.3; ‘exit’ here means ‘set off, go into (motion)’ with following
 sequential VP; sáa as reflexive verb ‘lie down’ but as intransitive plus PP ‘after/behind’
 it means ‘follow after, pursue’]*

(03:40) A [múð pèndèèŋ-gù] ɲūðⁿ-yè xéélè, [ɲūðⁿ-yè xéélè máàŋ]
 [person two-Def] DemDef-Pl run.Pfv, [DemDef-Pl run.Pfv Rel]
 yè kóðŋ kùⁿ, yē ɲōðⁿ fáy-nì [yè fáà] gō,
 3Pl one catch.Pfv, 3Pl DemDef sit-Caus.Pfv [RefIPl by] there.Def,
 A: ‘The two people (K&T), those ones (K&T) ran. As those ones ran, they caught
 one (=F). They had that one settle by them there.’
[relative máàⁿ as headless relative in adverbial clause]

(03:48) A *bon* ηūðⁿ fáy [dé [yè jíyó-nàá] nī],
 okay DemDef become.Pfv [for [3Pl three-Ord it.is],
bon [bí yé tày [ηðrðð níηī] [ηūðn sááⁿ],
 okay [Seq 3Pl let.Pfv [DemDef.Foc inside] [DemDef time],
 A: ‘They had that one settle as their third (member). Okay, they were left in that situation then.’

[ordinal = nāā, §4.6.2.2; nīⁿ postposition in context of transformation, §8.1.2.3]

(03:53) A yà= á [ηðrðð níηī] [yé [xàlù kóðη] xáy]
 3Pl be.Loc [DemDef.Foc inside] [3Pl [man one] see.Pfv]
 [[ηūðⁿ =à [jíé-xàlù fáà]] [à gá biè],
 [[3Sg be.Loc [horse-male by]] [3Sg Ipfv come.Ipfv],
 A: ‘(As) they were in that (situation), they saw a man. That one (=man), he was coming on a stallion.’

(03:57) A [ηūðm bè [gèrè máàⁿ]] [[ā tòmð] bè [yé tàwá]
 [DemDef come.Pfv [place Rel]] [[3Sg too] come.Pfv [3Pl find.Pfv]
 [[gólò-gólò tìndìη-gú ròð] xúmà] gō],
 [[G elevation-Def Foc] on] there.Def]],
 A: ‘Where (=when) that one (=horseman) came, he (=horseman) for his part came and found them on the high ground at Gologolo.’

(04:00) A àywà álá= á fūð,
 well God 3Sg want.Pfv,
 ā bàárà [[ηððⁿ fíéré-yè] gà [à fáà]],
 3Sg happen.Pfv [[slave many-Pl] be.Loc [3Sg by]],
 A: ‘Well, (as) God willed, it happened that many slaves had been with him (=horseman).’

[fíéré, §6.4.2.1]

(04:04) A kómì [fðⁿ máàⁿ-yè] bày [ηūðⁿ-yè níηī]
 like [thing Rel-Pl] exit.Pfv [DemDef-Pl inside]
 [ηūðⁿ [xáy bàánà-yè] nī] [ηúà= à gíndò nī]
 [DemDef [1PlIn exclusively-Pl] it.is] [DemDef be.Cop secret it.is]
 A: ‘Like, the ones that originated in (=descended from) those ones (=slaves). That is strictly (between) us (inclusive), that is confidential.’

[i.e. it is nowadays impolite to speak of slaves; kómì < French *comme* ‘like’ cf. ìṅgàásēē, §8.4.1.1; bàánà ‘exclusively’, §19.3.2.5; ηūðη gà; gíndò (< Bambara) ‘secret, private information’, synonym sùurdéèⁿ]

(04:07) A [ŋúà = à ŋúndùúⁿ nī], àywà [ŋūðn sáàⁿ]
 [DemDef be.Cop secret it.is], well [DemDef time]
 [[ŋóó ñ-kóòⁿ nōò] kòòná = [á sīⁿ]]
 [[slave Link-one Foc] remain.Pfv [3Sg in.hand]]
 A: ‘That is private. Then a single slave was left in his (=horseman’s) custody.’
 [*< kóónó ; possessive with sīⁿ, §11.4.1.2*]

(04:11) A [ā hūnù] ìⁿ fáy
 [3Sg Top] Refl sit.Pfv
 [ā hílá [[ìⁿ jòò] jìè] tē]],
 [3Sg be.busy.Pfv [[Refl fish] eat.VblN] Dat]],
 A: ‘He for his part sat down, he busied himself with eating his fish-Sg.’
 [*< hílā ; possessive with sīⁿ, §11.4.1.2*]

(04:13) A àywà [yē tòmò] wō ā! yē wō [sāw húnù]
 well [3Pl too] said ah! 3Pl said [now Top]
 xáy yáà [dē, náárà nī], [tíndííŋ-gú xúmà] gòy,
 1PlIn become.Pfv [for, four it.is], [elevation-Def on] Emph,
 A: ‘Well, they said “ah!” They said “now we (inclusive) sure have become four,
 (here) on the high ground.”’
 [*yáà dè, §11.2.4.2; náárà ‘might one, formidable one’; góy, §19.4.1.1*]

(04:17) A xáy dì [múò ñ-kóòn] lèè
 1PlEx IpfvNeg [person Link-one] pick.up.Ipfv
 [kyá = á dùñè-nì [kí kìé-nà]],
 [1PlIn 3Sg precede-Caus.Pfv [1PlIn ahead.of-Ppl]],
 A: ‘(They said:) “Shall we not pick one person and put him ahead of us (as our
 leader)?”’
 [*kìé-nà, §8.2.7.3.2, cf. kìéⁿ below @ 04:24*]

(04:20) A [ŋūðm bàárà] [híní gà [[á rōò] mā]]
 [DemDef happen.Pfv] [wealth be.Loc [[3Sg Foc] against]]
 [án dí màà [jámà mārāā]]
 [2Sg IpfvNeg be.able.Ipfv [crowd govern.Ipfv]]
 A: ‘It happened that that he (=horseman) had wealth. You-Sg cannot manage
 (=support) a crowd ...’
 [*jāmā ; mārā ‘govern, administer; raise, support, bring up (child)’*]

(04:24) A [yá= àn dí hìnì-n-tùù nī],
 [if 2Sg not.be.Cop wealth-Link-owner it.is],
 [[yē tòmò] á lèè] [yà= á dùṅè-nì, [yé kìéⁿ]],
 [[3Pl too] 3Sg pick.up.Pfv] [3Pl 3Sg precede-Caus.Pfv, [RefIPl before]],
 A: ‘... if you-Sg are not a wealthy person. They for their part picked him and put
 him ahead of them (as leader).’
*[‘owner’ compound, §5.1.7; two complete indicative clauses “conjoined” by
 juxtaposition without a break, §7.1.12]*

(04:27) A *bon* [bí yé tỳ [ṅṛòḍò níṅī]], àywà,
 okay [Seq 3Pl let.Pfv [DemDef.Foc inside]], well,
 yē wō hàywà [nòḍn dí màà mérēē]
 3Pl said well [village IpfvNeg be.able.Ipfv be.governed.Ipfv]
 A: ‘Okay, they having been left in that (situation), they said, “well, a village cannot
 be governed ...” ’
[mérè detransitivied < mārà, §9.3.1.1]

(04:32) A [yā= ā ò [fàriyá [yè fàriyá]] [yē wō] hàywà
 [if 3Sg not.be.Cop [law.& [and law]]] [3Pl said] well
 [yē wō] [kì mà láámà bùò]],
 [3Pl said] [IPlIn Proh the.bush burn.Pfv]],
 A: ‘ “... if not (by) laws.” They said, “well,” they said, “let us not burn the bush
 (=outback, surrounding forest).” ’
*[yā= ā ò ‘if it’s not’ = ‘other than, aside from, without’; IPl prohibitive functioning
 as hortative negative, §10.4.2.2]*

(04:36) A [múḍ má [jìrì xààmù] ságà, [jírì máàṅ]
 [person Proh [tree wet] chop.Pfv, [tree Rel]
 gá [jìrì lànsàà] nī, múḍ má ṅūḍn ságà,
 be.Cop [tree fertile] it.is, person Proh DemDef chop.Pfv,
 A: ‘ “Let nobody chop down any wet (=living) tree. Any tree that is a fertile (=fruit-
 bearing) tree, let nobody chop that one down.” ’
[a correlative-like relative construction, §14.1.9]

(04:41) A [yè [ṅúó-ní fàriyá-giè fìèⁿ] fáy-nì]
 [3Pl [DemDef-Link law-Pl all] sit-Caus.Pfv]
 [máàṅ fìèⁿ] ná—, ṅúó— fàriyá-giè sósò,
 [Rel all] if.Pfv, DemDef— law-Pl violate.Pfv,
 A: ‘They established all those laws. (If there is) anyone who violates those laws,
 ...’
[for ṅúó-ní fàriyá-giè < fàriyá LH-toned after demonstrative, §6.5.3]

(04:45) A áŋ gá náŋgī, bon [bí yé tày [ŋɔ̄rɔ̄ɔ níŋī]],
 2Sg Ipfv be.punished.Ipfv, okay [Seq 3Pl let.Pfv [DemDef.Foc inside]],
 [[fáájèè è láámà-g=] ì]
 [[F the.bush-Def] Loc]

A: ‘... you-Sg will be punished. Okay, they having been left in that (situation), out in the bushland of Fadiene, ...’

[assistant suggests emendation to yè gá àⁿ náŋgī ‘they (will) punish you-Sg’, transitive verb náŋgì]

(04:50) A yā= à xáy [[tùù-tòòrò xòlól] kèlè gō],
 3Pl 3Sg saw.Pfv [[fire-post big] be.lit.Pfv there.Def],
 ē! ā wō [xáy ród] béeⁿ [à xúmà]]
 oh! 3Sg said [1PlIn Foc] agree.Pfv [3Sg on]]

A: ‘They saw that a big fire was lit (on the ground) there. “Hey,” he (=chief) said, “we (inclusive) [focus] have agreed on it.”’

[lit. “they saw it, ...”; túú ‘fire’, tóórō ‘hitching post’, túú-tóórō ‘fire on ground, campfire’; béeⁿ ‘agree (on)’ < Bambara, cf. méè]

(04:55) A [xáy wō→, [túú má kèlè] [túú má kèlè]
 [1PlIn said, [fire Proh be.lit.Pfv] [fire Proh be.lit.Pfv]
 [sāw láámà-gú xāy], ā wō [xā sō à tónò],
 [now the.bush-Def Prsntv], 3Sg said [2Pl.Imprt go.Pfv 3Sg look.at.Pfv],

A: ‘We said, “fire must not be lit! Fire must not be lit! Now there’s the bush(=outback).” He (=chief) said, “you-Pl go look at it!”’

[2Pl imperative with xā, §10.4.1.1]

(05:00) A [yē bày [ŋɔ̄rɔ̄ɔ níŋī]] [yè só à tónò],
 [3Pl exit.Pfv [DemDef.Foc inside]] [3Pl go.Pfv 3Sg look.at.Pfv],
 yē bàárà [[xàlù xòndòmòndò kà] =á gō]—
 3Pl happen.Pfv [[man old a.certain] be.Loc there.Def]—

A: ‘They went out at that point, they went and looked at it (=the bush). They found that an old man was there—’

(05:04) A [[kóròŋ gá [á sīⁿ]] [à =á tùù-gù kòrî]
 [[skin be.Loc [3Sg in.hand]] [3Sg Ipfv fire-Def hit.Ipfv]
 [à gá yèè [íŋ gá tùù-wù wáá [à gā]],
 [3Sg Ipfv say.Ipfv [Logo Ipfv fire-Def kill.Ipfv [3Sg Inst]],

A: ‘He (=old man) had an (animal) skin. He was swatting the fire (with it), he said (=intended) he was extinguishing the fire with it.’

[i.e. he was trying to extinguish the fire]

(05:06) A [yà= á kùⁿ [ŋɔ̄rɔ̄ɔ̄ ÿ]] [yē bà= [á tīⁿ]]
 [3Pl 3Sg catch.Pfv [DemDef.Foc Loc]] [3Pl come.Pfv [3Sg under]],
 [yé wō [kù túù] múò wō→,
 [3Pl said [Dem owner] 1PIEx said,
 A: ‘They arrested him (=old man). They brought him. They said, “So-and-so, we
 (exclusive) said ...” ’
 [kù túù ‘so-and-so’, literally perhaps “owner of this/that”, §5.1.7]

(05:09) A [láámà-gù dì bóy, [múò járiyà fáy-nì]
 [the.bush-Def IpfvNeg be.burned.Ipfv, [1PIEx law sit-Caus.Pfv]
 [áⁿ [múò járiyá-gù] sósò] [múò àŋ kùm bìè],
 [2Sg [1PIEx law-Def] violate.Pfv] [1PIEx 2Sg catch.Pfv come.Ipfv],
 A: ‘ “the bush is not (=will not be) burned. We established the law. You-Sg have
 violated our law (and) we arrested and brought you (here).’
 [< kùⁿ ; the final bíé here indicates motion of the old man (object of the main verb),
 §15.1.1.4]

(05:13) A ā wō á!, ā wō [ŋ húnù yóròó-gù]
 3Sg said ah! 3Sg said [1Sg Top self-Def]
 [ŋ gà jírifú ròò ní], á= à fáàmúⁿ,
 [1Sg be.Cop cherif Foc it.is], 2Sg 3Sg understand.Pfv,
 A: ‘He said, “Ah!” He said, “as for me myself, I am a cherif (descendant of the
 Prophet)” Did you-Sg understand it?’

(05:18) A yē wō é→, yē wō [áj gá jírifú ní],
 3Pl said “eh?”, 3Pl said [2Sg be.Cop cherif it.is],
 ā wō [yá= àŋ gà jírifú ní]
 3Sg said [if 2Sg be.Cop cherif it.is]
 A: ‘They said, “eh?” He (=chief) said, “you-Sg are a cherif? If you-Sg are a cherif,
 ...”

(05:21) A [máà gà múò hólá-nì yēē]
 [what? Ipfv 1PIEx trust(v)-Caus.Ipfv therein]
 [ŋūòm bààrà fànáàŋ jírifú [tùù dà= á bùó fìèw]],
 [DemDef happen.Pfv firstly cherif [fire IpfvNeg 3Sg burn.Ipfv at.all]],
 A: ‘ “... What will make us (exclusive) trust therein?” As it happened, in the old
 days fire didn’t burn a cherif at all’
 [i.e., ‘what will prove that to us?’; ‘cherif’ fronted as topic and resumed as 3Sg; fìéw
 ‘(not) at all’, §6.3.2.5]

(05:25) A á= à fáàmú,
 2Sg 3Sg understand.Pfv,
 ā wō [yá= àŋ gà jířífú nī] ā wō→,
 3Sg said [if 2Sg be.Cop cherif it.is] 3Sg said,
 ā wō, [yē bèlèŋ-xòrì yáà [tùù xúmà] [ŋòròò ò]]
 3Sg said, [3Pl frying.pan put.Pfv [fire on]] [DemDef.Foc Loc],
 A: ‘Did you-Sg understand it? He (=chief) said, he said, “they have put a frying pan on the fire in that [focus].” ’

(05:31) A [yē tùù lòn [á tīīⁿ]]
 [3Pl fire put.in.Pfv [3Sg Dat]]
 [yē cìè-gù sólò [àlá= à múò],
 [3Pl oil-Def cook.Pfv [until 3Sg be.cooked.Pfv],
 A: ‘(said: “They have put fire under it. They have boiled the oil, until it was done (=boiling).” ’

(05:34) A ŋūòŋ sáàⁿ, jáá-màŋà-gù [im bààkí-gù] bàà
 DemDef time, Dia-master-Def [Refl ring-Def] remove.Pfv
 [[in sùù] ò]] [ā à gòŋ jóò [bèlèŋ-xòrì-g= ò]],
 [[Refl hand] Loc]] [3Sg 3Sg drop.Pfv go.Ipfv [frying.pan-Def Loc]],
 A: ‘Then the chief of Dia (village) removed his ring from off his hand, (and) he dropped it onto the frying pan.’
 [báákí (French bague); gòⁿ ; jóò specifies motion of the ring (object of ‘drop’), §15.1.1.5]

(05:38) A ā wō hàywà sò→, bààkí-gù lèè, [cìè-g= ò]
 3Sg said well go.Pfv, ring-Def pick.up.Pfv, [oil-Def Loc]
 [yá= àŋ gà jířífú nī] [ā wō hé→]
 [if 2Sg be.Cop cherif it.is] [3Sg said hey!]
 A: ‘He (=chief) said, “well, go (and) pick up the ring in the oil, if you-Sg are a cherif.” He (=old man) said, “hey!” ’

(05:42) A ā wō [kú dí síŋéé
 3Sg said [Dem IpfvNeg arrive.Ipfv
 [ŋ húnù yóròó-gù tó] gòy,
 [1Sg Top self-Def at] Emph,
 A: ‘He (=old man) said, “this sure isn’t worthy of me myself.”’
 [i.e. it’s too easy; tō, §8.3.3, here H-toned before an L-tone]

(05:44) A [ā wō [ɪŋ ɲḁḁ-xàlù-gù tē]] sô [swá= á lèè],
 [3Sg said [[Refl slave-male-Def] Dat] go.Pfv [go.Pfv 3Sg pick.up.Pfv],
 [só á lèè] [ám bà= [á là [à gā]]],
 [go.Pfv 3Sg pick.up.Pfv [2Sg come.Pfv [3Sg give.Pfv [3Sg Dat]]],
 A: ‘He (=old man) said to his male slave, “go-2Sg (and) go pick it up! Go pick it
 up, then bring it to him (=chief)!” ’
 [doubled motion verb, cf. plural addressee xà sô [xà swá= á lèè], §15.1.2.1; < ló ~ lá
 ‘give’]

(05:48) S só [àn sùù] lò [cìè-g= ì]
 go.Pfv [2Sg hand] put.in.Pfv [oil-Def Loc]
 [áⁿ ná á lèè]
 [2Sg Sbjn 3Sg pick.up.Pfv]
 S: ‘ “Go put your-Sg hand in the oil, and pick it up!” ’
 [S has been quietly listening but interjects here; subjunctive clause added on to
 imperative, §17.4.1.1]

(05:49) A [áⁿ ná á lèè]
 [2Sg Sbjn 3Sg pick.up.Pfv]
 [áⁿ ná bà= [á là [à gā]]],
 [2Sg Sbjn come.Pfv [3Sg give.Pfv [3Sg Dat]]],
 A: ‘ “... and pick it up, and come and give it to him (=chief)!” ’
 [A resumes the narration]

(05:50) A [[ā tòmḁ] só [ɪn sùù] lò [cìè-g= ì]]
 [[3Sg too] go.Pfv [Refl hand] put.in.Pfv [oil-Def Loc]]
 [à á lèè báý yēē],
 [3Sg 3Sg pick.up.Pfv exit.Ipfv therein],
 A: ‘He (=slave) went and put his hand in the oil, (and) he picked it up and took it
 out from there.’
 [báý ‘exit.Ipfv’, here H-toned due to yēē, has directional sense, §15.1.1.5]

(05:52) A [ā bà= á là [à gā]]
 [3Sg come.Pfv 3Sg give.Pfv [3Sg Dat]]
 àywà [ɲūḁn sáàⁿ] [[kú tómó] ín tóy],
 well [DemDef time] [[Dem too] Refl let.Pfv],
 A: ‘He (slave) came and gave it to him (=chief). Well, then that one (=chief) acted
 (=spoke up).’

(05:55) A ā wō á!, ā wō [áɲ ʃírífú-yà-gù]
 3Ssg said ah!, 3Ssg said [2Ssg cherif-Abstr-Def]
 ɲ hòðlá yēē,
 1Sg trust.Pfv therein,
 A: ‘He (=chief) for his part said, “Ah!” He said, “your-Sg cherif-hood, I trust (=believe) in it!”
 [abstractive, §4.2.3.2]

(05:57) A ā wō ɲkàà [láámà-gù kúúrì-gù], ā wō
 3Ssg said but [the.bush.Def circle-Def], 3Ssg said
 n̄ nà kúúrì-gù— nà— [n̄ nà à kúyà= [àⁿ mā],
 (hesitations) [1Sg Sbj/Obj 3Sg grant.Pfv [2Sg against],
 A: ‘He (=chief) said, “but this area of the bushland,” he said, “I (hereby) grant it to you-Sg.”
 [< kúyè ; portions of this segment broken]

(06:02) A [ɲɔ̄rðò gà [[fáájèèè láámà-g=] ì] [á ɲièn-sààntè],
 [DemDef.Foc be.Loc [[F the.bush-Def] Loc] [3Sg tomorrow],
 ʃì á bì yáà [dé kààzìyé nì] gù,
 since 3Sg Fut become.Pfv [for reservoir it.is] Def,
 A: ‘That is in the bushland of Fadiene, (even) tomorrow morning (=ever since then).
 Before it (=Fadiene) became a reservoir.’
 [ɲièn-sààntè, §8.4.5.1; ʃìⁿ ‘since’ in ‘before’ clause, §17.2.5.2; kààzìyé < French casier ‘reservoir’ (in the modern irrigation system managed by the Office du Niger); n̄ is L-toned here even before L-tone because of preceding LH-tones, compare dé sòò ní gù ‘(beame) a goat’]

(06:08) A [ɲɔ̄rðò gà [[[ɲúó-ní lààmà-gù] kírè-sàbàbú] n̄i]
 [DemDef.Foc be.Cop [[[DemDef-Link the.bush-Def] get.VblN-reason] it.is]
 parce que [jáà láámà-láámà máàɲ ʃìèⁿ],
 because [Dia Iter-the.bush Rel all],
 A: ‘That is the reason (=origin) of the acquiring of that bushland. Because whatever (sections of) bushland of Dia, ...’
 [stem iteration (full reduplication)]

(06:11) A [máàɲ ʃìèⁿ] nà á sè
 [Rel all] if.Pfv 3Sg say.Pfv
 [kú-nú lààmà-gù] gá [nɔ̄ð fùó] n̄i,
 [Dem-Link the.bush-Def] be.Cop [1Sg.Foc possession] it.is,
 A: ‘..., anyone at all who claims, “this bushland is my property,” ...’
 [fúó, §6.2.2.2]

(06:14) A [yá= àⁿ ná [à túù] sègè-sègè]
 [if 2Sg if.Pfv [3Sg owner] check.out.Pfv]
 [kírè-xààŋ ká rðð] gà [á síⁿ],
 [get.VblN-neck a.certain Foc] be.Loc [3Sg in.hand],
 A: ‘if you-Sg check the fellow out, (to verify whether) he has some proof [focus],
 ...’
 [kírè ‘get.VblN’, xááⁿ ‘neck’, kírè-xààⁿ ‘evidence, proof’ (‘neck’ associated with
 truthful speech)]

(06:17) S [sábábú kà] =á yēē
 [reason a.certain] be.Loc therein
 A [sábábú kà] =á bàárāā
 [reason a.certain] be.Loc happen.Ipfv
 [ā kírè [ŋðrðð y]]
 [3Sg be.gotten.Pfv [DemDef.Foc Loc]]
 S: ‘... there is some reason (=explanation) therein.’
 A: ‘There happens to be some reason (why) it was obtained in that (way).’
 [S interjects a comment]

(06:20) A bon [ŋūðn sààⁿ], yē ŋūðn là [ŋūðŋ gā],
 okay [DemDef time], 3Pl DemDef give.Pfv [DemDef Dat],
 àywà [bí yé tỳ [ŋðnðð y]]
 well [Seq 3Pl let.Pfv [DemDef.Foc Loc]]
 A: ‘Okay, then they gave that (bushland) to that one (=cherif). Well, the having
 been left in that (way), ...’

(06:25) A [fáy-gù húnù] kóónóò→, xíyáá-yà→ fòò biè,
 [sit.VblN-Def Top remain.Ipfv, long-Inch.Pfv go.Ipfv come.Ipfv,
 [àywà álá á fū̄̄]
 [well God 3Sg want.Pfv]
 A: ‘... sitting (=dwelling there) kept on for a long time, going and coming. (As)
 God willed, ...’
 [prolongation with falling pitch (twice), §3.7.1.4]

(06:29) A [à-ní jàà-màṅà kóóŋ-kðóŋ] kòònò gō,
 [Dem-Link Dia-master Iter-one] remain.Pfv there.Def,
 álá ðì [júrúyá sèwé] xòrð-nì [yè mā]
 God PfvNeg [progeny matter] become.hard-Caus.Pfv [3Pl against],
 A: ‘... those chiefs of Dia (village) continued on there, one after the other. God did
 not harden (=make difficult) the matter of descent on them.’
 [à-ní, §6.5.4; distributive iteration of numeral, §4.1.5.1.1, see also the following
 segment; júrúyā ~ zúrúyā < Arabic ذرية ; séwè]

(06:33) A [ɲũ̀ðm bààrà] [mú̀ð-giè kóónóò
 [DemDef happen.Pfv] [person-Pl remain.Ipfv
 [biè kóóŋ-kóóm péndéém-péndééⁿ],
 [come.Ipfv Iter-one Iter-two]],

A: ‘It happened that (new) people kept coming, one or two at a time.’

[i.e. sporadically, intermittently; kóónóò, §10.3.4]

(06:36) A [kómà= à wō→, [[kílée ród] nà=]
 [as 3Sg said [[key Foc] it.is]
 ā mà xíyáá-yà [[mìnítí tàn] tē],
 3Sg Proh long-Inch.Pfv [[minute ten] Dat],

A: ‘Seeing that he said, it’s a key (=memory stick), it (=recording) mustn’t exceed ten minutes.’

[French comme; A departs from the narrative to check whether the audio file will exceed the limit; cf. French clé USB ‘memory stick, flash drive’; mìnítí ‘minute’]

(06:39) A ɲ gá bi— [màsáálà-gù gèrè kà] búdi-búdi,
 1Sg Ipfv Fut— [conversation-Def place a.certain] cut-cut.Pfv,
 àywà [ɲũ̀ðn sáàⁿ] mú̀ð-giè kóónóò kóóŋ-kóóm biè
 well [DemDef time] person-Pl remain.Ipfv Iter-one come.Ipfv
 [kóóŋ-kóóm biè],
 [(repetition)]

A: ‘I will be cutting a portion of the talk. [resumes narrative:] Well, at that time, people kept coming one at a time, coming one at a time.’

(06:45) A àywà jáà bè fáy [dè dálílú-nòò nī],
 well Dia come.Pfv become.Pfv [for knowledge-village it.is],
 ā bè fáy [dè [tóy-ná]-nòò nī],
 3Sg come.Pfv become.Pfv [for [know-Ppl]-village it.is],

A: ‘Well, Dia became a village of (=known for) (mystical) knowledge. It became a village of savants.’

[fáy [dē X [nī], §11.2.4.2; dálílú ‘deep religious or mystical knowledge’, tóy ‘knowledge’]

(06:50) A [ɲũ̀ðn sáàⁿ] [jáá-màŋà jù̀ðⁿ],
 [DemDef time] [Dia-master child],
 [júruyá-sèwé bè [xòrò-yà [à mā]]]
 [descent-matter come.Pfv [hard-Inch.Pfv [3Sg against]]]

A: ‘At that time, the son of the chief of Dia, descent (=producing an heir) became difficult for him.’

[‘come’ plus perfective VP, §15.1.2.1]

(06:53) A [ā bè [xòrò-yà [à mā]],
 [3Sg come.Pfv [hard-Inch.Pfv [3Sg against]],
 [ā bè ìn tòy [ɲòròò níŋī]] [ā wō á!],
 [3Sg come.Pfv Refl let.Pfv [DemDef.Foc inside]] [3Sg said ah!],
 A: ‘It became difficult for him. He intervened (spoke up) at that point. He said,
 “ah!” ’

(06:56) A ā wō→, [nóŋ-gu [kú-nú→, mùò làmà]]
 3Sg said, [village-Def [Dem-Link person a.few]]
 [xá jíén] dálílú-tùù, [xá jíéŋ] [kù-ŋùòŋ]-tùù,
 [2Pl all] knowledge-owner, [2Pl all] [whatchamacallit?]-owner,
 A: ‘He said, “(you) these several people of (=in) the village, all you-Pl savants, all
 you-Pl (owners of) whatchamacallit.” ’
 [lámá ‘a few’, §6.4.2.4; kù-ŋùòŋ ‘whatchamacallit?’, §4.4.4]

(07:01) A ā wō [júrúyá xāy] [ā xòrò-yà [m mā]],
 3Sg said [descent Prsntv] [3Sg hard-Inch.Pfv [1Sg against]],
 ā wō [yè ní dì jùòŋ kírè],
 3Sg said [if 1Sg PfvNeg child get.Pfv],
 A: ‘He said, “look, descent (=having an heir) here has been hard for me.” He said,
 “if I don’t get a child, ...” ’
 [< yé ò dí]

(07:04) A [ŋ gú [xà jíèŋ] sàà-nì]
 [1Sg Fut [2Pl all] lie.down-Caus.Pfv]
 [ŋ gú [xà jíèŋ] xààná-bàlà],
 [1Sg Fut [2Pl all] slaughter.Pfv],
 A: ‘ “I will have all of you lie down and I will slaughter (=cut the throat of) all of
 you.” ’
 [The savants are charged with giving the chief a child]

(07:06) A [ŋúó-ní wààdú-gì] [yē gà á sèè]
 [DemDef-Link time-Def] [3Pl Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv]
 [máálù lỳ] gá [àn dúŋè] ní,
 [M enter.VblN] be.Cop [2Sg agree.VblN] it.is,
 A: ‘ “At that time, whether to go into (the place) they call Malou is your-Sg
 decision, ...” ’
 [Malou is a quartier of Dia]

(07:08) A [ńkàà [ā báy] dá= [àn dúṅè] nī],
 [but [3Sg exit.VblN] not.be.Cop [2Sg agree.VblN] it.is],
 [ā kūùṅ ʃìèṅ] gá ṅūḍⁿ nī,
 [3Sg reason all] be.Cop DemDef it.is,

A: ‘ “... but leaving it is not your-Sg decision. That is the reason for it.’

(07:10) A ā wō [ìṅ gù [yé ʃìèṅ] xàaná-bàlà]
 3Sg said [Logo Fut [3Pl all] slaughter.Pfv]
 [yē tòmò] bólò xēⁿ,
 [3Sg too] Recip call.Pfv,

A: ‘He said that he would slaughter them all. They for their part called (=consulted with) each other.’

(07:15) A é! [ṅūḍm bàárà]
 oh! [DemDef happen.Pfv]
 [ká-xòḍ kà] gá [nóṅ-g= í] bō,
 [father-house a.certain] be.Loc [village-Def Loc] here,

A: ‘(they said) “Oh!” There happens to be a certain patri-clan here in the village.’

(07:15) A yē wō hàywà, yē ìn tỳ] [yē wō]
 3Pl said well, 3Pl Refl let.Pfv [3Pl said]
 [kì kímè] [kyá= [á xòlò-nì] là [kù gā],
 [1PlIn.Hort unite] [1PlIn [3Sg big-Caus.VblN] give.Pfv [Dem Dat],

A: ‘They said, “well,” those ones (=clan) intervened (=spoke up). They said, “let’s unite, let’s give this (clan) its honor.” ’

[1Pl hortatives, §10.4.2.1; xólò-nì ‘greatness; honor’]

(07:20) A [máàṅ ʃì=] =á hìnî, ʃíéⁿ [íⁿ hínèè] wàlé yēē,
 [Rel all] Ipfv be.able.Ipfv, all [Refl ability.] do.Pfv therein,
 ā wō [ṅūḍn sááⁿ],
 3Sg said [DemDef time],

ā bè [ìn tỳ [ṅṵrḍḍ níṅī]]
 3Sg come.Pfv [Refl let.Pfv [DemDef.Foc inside]]

A: ‘Whoever was able, each one did his best therein. He (=a savant) said then, he intervened (=spoke up) in that situation.’

[ʃíéⁿ ‘all’ in distributive sense ‘each’, §6.6.2.1]

(07:25) A [ā bɛ̀], [jíní-júʂⁿ-yààlù rɔ̀] bàà— [ā kūjì=] ỳ,
 [3Sg come.Pfv], [genie-child-female Foc] remove.Pfv— [3Sg belly] Loc,
 ā bà= à yàà ʃò̀,
 2Sg come.Pfv 3Sg put.Pfv go.Ipfv,

A: 'He came and took out a genie girl—, from her belly (the belly of a female genie). He came and put it in.'

[jíní 'genie'; the savant took a genie fetus out of the womb of a genie woman and put it into the womb of the chief's wife; it turns out later that the genie child is male rather than female; kūjù 'belly']

(07:32) A [[[jáá-màṅà, yáálù-gù] kūjù] núùṅ-g=] ì], [ṅū̀ḍṅ sáà^m]
 [[Dia-master, woman-Def] belly] interior-Def] Loc], [DemDef time]
 [kūjù núùṅ-gù] kóónò̀ ʃò̀ [à =á xòlɔ́-yāā]
 [belly interior-Def] remain.Ipfv go.Ipfv [3Sg Ipfv big-Inch.Ipfv]

A: 'Inside the belly of the woman (=wife) of the chief of Dia. Then the interior of the belly kept going and getting bigger ...'

(07:36) A [à =á xòlɔ́-yāā], àlà= á bɛ̀ kírɛ̀,
 [3Sg Ipfv big-Inch.Ipfv], until 3Sg come.Pfv give.birth.Pfv
 kúmà= àlà= á bɛ̀ síṅɛ̀ [fùlè mā],
 like until 3Sg come.Pfv arrive.Pfv [fishing(n) against],

A: '... and bigger. Eventually she gave birth. Like, eventually she (=girl) attained (the age of) fishing.'

[kírɛ̀ 'get' (as transitive), 'give birth' as intransitive; children begin fishing at age ten]

(07:41) A [ṅū̀ḍṅ bàárà], [kómbó kòʂⁿ nɔ̀] gà [nóḍṅ-g= ì]
 [DemDef happen.Pfv], [pond one Foc] be.Loc [village-Def Loc]
 yà= =á ṅòr̀ḍḍ fùlè̀,
 3Pl Ipfv DemDef fish.Ipfv,

A: 'It happened that there was (just) a single seasonal pond in the village, they used to fish that (swamp).'

[kómbó 'swamp, seasonal pond', flooded in the rainy season]

(07:46) A àywà [ṅū̀ḍṅ sáàⁿ], [ṅū̀ḍṅ bàárà]
 well [DemDef time], [DemDef happen.Pfv]
 yē gà á xèénì kómbó-kòmbò̀,
 3Pl Ipfv 3Sg call.Ipfv K,

A: 'Well, then it happened that they called it Kombokombo.'

[name of a large seasonal pond east of Dia]

(07:49) A ʃòò [[[sísé làà] kómbò-g=] ì] [ɲū̀ðm bààrà]
 go.Ifv [[[Cissé door] pond-Def] Loc] [DemDef happen.Pfv]
 yē gà á yèé [yè tē] kómbó-kòmbò kómbó-kòmbò,
 3Pl Ipfv 3Pl say.Ipfv [3Pl Dat] K K

A: ‘On the way to the Cissé family’s pond. It happened that they called them (both) Kombokombo, Kombokombo.’

[the Cissé clan’s pond is part of the Kombokombo complex]

(07:54) A ā wō [ɲū̀ðn sáàⁿ], gíémááⁿ nú̀ù→,
 3Sg said [DemDef time], G interior,
 ā kírè, ā kírè [wààdù máàⁿ],
 3Sg give.birth.Pfv, 3Sg give.birth.Pfv [time Rel],

A: ‘She (=chief’s wife) said then, (in) pregnancy with Giema, she (=chief’s wife) gave birth. When she gave birth, ...’

[G is the name of the genie child who was born; nú̀ù ‘interior; womb, pregnancy’; wáàdū ‘time’]

(08:00) A ā bè jù̀ðn t̄̄̄ [ā wō gíèmààⁿ],
 3Sg come.Pfv child name(v).Pfv [3Sg said G],
 à= á t̄̄̄ gíèmààⁿ [wààdù máàⁿ],
 3Sg 3Sg name(v).Pfv G [time Rel],

A: ‘She came and named the child, she said Giema. At the time when she named it Giema, ...’

[t̄̄̄ ‘name (sb)’ as transitive verb]

(08:03) A [bá= á t̄̄̄ [náɲ-gù— sàà-nà]
 [Seq 3Sg let.Pfv [mother-Def— lie.down-Ppl]
 [à =á xèéɲ ʃū̀ē],
 [3Sg Ipfv breast suckle.Ipfv],

A: ‘The mother having lain down, it (=child) suckled.’

[can be emended to bí náɲ-gù t̄̄̄ sàà-nà ; xééⁿ]

(08:06) A [wáxádí kà] [[gúlù-ỳ]-náàⁿ ỳⁿ] [náɲ-gù gá
 [time a.certain] [[night-Loc]-middle Loc] [mother-Def Ipfv
 bàárāā [ā xìyóóⁿ— [ā xìyóóⁿ [in tē]],
 happen.Ipfv (hesitation)— [3Sg be.long.Stat [Logo Dat]],

A: ‘At times in the middle of the night, the mother was noticing that it (=child) was longer than she was.’

[< compound [gúlù-ỳ]-náā ‘middle of the night’; comparative, §12.1.2]

(08:09) A [wáxádí kà] ā =à túláá-yāā,
 [time a.certain] 3Sg Ipfv short-Inch.Ipfv,
 ā =à túláá-yàá biè [[iŋ xálámbéé-nà] níŋī],
 3Sg Ipfv short-Inch.Ipfv come.Ipfv [Refl child-Nom] inside],
 A: ‘At (other) times it was getting short (again), it was getting short, coming (back)
 into its childhood (shape).’
 [xálámbéé-nà, §4.2.3.3]

(08:12) A [ʃí gō-nààn-tòò-gú ròò] níŋì [náŋ-gù sígá],
 [since there.Def-middle-place-Def Foc] inside] [mother-Def doubt.Pfv],
 [àlà= á bè kũ-ŋũðⁿ [ŋōròò ý]]
 [until 3Sg come.Pfv whatchamacallit? [DemDef.Foc Loc]]
 A: ‘From that point on, between them (mother and child), the mother became
 suspicious. Eventually it (=child) came (to) whatchamacallit like that, ...’
 [sígā]

(08:15) A [ā bè jùðlì-mà],
 [3Sg come.Pfv bachelor-Abstr],
 [à ŋúó-ní jùðlì-mà-nà] [ŋōròò níŋìín] sà,
 [3Sg DemDef-Link bachelor-Abstr] [DemDef.Foc inside] Emph,
 A: ‘It (=child) came to (the age of) bachelorhood. That (age of) his bachelorhood,
 in that [focus], ...’
 [around 18 years of age; júólí-má and júólí-má-nà §4.2.3.1, §4.2.3.3; possessor
 combined with prenominal demonstrative; sá, §19.4.1.5]

(08:19) A *bon* [ā [in tètèŋè] lò]
 okay [3Sg [Refl front] put.in.Pfv]
 jáà [gètè bàdù-nà fiètè] túùŋ gá bō,
 Dia [place taboo-Ppl many] Past be.Loc here,
 A: ‘... okay, he (=bachelor) ventured (out). Dia (village), there used to be lots of
 tabooed places here.’
 [no-go places thought to be possessed by genies and devils]

(08:22) A [ā ròò] gáánà— [ā sēédàáni-gíé] [yà= [á jìní-giè]]
 [3Sg Foc] Pfv— [3Sg satan-Pl.&] [and [3Sg genie-Pl]]
 [[ā ròò] gáánà yé xàráⁿ],
 [[3Sg Foc] Pfv 3Pl expel.Pfv],
 A: ‘It was he [focus] who (drove out) its (=the place’s) devils and genies, it was he
 [focus] who drove them out.’
 [clause restarted after heavy conjoined object NP, §11.1.4; séédàáni ; xàráⁿ]

(08:25) A [ŋūðⁿ-yè xèré-nà-gù] ŋūðm bààrà,
 [DemDef-Pl expel-Ppl-Def] DemDef happen.Pfv,
 [kòmbó-gù [yā= à ʃòò] [yā= à yóò kòmbó-gù fùlè],
 [pond-Def [3Pl Ipfv go.Ipfv] [3Pl Ipfv go.Ipfv pond-Def fish(v).Pfv],
 A: ‘When those ones had been expelled, it happened that, the pond, they (=villagers)
 would go, they would go to the pond to fish.’
 [*xèré-nà participle of detransitivized xārāⁿ, §9.3.1.2; participial background resultative
 clause, §15.4.3; yóò variant of ʃòò ‘go.Ipfv’ in allegro speech*]

(08:29) S yā= à yóò kómbó-kòmbó fùlè
 3Pl Ipfv go.Ipfv K fish(v).Pfv
 A kómbó-kòmbó fùlè, [kómbó-kòmbò túù-yè] gá gō,
 K fish.Pfv, K owner-Pl] be.Loc there.Def,
 S (clarifying): ‘They would go to Kombo-kombo (pond) to fish.’
 A: Kombo-kombo to fish. The owners of Kombo-kombo are there.’
 [*‘owners’ here as regular possessum, not compound final*]

(08:33) A [ŋúó-ní kòmbó-gù] [ŋúó-ní fùlè-nà-gù]
 [DemDef-Link pond-Def] [DemDef-Link fish-Ppl-Def]
 [ŋōròò níŋī], [kádáá ká] ā wō é→,
 [DemDef.Foc inside], [time a.certain] 3Sg said hey!
 A: ‘(They) having done that fishing in that pond, then one day he said “hey!”’
 [*definite participial clause, §15.4.3; kádáá ká ‘one day’ (time setting), §6.3.2.1*]

(08:37) A ā wō [ŋ kómbò] gá [ŋ kómbó] nī→,
 3Sg said [1Sg pond] be.Cop [1Sg pond] it.is,
 yā= à yóò ŋūðⁿ fùlè [ŋ xòórèé] rà,
 3Pl Ipfv go.Ipfv DemDef fish(v).Pfv [1Sg behind] Q,
 A: ‘He said (=thought), “my pond is my pond. They (=villagers) go fish that (pond)
 behind my back?”’
 [*xòórèé ‘behind’ < xòórò yè, §8.2.7.4*]

(08:40) A [yè =é nà sò]
 [if 3Pl if.Pfv go.Pfv]
 [yè =é nà kómbó-fùlè-gù sóló-nì ʃièⁿ]
 [if 3Pl if.Pfv pond-fish.Vbl-Def descend-Caus.Pfv all]
 A: ‘If they go (and) if they allow pond-fishing, ...’
 [*ʃièⁿ ‘all’ marking the right edge of a complex conditional antecedent, §16.1.2, likewise
 @ 08:48 below*]

(08:43) A [[ā tòmò] gá [im bóónààn] lēē]
 [[3Sg too] Ipfv [Refl whip] pick.up.Ipfv]
 [à =á lòò [yé nāāⁿ],
 [3Sg Ipfv enter.Ipfv [3Pl between]],

A: ‘He for his part was picking up his leather whip (and) he was entering among them.’

[starting here there is minor microphone feedback for a minute or so, but the speech is still intelligible]

(08:48) A [yē nà sò [kómbò-g= í] ʃìèⁿ]
 [3Pl if.Pfv go.Pfv [pond-Def Loc] all]
 [[ā tòmò] gá bóónààn lèé]
 [[3Sg too] Ipfv whip pick.up.Pfv]
 [à =á lòò [yé nāāⁿ],
 [3Sg Ipfv enter.Ipfv [3Pl between]],

A: ‘If they (=people) went into the pond, he for his part would take his whip and enter among them.’

(08:51) A àywà ŋūòⁿ-yè ìŋ kū-ŋūòⁿ, é→,
 well DemDef-Pl Refl do.whatchamacallit?.Pfv, hey!,
 [ŋūòm bàárà],
 [DemDef happen.Pfv],
 [ā kù-ŋūòⁿ] [ŋūòm bàárà] [à gáána bè→],
 [3Sg whatchamacallit?], [DemDef happen.Pfv] [3Sg Pfv come.Pfv],

A: ‘Well, those (villagers) did whatchamacallit? Uh, it happened that it did whatchamacallit, it happened that he came.’

[‘whatchamacallit?’ as verb, §4.4.4]

(08:56) A [yē [yāālù máàn] là [à gá] gù
 [3Pl [woman Rel] give.Pfv [3Sg Dat] Def]
 [ŋūòŋ gá [[xàándáá-gíé ròò] máá-yààlù] nī],
 [DemDef be.Cop [[Kanta-Pl Foc] sister] it.is],

A: ‘The woman who(m) they had given to him, that (woman) was the sister of the Kanta’s.’

[xáándáá, Bozo clan name, spelled ‘Kanta’ in French; focalization of possessor, §13.1.6]

(09:00) A [sāw húnù] [séwè-gíé ròò] kùyé-yà sà,
 [now Top] [matter-Pl Foc] many-Inch.Pfv Emph,
 [nóòŋ-g= ì] yè bólò sà bólēē,
 [village-Def Loc] 3Pl Recip put.Pfv together,

A: ‘Now the problems had become many. In the village they got together.’

[bólēē ‘together’ < bólò yè, §18.4.3]

(09:03) A yē wō á! [yē wō bààⁿyìŋ-gù gáána kùyé-yà],
 3Pl said ah! [3Pl said damage-Def Pfv many-Inch.Pfv],
 [ŋūðn sáàⁿ]
 [DemDef time]
 xây dì féeà mánàá [kù níŋíⁿ] nà,
 1PlIn IpfvNeg solution look.for.Ipfv [Dem inside] Q,
 A: ‘They said, “ah!,” they said, “the damage has gotten big. So then shall we
 (inclusive) not look for a solution in this (matter)?’

(09:08) A àywà, [ŋūðn sáàn sà] yē wō
 well, [DemDef time Emph] 3Pl said
 [xây sò [yáálù-gù fáà]] [kí ná á nèxé-nèxè],
 [1PlIn.Hort go.Pfv [woman-Def by]] [1PlIn Sbjn 3Sg cajole-cajole.Pfv],
 A: ‘Well, “so then,” they said, “let’s go to the woman and (let’s) entreat her.” ’
[subjunctive clause with ná extending a hortative, §17.4.1.1, < néxē]

(09:11) A yē sò [yáálù-gù fáà] [yà= á sè [yáálù-gù tē]]
 3Pl go.Pfv [woman-Def by] [3Pl 3Sg say.Pfv [woman-Def Dat]]
 yē wō á!, yē wō [á= à xáy]
 3Pl said oh!, 3Pl said [2Sg 3Sg see.Pfv]
 A: ‘They went to the woman (and) they said it to the woman, they said “ah!” They
 said, “you-Sg have seen (it), ...” ’

(09:14) A [[bààⁿyìŋ-gù húnà=] á [cìè-nà]-nà [nóðŋ-g= ì] dè],
 [[damage-Def Top] be.Loc [be.heavy]-Ppl [village-Def Loc] Emph],
 [ŋūðn sáàⁿ] [á tòmò] ìn tỳ
 [DemDef time] [3Sg too] Refl let.Pfv
 A: ‘ “... (that) the damage is serious in the village. At that point, she for her part
 intervened (spoke up).’
[forms of cíéⁿ ‘heavy’, §4.5.1.2.2; clause-final emphatic dé, §19.4.1.5]

(09:17) A ā wō á!, è→, ā wō [ŋ sèwé-tùù],
 3Sg said ah!, eh!, 3Sg said [1Sg matter-owner],
 ā wōò→, [[án ténè] fáà] =á [fòⁿ máàⁿ] nī
 3Sg said, [[2Sg totem] by] be.Cop [thing Rel] it.is
 A: ‘She said, “ah! Eh,” she said, “my master (=husband),” she said, “the thing that
 your-Sg totem is, ...” ’
[‘totem’, here a tabooed activity; sèwé-tùù lit. “owner of matter(s),” hence ‘master, husband’; fáà can be omitted here]

(09:23) A [ténè-gù sè [ń tē]] [yá= á dì ɲũ̀ðⁿ nī]
 [totem-Def say.Pfv [1Sg Dat]] [if 3Sg not.be.Cop DemDef it.is]
 [kááá ká] má bì só là= [[àn ténè] níṅī],
 [time a.certain] Proh Fut go.Pfv enter.Pfv [[2Sg totem] inside],
 A: ‘ ‘Tell me the totem (=what the totem is). If it isn’t that (=anyway), lest you-Sg
 go into (=intrude on) your-Sg totem some day.’ ’
 [má bì without, §17.4.4]

(09:27) A [ā tòmò] ìn tòy [ɲòròò níṅī]
 [3Sg too] Refl let.Pfv [DemDef.Foc inside]
 [ā wō hàywà] ā wō [[ṅ húnù] ténè] dì bó̀lò nī
 [3Sg said well] 3Sg said [[1Sg Top] totem] not.be.Cop other it.is
 A: ‘She for her part intervened (spoke up) then. She said “well,” she said, “my totem
 is none other ...” ’

(09:30) A [[ṅ húnù] ténè] gà—
 [[1Sg Top] totem] is—
 yà= =á bì jì sà, [xááⁿyòⁿ níṅī],
 3Pl Ipfv Fut water pour.in.Pfv, [calabash inside],
 A: ‘ ‘My totem is— they will pour water into a calabash, ...” ’

(09:34) A [bí ʃààró ló yèè] [bá= á fìgì [m mā]], [wàlá
 [Seq broom put.in.Pfv therein] [Seq 3Sg strew.Pfv [1Sg against]], [or
 [xà̀lambèèⁿ-ṅ̀ùðⁿ m̀ỳd̀ṅ] gá bì kúúlùún lèè
 [child-Dim small] Ipfv Fut van pick.up.Pfv
 [bì ṅ fífà],
 [Seq 1Sg fan(v).Pfv],
 A: ‘ ‘... and pick up a broom and splash it (=water) lightly against me. Or else a
 little kid will take a winnowing van and fan me (with it).” ’
 [ʃààró ; diminutive, §5.1.6.2; kúúlùúnⁿ ‘slightly concave van for winnowing’; fífà]

(09:40) A [xá ná gáxítò] wàlà bílááṅkòrò gá bì tóló-xùdú lèè
 [2Pl Sbjn excuse] or uncirc.child Ipfv Fut clod.of.earth pick.up.Pfv
 [yà= á bì ṅ xídì],
 [3Pl Ipfv Fut 1Sg throw.at.Pfv],
 A: ‘Excuse me! “Or an uncircumcised child will pick up a chunk of earth (or a
 stone) and they (=children) will throw (it) at me.” ’
 [narrator says ‘excuse me!’, §19.5.7, since bílááṅkòrò is an indelicate term; tóló-xùdú,
 xídì]

(10:01) A ā bè [iŋ g̀̀b́í [dē, [sóm̄bó-túú r̄̀ò̄] n̄́]],
 3Sg come.Pfv [Refl flip.Pfv [for, [milk-owner Foc] it.is]],
 ā bè [l̄̀ [n̄́ò̄-g = ì]],
 3Sg come.Pfv [enter.Pfv [village-Def Loc]],

A: ‘... he came and transformed himself into a milk-seller. He came and entered the village.’

[g̀̀ó̄b́í ; sóm̄bó ‘milk’; n̄́ⁿ as apparent postposition in ‘transform’ construction, §8.1.2.3]

(10:05) A ā nà á yè [sipe k̄̀s̄əm],
 3Sg if.Pfv 3Sg say.Pfv [measure(v) milk]
 [máàⁿ ná sòm̄bò s̄̀áⁿ] [yē nà = à mēⁿ],
 [Rel if.Pfv milk buy.Pfv] [3Pl if.Pfv 3Sg drink.Pfv],

A: ‘When he said (in Fulfulde) “measure (=buy) milk!” (if there is) anyone who buys milk and they drink it, ...’

(10:08) A [kújú-nèè gà máàŋ k̀̀n̄́nú̀ù]
 [belly-disease Ipfv Rel catch.Ipfv]
 [ā = à kálēē],
 [3Sg Ipfv die.Ipfv],

A: ‘... (anyone) whom stomach disease catches (= afflicts), he/she dies.’

[kújú ‘belly’]

(10:10) A wàlà [túúŋ-gùlá gà máàŋ k̀̀n̄́nú̀ù]
 or [body-heat Ipfv Rel catch.Ipfv]
 [ŋ̀̀ú̄̀ŋ̀̀ gà ʃóò [lááxàrá ò̄]],
 [DemDef Ipfv go.Ipfv [Hereafter Loc]],

A: ‘Or (anyone) whom fever catches, that one goes to the Hereafter (i.e. dies).’

[< túúⁿ ‘body’, gùlá ‘heat’]

(10:12) A [ŋ̀̀ò̄n̄̀d̀̀ò̀ g̀̀l̄̀à] xónóm̀̀n̄̀d̀̀-̀̀g̀̀iè ìn t̄̀y [ŋ̀̀ò̄r̀̀d̀̀ò̀ n̄́ŋ̀̀í̄̄],
 [DemDef.Foc get.hot.Pfv] old.person-Pl Refl let.Pfv [DemDef.Foc inside],
 [yē w̄̀ á!] yē w̄̀ = [á = á k̀̀ xéén̄̀éè d̄̀],
 [3Pl said ah!] 3Pl said [2Sg Ipfv Dem see.Ipfv Emph],

A: ‘That [focus] got hot (=raged). The old people intervened (=spoke up) then. They said “ah!” They said, “you-Sg see that!”’

(10:16) A yē w̄̀ [[g̀̀iè̀m̄̀àà r̄̀ó̄] xà =] [á b̄̀],
 3Pl said [[G Foc] Prsntv] [3Sg come.Pfv],
 bá̀y yè xwáà b̄̀ [ŋ̀̀ò̄r̀̀d̀̀ò̀ n̄́ŋ̀̀í̄̄]
 (false start) 3Pl again come.Pfv [DemDef.Foc inside]

A: ‘They said, “there’s Giema! He has come!” They again came at that point, ...’

[name Giema cf. @ 07:54 above; Prsntv x̄̀ȳ]

(10:19) A [yé bè [bày [à fàà]],
 [3Pl come.Pfv [exit.Pfv [3Sg by]],
 [ṅúó-ní kùúlùùṅ-giè→], fàáró-giè→, yè gá à fífāā→,
 [DemDef-Link van-Pl], broom-Pl, 3Pl Ipfv 3Sg fan(v).Ipfv,
 A: ‘... (and) they came out (and went) to him. Those winnowing vans, (and) brooms, they fanned him.’
 [*‘vans’, ‘brooms’ and the following clause are expressed with incompleteness terminal prolongation*]

(10:24) S (inaudible)

A ɔ̃ⁿhó [ṅūɔ̃ⁿ-yè gā], [yà = á xàráⁿ] [yà = á xàráⁿ] [yà = á xàráⁿ],
 uhuh [DemDef-Pl Inst], [3Pl 3Sg expel.Pfv] (repetitions)

S: (inaudible)

A: ‘Uh-huh, with those (vans etc.). They were driving him out.’

[< xàráⁿ ; repeated perfective clauses with the effect of a progressive]

(10:27) A [àlì yē sò síṅè dígè-gù→, [kú níṅī], é→,
 [until 3Pl go.Pfv arrive.Pfv river-Def, [Dem inside], eh,
 féṅé, yè gá á yèè [xáándáá-yè dòrò],
 whatchamacallit?, 3Pl Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv [Kouanta-Pl haven],
 A: ‘Eventually they reached the river. In that, eh, whatchamacallit, they call it the Kouanta’s haven.’

[cf. àlì yè só ‘until they went’; féṅé < Bambara ; dóró, a haven where boats can be kept during storms]

(10:33) A [àlì yé sò síṅè gō] [ā wō hàywà],
 [until 3Pl go.Pfv arrive.Pfv there.Def][3Sg said well],
 [gō-nààn-tòò]-gà = ā wō [xā tāà bō],
 [right.there]-Def 3Sg said [2Pl.Imprt stop.Pfv here],
 A: ‘Eventually they reached there. He said, “well, on that spot,” he said, “you-Pl stop here!”

[gō-nààn-tòò, cf. @ 09:46 above; tāà ‘stop’ (reflexive, here imperative)]

(10:39) A [ṅūòṅ sáàⁿ] ā wō [xā tāà bō]
 [DemDef time] 3Sg said [2Pl stop.Pfv here]
 [[bōⁿ nōò] gá [ṅ ká-xòò] nī],
 [[here Foc] be.Cop [1Sg father-house] it.is],

A: ‘Then he said, “you-Pl stop! My paternal clan is here [focus].” ’

[i.e. this is where the other genies dwell; at this point in the recording someone else comes by and there is some conversation in the background; the narrator slows down and repeats some phrases to insure uptake by the listeners]

(10:42) A ā wō [xā t̄āā bō], ā wō [ŋū̀ðn sáàⁿ]
 3Sg said [2Pl stop.Pfv here], 3Sg said [DemDef time]
 [n̄ t̄òm̄ð] gáánà [ŋ kúnà],
 [1Sg too] Pfv [1Sg swear.Pfv],

A: ‘He said, “you-Pl stop here!” He said, “at this point, I for my part (hereby) swear an oath.”’

[kúnà (reflexive verb) ‘swear an oath’; perfective clause with gáánà in performative function, §10.2.1.1]

(10:46) A ā wō [n̄ t̄òm̄ð] gáánà [ŋ kúnà],
 3Sg said [1Sg too] Pfv [1Sg swear.Pfv],
 [yé [xáándáà máàŋ ʃìèⁿ] ná [xáándáá t̄òó] sè bō,
 [if [K Rel all] if.Pfv [K name] say.Pfv here],

A: ‘He said, “I for my part (hereby) swear an oath. If any Kanta says the name Kanta here, ...”’

(10:50) A àywà yá= [à túù] t̄ùm bō, [ŋõr̄òð làà=]
 well (wish) [3Sg owner] disappear.Pfv here, [DemDef Purp]
 [àlí ñién-sààntè] [ŋúó-ní ðìgè-gú r̄òð] xáándáā—
 [until tomorrow] [DemDef-Link river-Def Foc] Kanta—

A: ‘ “Well, may the fellow disappear from here!” Because of that, from the next day on, Kanta—’

[túⁿ ‘disappear’; yé here begins a wish, §10.4.3.1; ā tū̀ referring to a previously introduced generic individual, §5.1.7]

(10:53) A yē gà á yèè
 3Pl Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv
 [[xáándáá t̄òó] ðì ìn sèé [[ðìgè máàŋ-g=] ì] gù],
 [[K name] IpfvNeg Refl say.Ipfv [[river Rel-Def] Loc] Def],

A: ‘They say, the river in which the name of Kanta is not (=cannot be) said, ...’

[relativization on postpositional complement, §14.2.4; final gù in relative clause (§14.1.2) with additional definite suffix on máàⁿ]

(10:55) A ŋõ-nà= =à [ŋúó-ní ðìgè-gù] nī,
 DemDef.Foc be.Cop [DemDef-Link river-Def] it.is,
 àywà [ŋū̀ðn sáàⁿ], [ā hū̀nù] bì—, bon jáà bè,
 well [DemDef time], [3Sg Top] Seq—, okay Dia come.Pfv,

A: ‘... that one [focus] is that (same) river. Well, then, he came—. Okay, Dia (village) came.’

[the end of this segment and the next segment are rather broken as the narrator hesitates]

(11:01) A jáà bè, jáà bè fáy [dē—]
 Di come.Pfv, Dia come.Pfv become.Pfv [for—]
 kú gá jáà— [fáy-m-béénàà sìndì] nī,
 Dem be.Cop Dia— [sit.Vbl-Link-manner begin.VblN] it.is,
 A: ‘Dia came. Dia became—. This is the beginning of the manner of settling of
 Dia.’

[‘become’ construction, ; §11.2.4.2; síndì]

(11:06) S sínè
 for.now
 A ʒⁿhðⁿ, sínè,
 uh.huh, for.now,
 S: ‘For now.’
 A: ‘Uh-huh. For now.’
 [i.e. there is more coming]

(11:07) A mais [à xáy], ā jīēmù [[júóŋð máàn] xúmà] gù,
 but [3Sg Prsntv], 3Sg speak.Pfv [[marriage Rel] on] Def,
 è→, júóŋð fànààⁿ,
 eh, marriage firstly,
 A: ‘But look here, marriage on (=about) which he spoke, eh, marriage (customs) in
 the old days, ...’

[the ‘he’ may perhaps be the assistant who planned the recording]

(11:14) A júóŋð [yá= àŋ gá bì— bày [yáálù fáà] jáà
 marriage [if 2Sg Ipfv Fut— exit.Pfv [woman by] Dia
 [[ŋúó-ní wàxàdí-g=] ì],
 [[DemDef-Link time-Def] Loc]
 A: ‘Marriage. If you-Sg were going to go out with (=court) a woman in Dia in those
 days, ...’

(11:18) A [ŋ xáy] [[wáxadí máàn] gá] dè, [ŋūðm bàárà]
 [1Sg Prsntv] [[time Rel] Dat] Emph, [DemDef happen.Pfv]
 [wárí dī gō] [wâr jíémù] dī gō]
 [money not.be.Loc there.Def] [money talk(n)] not.be.Loc there.Def]
 A: ‘Mind you (in) the time (=era) I here am (talking) about, it happened that money
 was not (involved) there, discussion (=negotiation) of money was not (involved)
 there.’

[wárí ‘money’]

(11:22) A ḡkàà ṅièn-sààntè [ṅúó-ní tòò kóòṅ-gù róò]
 but tomorrow [DemDef-Link name one-Def Foc]
 gà [júóṅò xúmà],
 be.Loc [marriage on],

A: 'But (even) the next day, that same name [focus] was on marriage.'

[i.e. there was a uniform marriage custom for everybody]

(11:25) A *parce que* fánááṅ júóṅò gá ìⁿ wálèè
 because firstly marriage Ipfv Refl do.Ipfv
 [kóó-júón tám-éndéén lámà tán],
 [cowry-child twenty only only],

A: 'Because in the old days a marriage was done (for) only twenty cowries.'

[cowrie shells were used as currency; lámà and tán, §19.3.2.3-4]

(11:29) A [ṅūòṁ bààrà] [yá= àṅ gá gō] [dáláy tám-ndèèⁿ],
 [DemDef happen.Pfv] [if 2Sg be.Loc there.Def] [5.FCFA twenty],
 [ā à yóò jíémà [[dáláy tám-ndèèⁿ] mā]]
 [3Sg Ipfv go.Ipfv match.Pfv [[5.FCFA twenty] against]]

A: 'It happened that if you-Sg were there, (it was) one hundred francs CFA. It was equivalent to one hundred francs CFA (now).'

[dáláy 'currency unit (=5 francs CFA)'; yóò variant of jóò 'go.Ipfv'; jíémà 'coincide (with), match', §10.1.3.3.3]

(11:33) A ṅōnòò túùṅ gà júóṅó-nàⁿfòrò nṅṅ jáà bō,
 DemDef.Foc Past be.Cop marriage-wealth it.is Dia here,
 á= à fáàmúⁿ nà,
 2Sg 3Sg understand.Pfv Q,

A: 'That [focus] was the marriage wealth (=cost) here in Dia. Did you-Sg understand it?'

[brideprice paid by the bridegroom to the family of the bride]

(11:36) A *bon* [jáà húnù] kóónóò júóṅò-júóṅò
 okay [Dia Top] remain.Ipfv Iter-marry.Ipfv
 [ṅúó-ní xàbàrì-yà máàⁿ] níṅìíṅ] gù dè,
 [DemDef-Link news Rel] inside] Def Emph,

A: 'Okay, that situation in which Dia kept (doing) marriages.'

[iteration of júóṅò 'marry.Ipfv' (§9.6.2); xábàrì-yà]

(11:41) A alá á fūō, bí yé tòy [ɲōròò níjī],
 God 3Sg want.Pfv, Seq 3Pl let.Pfv [DemDef.Foc inside],
 [xóórò fáà rōò] yē wàrí-gù jààsí-nì,
 [back by Foc] 3Pl money-Def feeble-Caus.Pfv,
 A: ‘God chose it, to leave them in that situation. It was afterwards [focus] that they
 weakened (=depreciated) the money.’
[focalization of lexicalized PP, §13.1.6.2]

(11:46) A [júóṅó-nàⁿfòrò máàⁿ]— yē wàrí-gù jààsí-nì
 [marriage-wealth Rel]— 3Pl money-Def feeble-Caus.Pfv
 [júóṅò ṅà] =á [fòṅ xòlò róò] nī,
 [marriage QTop] be.Cop [thing big Foc] it.is,
 A: ‘The marriage wealth that—, they weakened the money. What a big thing [focus]
 marriage is!’
[QTop as mirative, §19.1.2]

(11:51) A [yē tòmò] [ɲúó-ní jùòṅò-nàⁿfòrò-gù],
 [3Pl too] [DemDef-Link marriage-wealth-Def],
 yā = à yáà [dè [júóṅó-bááⁿyíⁿ]-nàⁿfòrò nī],
 3Pl 3Sg put.Pfv [for [marriage-ruin.VblN]-wealth it.is],
 A: ‘They for their part (changed) that marriage wealth. They transformed it into
 marriage-ruin wealth.’
*[‘transform’ construction, §11.2.4.2; tripartite compound, §5.1.4.3, cf. bipartite
 júóṅó-bààⁿyí]*

(11:54) S sùbáánà-llàày
 glory.to.God (< Arabic)
 A ðⁿhóⁿ, yá = àⁿ ná à kóròsí,
 uh-huh, if 2Sg if.Pfv 3Sg watch.over.Pfv,
 S: ‘Glory to God!’
 A: ‘Uh-huh! If you-Sg watch over (=consider) it, ...’

(11:57) A yá = àṅ gá bì yáálù fídì,
 if 2Sg Ipfv Fut woman dump.Pfv,
 yē gà á yèè [áⁿ [máà róò]]—
 3Sg Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv [2Sg [what? Foc]]—
 A: ‘... if you-Sg are going to divorce a woman, they say (=ask), “what have
 you-Sg —” ’

(11:59) A yē gà á yèè [áⁿ [máà ród] là [à gā]],
 3Sg Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv [2Sg [what? Foc] give.Pfv [3Sg Dat],
 yē gà á yēē, [ā [àŋ jùdŋó-kòd] là [àŋ gá] rà,
 3Sg Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv, [3Sg [2Sg marriage-cowry] give.Pfv [2Sg Dat] Q,
 A: ‘They say (=ask), “what have you-Sg given to her?” They say (to the woman),
 “did he give you-Sg your marriage cowries (=divorce settlement)?” ’
*[the divorce settlement paid to the woman, essentially a return of the brideprice at
 marriage, was formerly in cowries]*

(12:01) S júŋó-kòd là [àŋ gā]
 marriage-cowry give.Pfv [2Sg Dat]
 A fánááⁿ ŋōròdò twⁿá = =à júŋó-nàⁿfòrò nī
 firstly DemDef Past be.Cop marriage-wealth it.is
 S (repeating): ‘Gave you the marriage cowries.’
 A: ‘In the old days that used to be marriage wealth.’
[< túŋ gà]

(12:04) A *parce que* yá = àⁿ nà— ā jādè,
 because if 2Sg if.Pfv 3Sg calculate.Pfv,
parce que kós-júó— [kós-júón síláámbé-kìèrmà]
 because (hesitation)— [cowry-child Muslim-hundred]
 A: ‘Because if you-Sg have calculated it, one Muslim-hundred cowries, ...’
*[jádè ; the ‘Muslim hundred’ (100) is distinct from the so-called bámbará-kìèrmà
 ‘Bambara hundred’ (80)]*

(12:09) A [à = á fìémàà [ŋéénù mā]
 [3Sg Ipfv coincide.Ipfv [how.much? against]
 S síláámbé-kìèrmà
 Muslim-hundred
 A: ‘It corresponds to (=is worth) how much (in cash)?
 S: ‘(One) Muslim-hundred (=500 FCFA).’
[fìémà, §10.1.3.3; 500 FCFA cash is the current amount of a divorce settlement]

(12:12) A háⁿ, ŋūdn dì— [ŋūdn dì síláámbé-kìèrmà níⁿ nà],
 huh?, (hesitation) [DemDef not.be.Cop Muslim-hundred it.is Q],
 [yá = à = = á bì júŋò bàà]
 [if 2Sg Ipfv Fut marriage remove.Pfv]
 A: ‘Huh? Isn’t that one Muslim-hundred (=500 FCFA)? If you-Sg are going to
 remove the marriage (=divorce), ...’
[< yé àŋ gá bì]

(12:15) A [áṅ gá á bàà [[máà ród] gā]]
 [2Sg Ipfv 3Sg remove.Pfv [[what? Foc] Inst]]
 [áṅ gá á bàà [síláámbé-kìèrmà ród] gā]],
 [2Sg Ipfv 3Sg remove.Pfv [Muslim-hundred Foc Inst]],

A: ‘... you-Sg remove it with what [focus]?’

S: ‘You-Sg remove it with one Muslim-hundred (=500 FCFA).’

(12:16) A [síláámbé-kìèrmà ród] gá ìn láà [àṅ gā]],
 [Muslim-hundred Foc] Ipfv Refl give.Ipfv [2Sg Dat]],
 [yá= á dì ṅūḁⁿ nī] fàràⁿ,
 [if 3Sg not.be.Cop DemDef it.is] firstly,

A: ‘It’s one Muslim-hundred (=500 FCFA) that is given to you-Sg (=the wife). By contrast, in the old days, ...’

(12:20) A [yá= àⁿ nà á sà bólēē]
 [if 2Sg if.Pfv 3Sg put.Pfv together]
 [kód-júón síláámbé-kìèrmà] [yá= àⁿ nà á sà bólēē]
 [cowry-child Muslim-hundred] [if 2Sg if.Pfv 3Sg put.Pfv together]

A: ‘If you-Sg put it (all) together, one Muslim-hundred cowries. If you-Sg put it (all) together, ...’

(12:22) A [ā twáⁿ = á]ìémāā, [[tám-éndééⁿ nód] mā],
 [3Sg Past Ipfv coincide.Ipfv, [[twenty Foc] against],
 [ṅūḁⁿ sáàⁿ] yē bè [ṅōnòḁ tīⁿ],
 [DemDef time] 3Pl come.Pfv [DemDef.Foc] under],

A: ‘It was worth twenty (currency units, i.e. 100 francs). Then they brought that.’

[< ā tūṅ gá]ìémà ; *refers here to colonial-era and early independence-era “franc”;*
conveyance construction, §11.1.1.4]

(12:27) A sāgù, yā= à jóò [[gúl tàṁ-èndèèn] tīⁿ],
 now, 3Pl Ipfv go.Ipfv [[thousand twenty] under],
 ā tūṅ gá [gǔl tàⁿ nòḁ] nī,
 3Sg Past be.Cop [thousand ten Foc] it.is,
 wá-rí-gù jáásí-yà,
 money-Def feeble-Inch.Pfv,

A: ‘Nowadays, they go with (=deliver) twenty thousand (currency units). It used to be ten thousand (units). Money has weakened.’

[< gúlū ; *i.e. nowadays 100,000 FCFA, formerly 50,000 FCFA*]

(12:32) A [yē bà= [á tīⁿ] [[gǔl tàm-èndèⁿ] níjī], ĩkàà
 [3Pl come.fv [3Sg under] [[thousand twenty] inside], but
 [bá= á sè] sāw [[fɔⁿ máàŋ] kòrà= [à mā]]
 [Seq 3Sg say.Pfv] now [[thing Rel] be.added.Pfv [3Sg against]]
 A: ‘They brought it (back) to twenty thousand (currency units). But, to say now,
 what has been added to it (=price), ...’
 [< bí á sè ; kórí]

(12:36) A [ñ dí [fɔⁿ húnù] xábàrí yēē],
 [1Sg IpfvNeg [thing Top] be.aware.of.Ipfv therein],
 [yá= á dì ŋūⁿ nī] fànáⁿ
 [if 3Sg not.be.Cop DemDef it.is] firstly
 A: ‘I am not aware of anything in (=about) that. If it isn’t that (anyway), in the old
 days, ...’;
 [*topicalized postpositional complement, §19.1.1; xábàrí*]

(12:37) A [yá= àŋ gá bì júŋò wàlè],
 [if 2Sg Ipfv Fut marriage do.Pfv],
 ŋōnòò túⁿ= à fòò,
 DemDef.Foc Past Ipfv go.Ipfv,
 A: ‘... if you-Sg were going to do a marriage, that (amount) is what used to go (=be
 taken).’
 [< túⁿ]

(12:40) A [fòò ŋūòm bì sò]—
 [go.Ipfv DemDef Fut go.Pfv]—
 [yé [xàlù ñà] ná bày [yáálù fáà],
 [if [man QTop] if.Pfv exit.Pfv [woman by],
 A: ‘Before that (money) goes (=is taken there)—. If a man goes out with (=courts)
 a woman, ...’
 [*fòò in ‘before’ clause, §17.2.5.3*]

(12:42) A ā nà á—, xààyì [[ĭn làmbèè] gā],
 3Sg if.Pfv 3Sg show.Pfv [[Refl kin] Dat],
 [yē gà [wáliyá-kìidì ród] jí-nī],
 [3Pl Ipfv [griot Foc] get.up-Caus.Ipfv],
 A: ‘... when he has shown her to his kin, they engage a griot intermediary [focus].’
 [*wáliyá-kìidì ‘a type of griot who helps with marital negotiations and later with other
 marital problems*]

- (12:46) A wálíyá-kìidí-gà= =à ʃòò, [ā =à ʃòò [[à jíémù] níηī],
 griot-Def Ipfv go.Ipfv, [3Sg Ipfv go.Ipfv [[3Sg talk(n)] inside],
 [yá à ná [à jíémù] wàlè [ηūòñ sààⁿ],
 [if 3Sg if.Pfv [3Sg talk(n)] do.Pfv [DemDef time],
 A: ‘The griot intermediary goes. He goes into the discussion of that. When he has
 done the discussion of that, then, ...’

- (12:51) A [kóó-júón síláámbe-kìèrmà-gù wáy bì sô],
 [cowry-child Muslim-hundred-Def before Fut go.Pfv],
 [wáy bì júóηò wàlè],
 [before Fut marriage do.Pfv],
 A: ‘... before the Muslim-hundred cowries go (=are paid), before doing the
 marriage.’
 [wáy bì ‘before’, §17.2.5.1]

- (12:55) S jààtí-jààtí
 exactly
 A ʔⁿhóⁿ, yà= á bàárà [[tèlè bòlò máàη] gá gō]
 uh.huh, if 3Sg happen.Pfv [[question other Rel] be.Loc there.Def]
 S: ‘Exactly.’
 A: ‘Uh-huh. If it happens that there is whatever other question there...’
 [short for yá= ā ná bàárà with ná/nà ‘if.Pfv’]

- (13:00) S ah d’accord, [sāw húnù] ā fāàmú
 all right, [now Top] 3Sg be.understood.Pfv
 S: ‘All right, now it has been understood.’

recorded in Dia, 2022

file 180103_0036

duration 07:14

transcribable portion 00:19 - 07:14

(mike feedback, occasionally bad, at 01:22-29, 01:55-02:25, 03:02-44, 06:33-38)

speakers and their abbreviations in order of appearance:

Seni Yalouta (S), male, interviewer

Alfa Boubacar Karabenta (A), male, main narrator

(00:21) S yá= àn túùⁿ ná bày [á tìⁿ] [ʃwààⁿ ỹⁿ],
if 2Sg Past if.Pfv exit.Pfv [3Sg under] [market Loc],
yá= àⁿ nà á là [[máàŋ ʃìèŋ] gā],
if 2Sg if.Pfv 3Sg give.Pfv [[Rel all] Dat],

S: ‘When you-Sg used to transport it (=merchandise) out to the (weekly) market, whoever you might have given it to, ...’

[< tìⁿ in conveyance construction, §11.1.1.4]

(00:25) S [áj gwá= á sà= [à tē]]
[2Sg Fut 3Sg say.Pfv [3Sg Dat]]
àywà [yá= àⁿ nà [í fùó-gù] tòrò]
well [if 2Sg if.Pfv [1Sg possession-Def] sell.Pfv]

S: ‘... you-Sg will say to him/her, “well, if you-Sg sell my stuff, ...” ’

[here the speaker is shifting to the present day; áŋ gú ; sé]

(00:27) S [dáláy ŋ-kóóⁿ] yá= à ná à kíèni,
[currency.unit Link-one] if 3Sg if.Pfv 3Sg lack.from.Pfv,
xáy gù sò [bólò tìⁿ] [sèmbèⁿ-yè fāⁿ],
1PlIn Fut go.Pfv [Recip under] [power-Pl chez],

S: ‘ “if (even) one cent is missing from it, we (inclusive) will take each other to the authorities’ place.’

[dáláy, the smallest currency unit; kíèni (transitive) ’; gù sō]

(00:31) S [ŋūòŋ ʃìèŋ] gà [wáy róò] nī, íkàà fánáám bààrà,
[DemDef all] be.Cop [today Foc] it.is, but firstly happen.Pfv,
[mó-ʃìì múròò] túùn dì [ŋūòⁿ mā],
[person-any need(n)] Past not.be.Loc [DemDef against],

S: ‘All that is (what happens) today [focus]. In the past it happened that nobody used to need that.’

[< mó-ʃìì fused from múò ʃìì ‘any person’]

(00:35) S [àlá= àn túù ná bè [kìèrmà ród] là [à gā]]
 [even 2Sg Past if.Pfv come.Pfv [hundred Foc] give.Pfv [3Sg Dat]]
 [[xúlú fàxáá-ná] jód]
 [[skiff be.full-Ppl] fish]

S: ‘Even if you-Sg had come and given him a hundred (currency units) [focus]. A boatful of fish, ...’

[past-time conditional antecedent, same form as counterfactual]

(00:37) S [yá= àⁿ nà á sè [[kú ród] tòdré yēē]],
 [if 2Sg if.Pfv 3Sg say.Pfv [[Dem Foc] be.sold.Pfv therein]],
 ā tūùⁿ ḡá [iⁿ fùd] kámāā,
 3Sg Past Ipfv [Refl possession] take.away.Ipfv,

S: ‘..., if you-Sg said that that (=boatload of fish) is what was sold therein, he (=owner) used to recover what was his.’

[i.e. the owner and the reseller trusted each other; tóóró ‘sell’, antipassive tóóré, §9.3.1.1]

(00:40) S ḡkàà wáy ḡūdn òì gō,
 but today DemDef not.be.Loc there.Def,
 mais sāv yà= á bààrà
 but now if 3Pl happen.Pfv

S: ‘But today that does not exist. But now, if it happens that ...’

(00:42) S [áj gá màà [fóⁿ máàⁿ] séè]
 [2Sg Ipfv be.able.Ipfv [thing Rel] say.Ipfv]
 [xáy té] [[ḡūdn tēmè] níḡī], [[xáy xòd] níḡī],
 [1PlIn Dat] [DemDef too] inside], [[1PlIn language] inside],

S: ‘... (there is) something that you-Sg can tell us in (=about) that, in our language.’

(00:46) A bon [áj xáy] [[ḡūdnⁿ máàn] gá] gù, fúlé,
 okay [1PlIn Prstv] [[DemDef Rel] Dat] Def, fish(v).VblN,
 [à xáy] [fóⁿ máàn] séé gù,
 [3Sg Prsntv] [thing Rel] say.Ipfv Def,

A: ‘Okay, that which you-Sg here are getting at (=referring to). Fishing. The thing that he (there) is saying, ...’

[gā construction, §8.1.1.2.2; may refer to a discussion prior to the recording]

(00:53) A [fúlé [yé ḡūdn]] òì [[íèḡ kódⁿ] fáà],
 [fish(v).VblN.& [and DemDef] not.be.Loc [[road one] by],
 parce que yá àⁿ ná [à jádè] kùⁿ,
 because if 2Sg if.Pfv [3Sg calculation] catch.Pfv,

A: ‘Fishing and that (=what he said) are not on the same path. Because, if you-Sg do its calculation (=think about it),’

(00:57) A [fúlé gá [fùlè-kàlìtè làmà-làmàⁿ nòðⁿ] nī,
 [fish(v).VblN be.Cop [fish(v).VblN-kind several Foc] it.is,
 [ŋūðn sáàⁿ] yá àⁿ ná à jádè kùⁿ,
 [DemDef time] if 2Sg if.Pfv 3Sg calculation catch.Pfv,
 A: ‘Fishing is (really) various kinds of fishing (method). So then, if you count them
 up, ...’
 [lámá-lámá, §6.4.2.4; jādē]

(01:01) A [sónómó→ tēé] gà gō, xúúnú→ gà gō,
 [Clarias fishtrap] be.Loc there.Def, dike be.Loc there.Def,
 á= à fáàmúⁿ ná,
 2Sg 3Sg understand.Pfv Q,
 A: ‘... there’s the trap of (=for) *Clarias* catfish. There’s the dike-fishtrap. Did you-
 Sg understand?’
 [sónómò *air-breathing catfish sp.*, *Clarias spp.*; tēē traps are left overnight in fairly
 shallow water; xúúnú ‘fishtrap connected to large dikes in the water’]

(01:07) A [yé nòð gà kírēē]
 [if fish Ipfv be.gotten.Ipfv]
 [xálu dí máàⁿ wàléè fìèw]
 [man IpfvNeg Rel do.Ipfv at.all]
 A: ‘If fish are gotten (in abundance), what a man doesn’t do at all (by himself), ...’

(01:09) A [xálu [yé yáálù]] [[yē rōð] gà á wàléè bólēē],
 [man.& [and woman] [[3Pl Foc] Ipfv 3Sg do.Ipfv together],
parce que yá= à ná bày [jìi níjìíⁿ] sāw,
 because if 3Sg if.Pfv exit.Pfv [water inside] now,
 A: ‘... a man and a woman, they [focus] do it together. Because when he comes
 (back) from the water, ...’

(01:13) A [wáádú-yè gá biè [wáádú-yé nāāⁿ]],
 [time-Pl Ipfv come.Ipfv [time-Pl between]]
 [ŋ yóròð] à xáy, [múð yóròð] xúúnú—
 [1Sg self] 3Sg see.Pfv, [1PlEx self] dike—
 A: ‘... times (=days) will come among the times, I myself have seen it. Our own
 dike-fishtrap—.’
 [partitive function of nāāⁿ ‘between/among’, §8.2.6; yórōð, §18.2]

(01:18) A [xúúnú máàŋ] gá [[ŋ yóròó] tē]
 [dike Rel] be.Loc [[1Sg self] Dat]
 [[bíímá làmìnìŋ-gù] níŋī],
 [[B proximity-Def inside] ,

A: ‘The dike-fishtrap that belongs to me in the vicinity of Bima (village).’
 [bíímā (village); lámíníⁿ ‘proximity’ < Bambara]

(01:20) A ā =à síŋèè [[xùùnù [fòŋ jéni]] níŋī],
 3Sg Ipfv arrive.Ipfv [[dike [thing seven]] inside],
 ē→ [sāw húnù] kí má só [gèrè lààⁿ]
 eh [now Top] 1PlIn Proh go [place distant]

A: ‘It (=number) arrives at (=adds up to) seven dike-fishtraps. Now let’s (inclusive) not go (=digress) too far.’

[fɔ̃ⁿ ‘thing’ as classifier in numeral phrases, §6.4.1.5; hortative negative, §10.4.2.2]

(01:25) A *deux mille quatre* [kì tīⁿ], *deux mille quatre* [kì tīⁿ]
 2004 (year) [1PlIn under], 2004 (year) [1PlIn under],
 kúù pèndèèn lámà tàn,
 day two only only

A: ‘(year) 2004 near us (=just recently), 2004 near us. In just two days, ...’

[tīⁿ ‘under; next to’, §8.2.7.5.1; kúù]

(01:30) A múð túùŋ gà [[bárkòò pèndèèŋ] cìè] bāā,
 1PlEx Past Ipfv [[gas.drum two] oil] remove.Ipfv,
 múð túùŋ gà [[bárkòò, pèndèèŋ] léé-ŋ-cìè] bāā,
 1PlEx Past Ipfv [[gas.drum, two] *Brycinus*-Link-oil] remove.Ipfv,

A: ‘... we (exclusive) used to extract two barrel-fulls of oil, we (exclusive) used to extract two barrel-fulls of *Brycinus* (fish) oil.’

[former meter-high metal gas drums (bárkòò, French barique), which can be rolled, are re-used as barrel-sized containers, or cut up; oil from the sardine-like fish *Brycinus leuciscus* (léè) is extracted and commercialized; compounds of cíé ‘oil’, §5.1.3.2.3]

(01:34) S léé-ŋ-cìè bāā
Brycinus-Link-oil remove.Ipfv

A á= à fáàmúⁿ ná,
 2Sg 3Sg understand.Pfv Q,

S (overlapping): ‘... *Brycinus* (fish) oil.’

A: ‘Did you-Sg understand it?’

(01:37) A *bon* *xá* =*á* *bàý* [*ʃíjɪn* *ʃwàá*],
 okay 2Pl Ipfv exit.Ipfv [since morning],
yá= *àⁿ* *nà* *só* [*fùlè-n-tó-g=* *ì*],
 if 2Sg if.Pfv go.Pfv [fish.VblN-Link-place.of-Def Loc],
 A: ‘Okay, you-Pl (will) go out right away in the morning. When you-Sg go to the
 fishing place, ...’
 [*bāy* ; *ʃíⁿ* ‘since’, §8.2.8.3.1; *ʃwáá* ; compound with -*tō* ‘place of’, §5.1.4.3; “go to the
 fishing area” means ‘go fishing’]

(01:41) A *à* =*á* *bàáràà* [*á=* =*á* *bìè—* *màá* *bìè*]
 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv [2Sg Ipfv (error)— be.able.Ipfv come.Ipfv]
 [[[*búólò jíénì*] *ɲóó*] *wàlá* [[*xùlù-ɲàà* *ɲ-kóòɲ*] *sónómò*]] *tīⁿ*,
 [[[sack seven] fish.&] or [[skiff-eye Link-one] *Clarias*]] under,
 A: ‘... it (may) happen that you-Sg come—, can bring (back) seven sacks of fish,
 or one boatful of *Clarias* catfish.’
 [*conveyance construction with ‘under’, §11.1.1.4; ‘eye’ as a countable unit for
 measured volumes, §6.4.1.5*]

(01:46) A *yé* *xà* *ná* *bè*,
 if 2Pl if.Pfv come.Pfv,
 [*yáálù-giè* *ròò*] *gà* [*á* *ʃièn*] *kúòméè*,
 [woman-Pl Foc] Ipfv [3Sg all] fold.fish.Ipfv,
 A: ‘When you-Pl come (back, to the village), it’s the women [focus] who fold it
 (=catfish) all.’
 [*Each Clarias catfish is folded once for smoking, so the head is against the tail*]

(01:49) A *àywà* [*yē* *ròò*] *gá* *tùù* *kélé-nî*,
 well [3Pl Foc] Ipfv fire ignite-Caus.Ipfv,
 [*yé* *ròò*] *gà* [*á* *ʃièn*] *dìbî*,
 [3Pl Foc] Ipfv [3Sg all] smoke.fish.Ipfv,
 A: ‘Well, it’s they (women) [focus] who light the fire. It’s they [focus] who smoke
 it (=catfish) all.’
 [*fish, especially Clarias, are placed while still fresh on a grill for slow smoking*]

(01:54) A *yè* =*é* *nà* *á* *dìbì*.
 if 3Pl if.Pfv 3Sg smoke.fish.Pfv,
 [*áⁿ* *nóò*] *gá* *bì* *sìrèèɲ* [*jì* *níjī*]
 [2Sg Foc] Ipfv Fut spend.day.Pfv [water inside]
 A: ‘When they (=women) have smoked it, it’s you-Sg (=the man) [focus] who will
 spend the day in the water.’

(01:56) A [áⁿ ná àŋ kírè]
 [2Sg if.Pfv 2Sg be.finished.Pfv]
 áⁿ wō [ŋ gá bì gúlù xèèⁿ]
 2Sg said [1Sg Ipfv Fut night spend.night.Pfv]
 A: ‘When you-Sg have finished, you (will) say, “I will spend the night ...”’
 [kírè ‘be finished’ (reflexive); ‘spend day/night’ plus imperfective clause, §15.1.1.7]

(01:58) A [ŋ gá sòndòmó kùdémèè] [ŋ gá sòndòmó dībû],
 [1Sg Ipfv *Clarias* fold.fish.Ipfv] [1Sg Ipfv *Clarias* smoke.fish.Ipfv],
 [áj gá à tódò [nién-sàantè húnù]
 [2Sg Ipfv 3Sg know.Ipfv [tomorrow Top]
 A: ‘... folding catfish (and) smoking catfish.’ You-Sg know that, tomorrow, ...’
 [< sónómò kùdémèè, §3.6.3.5.6]

(02:02) A án dí màà fòò xàyn-tó,
 2Sg IpfvNeg be.able.Ipfv go.Ipfv work.VblN-place.of,
bon [ŋròò làà] [xálú [yè yáálù]],
 okay [DemDef Purp] [man.& [and woman]],
 A: ‘... you-Sg won’t be able to go to the workplace. Okay, for that reason, a man
 and a woman, ...’
 [lāā]

(02:06) A [yē ròò] gá fùlè-gù wàléè bólēē
 [3Pl Foc] Ipfv fish(v).VblN-Def do.Ipfv together
 [ŋúáⁿ = =a sónómò nī],
 [DemDef be.Cop *Clarias* it.is],
 A: ‘It’s they [focus] who do the fishing together. That’s (the info for) *Clarias*
 catfish.’

(02:09) A *bon* yé kì nà sò
 okay if 1PlIn if.Pfv go.Pfv
 [[[léè tìŋááⁿ] fùlè] níŋī],
 [[[*Brycinus* possession] fish.VblN] inside],
 A: ‘Okay, if we move on to the fishing of *Brycinus*,’
 [léè, a small sardine-like fish, *Brycinus leuciscus*, that is caught en masse around
 November-December; its oil is pressed and commercialized for cooking]

(02:11) A [ŋūðn sààn] léè, yè á— xà ná sùrèèⁿ,
 [DemDef time] *Brycinus*, if (error)— 2Pl if.Pfv spend.day.Pfv,
 xá gá à— [ʃìⁿ fàjìrì]
 2Pl Ipfv 3Sg— [since dawn]
 A: ‘Then *Brycinus* fish. When you-Pl have spent the day, you-Pl—. Since dawn.’
 [fàjìrì ‘pre-dawn prayer’]

(02:15) A yē gá á sēē, àlááhù?àkbàt [à = á bàárāā]
 3Pl Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv, God.is.great [3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv]
 [áj gá]óò] [àn táà [xùùnù níjī]],
 [2Pl Ipfv go.Ipfv] [2Sg stop.Pfv [dike inside]],
 A: ‘They say (in pre-dawn prayer), “God is great.” It happens that you-Sg go and stop at the dike.’
[i.e. one heads to the fishing spot early in the morning right after dawn prayer; tàà ‘stop’ (reflexive) preceded by áⁿ as reflexive object]

(02:18) A [ŋūðn sààn] léè, [yéⁿ-núðŋ gá bày lámà]
 [DemDef time] *Brycinus*, [light-Dimin Ipfv exit.Ipfv only]
 [léè gá bày [xúúnú-g = ì],
 [*Brycinus* Ipfv exit.Ipfv [dike-Def Loc],
 A: ‘At that point, *Brycinus* fish. As soon as a little light comes out, *Brycinus* fish go away from the dike.’
[Brycinus fish stay at the dike during the night, moving away at first light]

(02:22) A àywà [ŋūðn sààⁿ] [yé xà nà gàngá sàà-nì [ŋōròò ò]]
 well [DemDef time] [if 2Pl if.Pfv fishtrap lie-Caus.Pfv [DemDef.FocLoc]]
 [sáálí kùú-ŋàá sàà],
 [until setting.sun lie.down.Pfv],
 A: ‘Well, at that point, when you-Pl set the gàngá fishtrap in it, until the sun sets,’
[< gàngá sàà-ní, §3.6.3.5.6; kùú-ŋàá, originally “sun-eye”, denotes the rising (báy) or setting (sáá) sun at the horizon]

(02:26) A [ŋūðn sààⁿ], [máàⁿ-yè gá xùlù sùlèè]
 [DemDef time], [Rel-Pl Ipfv skiff propel.Ipfv]
 []óò lààxà-g = ì— [lááxá-g = ì]],
 [go.Ipfv camp-Def Loc— [camp-Def Loc]],
 [ŋūðⁿ-yè gá]wáà = [á tīⁿ]],
 [DemDef-Pl Ipfv go.Ipfv [3Sg under]],
 A: ‘At that point, those who propel the boat (with poles) to the camp, they convey it (=fish) (there).’
[sùlèè (/HLH/-melodic)]

(02:31) A ŋuà = á bàárāā, [léè máàⁿ-yè] kírè
 DemDef Ipfv heppen.Ipfv, [*Brycinus* Rel-Pl] be.gotten.Pfv
 níngé [wàlà níngè-]ià], yà = = á ŋūðⁿ-yè fòòyì-nî,
 yesterday.& [or day.before.yesterday], 3Pl Ipfv DemDef-Pl rot-Caus.Ipfv,
 A: ‘It happens, the *Brycinus* fish that were gotten (=caught), yesterday or the day before, they let it rot.’

[*Brycinus fish are set out to putrefy for a day or two before oil is extracted; nīngē and nīngé-ṣià, §8.4.5.1*]

(02:36) A [ṅūḍn sáàⁿ] yè =é nà á fòḍyì-nì,
 [DemDef time] if 3Pl if.Pfv 3Sg rot-Caus.Pfv,
 yà= =á bà= á sà [[bárkóó-búú bùdí] ÿ],
 3Pl Ipfv Fut 3Sg put.Pfv [[gas.drum-base cut.VblN.&] Loc,

A: ‘Then, when they have let it (=fish) rot, they will put it into a cut gas drum ...’
 [sá ‘put in’; a whole gas drum (metal barrel) has been cut in half so it is still cylindrical but open on top (like a trash can); bárkōō ‘gas drum’, búū ‘base, rear’, bárkóó-būū ‘gas-drum base’, búdí ‘cut.VblN’, bárkóó-búú bùdí ‘gas-drum cutting’]

(02:41) A [wàlà [xóri-yè níṅī]], [ṅūḍn sáàⁿ]
 [or [pot-Pl inside]], [DemDef time]
 yà= =á bì tùù lè [á tīⁿ],
 3Pl Ipfv Fut fire put.in.Pfv [3Sg under],

A: ‘... or into pots. At that point they (=women) will come and build a fire under it (drum or pot).’
 [‘into a cut gas drum or (into) pots’ with postposition níṅī having scope over both disjuncts, §7.2.1; tūú lè focally means ‘push firewood under the pot through gaps in the three-stone hearth’]

(02:44) A [yé [tùù tòmò] ná ìn lè [á tīⁿ]]
 [if [fire too] if.Pfv Refl put.in.Pfv [3Sg under]]
 yè [múò máàn] dì léé-ṅ-cìè→
 if [person Rel] IpfvNeg (hesitation)

A: ‘When the fire for its part has been built under it, if there is someone who doesn’t ...’
 [béé ‘remove, extract’ (antipassive of báá)]

(02:47) A [léé-ṅ-cìè bèè-ṅ-àà] tóò,
 [*Brycinus*-Link-oil remove.Antip.VblN-eye] know.Ipfv,
 [yá= àⁿ ná tùù lè [á tīⁿ]],
 [if 2Sg if.Pfv fire put.in.Pfv [3Sg under]],

A: ‘... know how to extract *Brycinus* oil, when you-Sg (=the person) build a fire under it, ...’

(02:50) A [cíé ḡ-kóòⁿ] án dá= à xéénèé [léè níḡī],
 [oil Link-one] 2Sg IpfvNeg 3Sg see.Ipfv [*Brycinus* inside],
 [cíé-júóḡ kóòⁿ] á dì xálíí yēē,
 [oil-child one] 3Sg IpfvNeg be.seen.Ipfv therein,
 A: ‘... you-Sg won’t see one drop of oil in (the) *Brycinus* fish Not one drop of oil
 will be seen therein.’
 [lit. “one oil, you-Sg don’t see it”; xálí ‘be seen’, §9.3.6]

(02:55) A [ḡūòḡ sáàⁿ] à =á bàárāā,
 [DemDef time] 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv,
 [tùù gá kèlè-nà [á tìⁿ] sāw̄,
 [fire be.Loc ignite-Ppl [3Sg under] now],
 A: ‘Then it happens that a fire is lit under it (=pot) now.’
 [the *Brycinus* fish will be slow-cooked in not-quite-boiling water]

(02:58) A à =á bàárāā, [jíí róò] gà [yé sīⁿ],
 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv, [water Foc] be.Loc [3Pl in.hand],
 [géré máàⁿ] ná yè [ḡḡ gá bì sólè]
 [place Rel] if.Pfv say.Pfv [Logo Ipfv Fut boil.Pass.Pfv]
 A: ‘It happens that they have water [focus] on hand. If there is anywhere that is
 about to be cooked (=boiled), ...’
 [lit. “a place that said it was going to be boiled”; yé variant of sé, also @ 03:02 below]

(03:01) A [ḡḡ gá bì ḡḡ]
 [Logo Ipfv Fut get.up.Pfv]
 [yà= =á jìí ḡùùrúú yēē],
 [3Pl Ipfv water pour.on.Ipfv therein],
 A: ‘... that is going to rise (=come to a boil), they pour some water onto it.’
 [the water should not reach a full boil;]

(03:02) A [géré máàⁿ] ná yè [ḡḡ gá bì sólè]
 [place Rel] if.Pfv say.Pfv [Logo Ipfv Fut boil.Pass.Pfv]
 [yà= =á jìí ḡùùrúú yēē],
 [3Pl Ipfv water pour.on.Ipfv therein],
 A: ‘If there is anywhere that is about to be cooked (=boil), they pour some water
 onto it.’
 [ḡúúrù]

(03:04) A sáálí [cìè-gù ḡḡⁿ] ná pòndè, bìè [júò fáà],
 until [oil-Def all] Sbjn float.Pfv, come.Ipfv [sky by],
 [ḡūòḡ sáàⁿ] yè wáy [bì léè-gù—]
 [DemDef time] (hesitation)
 A: ‘So that (eventually) all the oil comes floating to the top. Then they—’

(03:09) A [yè wáy bì léé-ŋ-cìè-gù tà-nì]
 [3Pl before Fut *Brycinus*-Link-oil-Def ascend-Caus.Pfv]
 [bà= á sà],
 [Seq 3Sg put.Pfv],

A: ‘Before they scoop up the *Brycinus* oil and put it (in a container).’

[wáy bì ‘before’, §17.2.5.1].

(03:12) A *mais* wáy-wáy-gì fúlé, [fóŋ ká] lò—
 but nowadays fish(v).VblN, [thing a.certain] enter.Pfv—
 ká gá lò-nà [[à tóò] nāāⁿ],
 a.certain be.Loc enter-Ppl [[3Sg foot] between],

A: ‘But nowadays, fishing, something got into—, something has come in between its feet.’

[i.e. there has been an innovation (in fishing)]

(03:15) A ŋūðn túùn dí yēē,
 DemDef Past not.be.Loc therein,
 yè gà á yèé jègè-mùgù, [ŋūðn túùn dí yēē]
 3Pl Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv fish-powder, [DemDef Past not.be.Loc therein]

A: ‘That didn’t use to be therein. They call it (in Bambara) “fish-powder.” That didn’t use to be therein.’

[jégé-múgú ‘fish-powder’ < Bambara, i.e. ground fish meal for chickens]

(03:19) A *parce que*, wáy-wáy-gì [yà= =á ŋōròò lēē]
 because nowadays [3Pl Ipfv DemDef pick.up.Ipfv]
 yē gà á làà [[wáá-[mèrè-yà-yè] róò] gā],
 3Pl Ipfv 3Sg give.Ipfv [[chicken-[raise.Antip-Agent-Pl] Foc] Dat],

A: ‘Because, nowadays they take that (=fish meal) (and) they give it to the chicken farmers [focus].’

[wáá-[mèrè-yà], §5.1.4.2]

(03:23) A [yá= á =à] fānāāⁿ, [kám nóò] túùn gá gō,
 [if 3Sg be.Cop] firstly, [dried.fish Foc] Past be.Loc there.Def,
 [ŋūðn sàāⁿ] yè é nà→,
 [DemDef time] (hesitation),

A: ‘By contrast, in the old days, there was (just) dried fish. Then they—.’

[large quantities of small fish like *Brycinus* were formerly dried for year-round cooking, nowadays much of the excess fish catch is sold for fish meal rather than dried;
 yá= á =à contracted and truncated < yá= á dì ŋūðⁿ nī ‘if it isn’t that’]

(03:27) A [yè é nà kúòmé], [yè ná dēsè],
 [if 3Pl if.Pfv fold.fish.Pfv], [3Pl if.Pfv be.unable.Pfv],

[yè ná [lèè-ɲ-cíé] bèè—
 [3Pl if.Pfv (hesitation)—

A: ‘When they folded (the fish), (and) they couldn’t handle (doing it all), (and) they ...’

(03:30) A [lèè-ɲ-cìè]-jí bèè,
 [Brycinus-Link-oil]-water remove.Antip.Pfv,
 yè ná dèèè,
 3Pl if.Pfv be.unable.Pfv,

A: ‘... extracted the liquid *Brycinus* oil, (and) they couldn’t handle (doing it),’
 [/[lèè-ɲ-cìè]-jí bèè, §9.3.1.3; cíé by itself can denote liquid (oil) or solid (butter)]

(03:32) A [ɲūðn sáàⁿ] [yē dèèè [[túròð máàɲ] xúmà] gù],
 [DemDef time] [3Pl be.unable.Pfv [[remainder Rel] on] Def],
 à =á bàáràá [yà= á sàw bàláà]
 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv [3Pl Ipfv grass reap.Ipfv]

A: ‘Then (if there was) leftover (fish) that they were unable to cope with, it would happen that they would cut grass (with a sickle), ...’

(03:35) A [yà= =á ɲōròð fáy [à xúmà],
 [3Pl Ipfv DemDef set.to.dry.Ipfv [3Sg on],
 [ɲūðn sáàⁿ] yé ɲūðⁿ ná gùé,
 [DemDef time] if DemDef if.Pfv dry(v).Pfv,

A: ‘... (and) they would set that (=the excess fish) out to dry on it (=grass). Then, when that had dried out, ...’

[*excess fish that was caught, beyond what could be handled for smoking or oil extraction, was laid out to dry in the sun*]

(03:39) A à =á bàáràà [lááxá ná]î]
 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv [camp if.Pfv get.up.Pfv]
 [yà= =á biè [ɲōròð tìⁿ] [nóð-g= ì]],
 [3Pl Ipfv come.Ipfv [DemDef under] [village-Def Loc]],

A: ‘It would happen that the (temporary) camp would get up (to move out). They bring that (=fish) to the (main) village.’

(03:41) A [ɲūðn sáàⁿ] yà= =á ɲōròð fùùnùù,
 [DemDef time] Pl Ipfv DemDef.Foc grind.Ipfv,
 yà= á ɲūðⁿ yàà [dé [kām nóð] nī],
 3Pl Ipfv DemDef put.Ipfv [for [fish.meal Foc] it.is],

A: ‘Then they would pound that (=fish, in a mortar). They would convert that (=fish) into ground fishmeal.’

[‘transform’ construction, §11.2.4.2; kām ~ kāmū]

(03:44) A *mais* wáy-wáy-gì dē→, kām— [kàm nò]—
 but nowadays (hesitation), fish.meal— [fish.meal Foc]—
 [kám gà á fùdò [bí tìⁿ],
 [fish.meal Ipfv 3Sg want.Ipfv [Seq disappear]

A: ‘But nowadays, fishmeal wants (=tends) to disappear.’

[fūō, §15.2.7.1]

(03:47) A [ŋūðn sáàⁿ] [ŋúó-ní gùé-nà máàŋ-giè]
 [DemDef time] [DemDef-Link dry(v)-Ppl Rel-Pl]
 gá ìⁿ fáy gù, [yē gà [á ʃièŋ] ʃūōⁿ]
 Ipfv Refl sit.Ipfv Def, [3Pl Ipfv [3Sg all] sew.up.Ipfv]

A: ‘Then those dry (ones) that were spread out (to dry), they (=people) would sew all of it (=fish) up (in sacks).’

[ʃūōⁿ ‘weave/sew up with broad strokes’]

(03:50) A yā= =à ʃwá= [[á ʃièŋ] tìⁿ] [[nóó xòlò] y],
 3Pl Ipfv go.Ipfv [[3Sg all] under] [[village big] Loc],
 yā= =à ywá= á tòdòdò,
 3Pl Ipfv go.Ipfv 3Sg see.Ipfv,

A: ‘They would transport all of it to a big city. They would go and sell it ...’

[< yē gà ʃóò ..., then variant < yē gà yóò ..., §10.1.6.2]

(03:54) A [ʃwáá-[mèrè-yà-giè] mā] [ŋōrðð níŋiⁿ]
 [chicken-[raise.Antip-Agent-Pl] against] [DemDef.Foc inside]
 S [yá á ðⁿ] fánááⁿ [kí fáà] bō
 [otherwise] firstly [1PlIn by] here

A: ‘... to the chicken farmers, in that (situation).’

S: ‘By contrast, long ago in the old days, here among us (Bozo).’

[postposition mā in ‘sell X [to Y]’, §8.2.7.2; yá á ðⁿ contracted/truncated < yá á ðì ŋūōⁿ nī, §16.1.4]

(03:58) S [ŋúó-ní kàmú-giè ród] túŋ gá ìn sáà
 [DemDef-Link fish.meal-Pl Foc] Past Ipfv Refl put.Ipfv
 [xúú-kìemà níŋiⁿ]
 [cooked.rice-unsauced inside]

S: ‘Those fish-meals [focus] are what used to be put in unsauced cooked rice meals.’

[a type of riz au gras, i.e. rice with sauce cooked in rather than served over it at meal time]

(03:59) A ðⁿhóⁿ [ŋūðⁿ-yè ród] túùŋ gá ìn sáà xúú-kièmà,
 uh-huh [DemDef-Pl Foc] Past Ipfv Refl put.Ipfv cooked.rice-unsauced,
mais wáy-wáy-gì
 but nowadays
 A: ‘Uh-huh, those [focus] are what used to be put in unsauced cooked rice. But nowadays ...’
[A’s turn overlaps with S’s preceding turn as he repeats what S says]

(04:02) A [ŋúó-ní ɲòòŋ gùé-nà máàŋ-gìè] gá ìⁿ fùùnúùⁿ dè,
 [DemDef-Link fish dry-Ppl Rel-Pl] Ipfv Refl pound.Ipfv Emph,
 yā = =à yòò ŋūòⁿ là,
 3Pl Ipfv go.Ipfv DemDef give.Pfv,
 A: ‘... any of those dried fish that are pounded (into meal), they (=people) go and give that (=dried fish), ...’

(04:05) S [ʃwáá-[mèrè-yà-gìè] gā]
 [chicken-[raise.Antip-Agent-Pl] Dat]
 A [ʃwáá-[mèrè-yà-gìè] ród] gā, ðⁿhóⁿ,
 [chicken-[raise.Antip-Agent-Pl] Foc] Dat, uh.huh,
 S: ‘... to the chicken farmers.’
 A: ‘... to the chicken farmers [focus]. Uh-huh.’

(04:07) A *bon* [ŋūòⁿ sáàⁿ], [xálú kóón] dí mǎā—,
 okay [DemDef time], [man alone] IpfvNeg be.able.Ipfv—,
 yé ɲùò— [yá = àⁿ ná à xáy]
 if fish— [if 2Sg if.Pfv 3Sg see.Pfv]
 A: ‘Okay, then, a man alone can’t—. If the fish— If you-Sg see him ...’
[kóóⁿ, ʃxxx]

(04:11) A [[xál kóóⁿ] fúlé ʃìèⁿ], [áⁿ má sigá yēē]
 [[man alone] fish(v).Pfv all], [2Sg Proh doubt.Pfv therein]
 [ā dī [ɲòó ród] kírēē],
 [3Sg IpfvNeg [fish Foc] get.Ipfv],
 A: ‘... a man fishing by himself, don’t doubt it! He isn’t getting any fish [focus].’
[sígā]

(04:14) A [yà = á =à] [ā kòòⁿ] dí mǎá fièw,
 [if 3Sg be.Cop] [3Sg alone] IpfvNeg be.able.Ipfv at.all,
 á = =á ʃí [ʃíⁿ fàjìrì],
 2Sg Ipfv get.up.Ipfv [since dawn],
 A: ‘Otherwise, he can’t (do it) alone at all. You-Sg get up at the pre-dawn prayer,’
[kóóⁿ, ʃí, ʃíⁿ]

(04:18) A [gúlò= óð] àŋ gá bìè,
 [night Foc] 2Sg Ipfv come.Ipfv,
 [ŋūðn sáàⁿ] [[ŋúó-ní gùlù-g=] í],
 [DemDef time] [[DemDef-Link night-Def] Loc],
 A: ‘You come (to the fishing spot) at night [focus]. Then, in (=during) that night,
 ...’
 [< gúlù róð]

(04:20) A yáálù-giè gà á lèè [báy [ŋūðⁿ mā]],
 woman-Pl Ipfv 3Sg pick.up.Ipfv [exit.Ipfv [DemDef against]],
 ǎl jùùn só kèlè,
 until year go.Pfv day.break.Pfv,
 A: ‘... the women pick it up (=start working with the fish), from that point, until
 the day goes and breaks, it happens that they are (involved) therein.’
 [léé ‘pick up’ in the sense ‘start doing’, §8.2.8.1; àlì ; báy, §8.2.8.2; júúŋ kélé ‘day has
 broken’, §11.1.1.2]

(04:23) A à =á bààràá [yà= =á yēē], ðⁿhóⁿ,
 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv [3Pl be.Loc therein, uh.huh,
 [télé bólá=] =á gōⁿ nà
 [ask.VblN other] be.Loc there.Def Q
 A: ‘It happens that they (=women) are (engaged) therein. Uh-huh. Is there another
 question?’

(04:28) S bon [[xáy tìŋááⁿ fááwò-g=] ì],
 okay [[1PlIn possession pond-Def] Loc],
 [fááwó-ŋúðⁿ máàŋ-giè] gà [xáy fáà] bōŋ gù,
 [pond-Dimin Rel-Pl] be.Loc [1PlIn by] here Def,
 S: ‘Okay, in our (inclusive) pond, the little ponds that are here around us
 (inclusive),’
 [diminutive fááwó-ŋúðⁿ, §5.1.5.2]

(04:33) S est-ce que [ŋúóⁿ [yè wáy]]
 Q [DemDef.& [and today]]
 [kí xáy] [fúlé-béénàà máàŋ gù],
 [1PlIn Prsntv] [fish.Vbln-manner Rel Def],
 S: ‘That (time) and today, the way we (inclusive) here are fishing, ...’
 [béénāā]

(04:35) S *est-ce que* [yé fà̀nà̀n-fù̀lè-gwà=] =á kò́óⁿ nī
 Q [and firstly-fish.VblN-Def] be.Cop same it.is
 A *bon,* [xáy→ fááwó-ɲù̀òⁿ máà̀n-gìè] xáy→ gṑn sā̀w gù,
 okay, [1PlIn pond-Dimin Rel-Pl] Prsntv there.Def now Def,
 S: ‘... are (it) and traditional fishing the same?’
 A: ‘Okay, our (inclusive) little ponds that are there now, ...’
 [kṑsⁿ (predicate)]

(04:45) A fáááⁿ fù̀lè-gù, [yé [sā̀w fù̀lè-gù]]
 firstly fish.VblN-Def.& [and [now fish.VblN-Def]]
 [yè dí [fù̀lè-bè̀nà̀ ñ-kò́óⁿ] nī],
 [3Pl not.be.Cop [fish.VblN-manner Link-one] it.is],
 A: ‘Traditional fishing and modern fishing, they aren’t the same fishing method.’
 [súú-béé̀nā́ ‘method, technique, system’]

(04:48) A *parce que* fò̀— [ɲū̀òⁿ-yè tòmò-yò̀ⁿ]
 because (false start)— [DemDef-Pl too]
 [modifé fíéré-yè] gáá̀nà ì̀n ló yēē,
 [change(n) many-Pl] Pfv Refl put.in.Pfv therein,
 A: ‘Because those ones for their part, many changes have been introduced therein.’

(04:52) A fáááⁿ— [fááwò-yé xáy sā̀w], à =á bàáráá [yè fááwò—]
 firstly— [pond-Pl Prsntv now], (hesitation) —
 à =á bàáráá [yè [fááwò ʃìè̀n] gá pò́y-nà bó̀lèé sā̀w],
 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv [if [pond all] be.Loc connect-Ppl together now],
 A: ‘Long ago— The ponds here now, it happens that when all the ponds are
 connected together (by annual flooding) now, ...’
 [cf. transitive pò́y ‘rip, open up’]

(04:59) A à =á bàáráá [ɲū̀ò̀n sááⁿ] à =á bàáráá
 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv [DemDef time] 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv
 [fááwò-ò gá [[mú̀ò lāmà-lāmà rò̀ò] fù̀ó] nì bó̀lèé],
 [pond-Def be.Cop [[person Iter-several Foc] Poss] it.is together],
 A: ‘... it would happen then, it would happen that the pond belonged to multiple
 people jointly.’
 [< fááwò-gù (definite suffix -gu is often contracted and may be inaudible in recordings)]

(05:03) A *parce que* ηūðm bààrà [yé =è gá pòy-nà bólēē]
 because DemDef happen.Pfv [if 3Pl be.Loc connect-Ppl together]
 à =á bààràā— [téé lámá-lámá-yé] gá yēē,
 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv— [fishtrap Iter-several-Pl] be.Loc therein,
 A: ‘Because it happened that when they (=ponds) were connected together, it
 happened that various fishtraps were there.’
 [téē ‘long fishtrap (that blocks off a water channel)’]

(05:07) A yè gá yè búdi-búdi, [ηūðn sáàⁿ]
 3Pl Ipfv 3Pl Iter-cut.Ipfv, [DemDef time]
 [yè [fááwò-gù jì] nà sólòm báy yēē]
 [if [pond-Def water] if.Pfv descend.Pfv exit.Ipfv therein]
 A: ‘They (=people) would cut them (=ponds) off (from each other). Then when the
 pond’s water had gone down there,’
 [*i.e. as the floodplain dries up or drains off annually; verb-stem iteration, §9.6.2*]

(05:11) A yè ná yè búdi báy [bólò mà] lámà tàn,
 3Pl if.Pfv 3Pl cut.Pfv exit.Ipfv [Recip against] only only,
 à =á bààràà [fááwò ʃī—]
 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv [pond any]—
 A: ‘As soon as they had cut them off from each other, it would happen that no
 pond—’
 [*‘as soon as’, §17.2.2.2*]

(05:14) A yè gá yèè
 3Pl Ipfv say.Ipfv
 [kú-nú fààwò] gà [[kú-nú fààwò] túù] nī,
 [Dem-Link pond] be.Cop [[Dem-Link pond] owner] it.is,
 A: ‘They would say, “this pond is the owner of this pond ...”’
 [*emend to ‘this person is the owner of that pond’, here and in the repetition just below*]

(05:16) A [kú-nú fààwò] gà [[kú-nú fààwò] túù] nī,
 [Dem-Link pond] be.Cop [[Dem-Link pond] owner] it.is,
 àywà [ηūðn sáàⁿ] [fááwò máàɲ ʃìèɲ] gá gō,
 well [DemDef time] [pond Rel all] be.Loc there.Def,
 A: ‘“... and that pond is the owner of that pond.” Well, then, any ponds that were
 (left) there,’
 [*i.e. each pond is owned by a specific clan*]

(05:19) A [fááwò ʃièn tòmó] [yé [in sáraxàadí-yè ród] nī],
 [pond all also.&] [and [Refl sacrifice(n)-Pl Foc]] it.is],
 [ɲū̀̀n sáàⁿ] [yé jìi nà sólòⁿ]
 [DemDef time] [if water if.Pfv descend.Pfv]
 A: ‘Each pond for its part had its (own) sacrifice. Then when the water (level) went down,’
 [i.e. its own rituals; ‘each X has its Y’, §7.1.7; sáraxàadí (< Arabic via Fulfulde)]

(05:24) A yè [xáxè kà] nà síɲè, [ɲū̀̀n sáàⁿ]
 if [amount a.certain] if.Pfv arrive.Pfv, [DemDef time]
 yā = =à ʃód fááwó-tù̀̀— [fááwó-tù̀̀ ród] gà órdúú lṑ̀,
 3Pl Ipfv go.Ipfv pond-owner— [pond-owner Foc] Ipfv order(n) give.Ipfv,
 A: ‘When it (=water) had reached a certain level, then they (=people) would go to the owner of the pond—. It’s the owner of the pond [focus] who would give the order.’
 [xáxē, órdúú; lṑ̀ ‘give (sth)’, form used when no dative PP is present, §9.3.3]

(05:29) A à =á bàáràà [fááwò nú—]
 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv [pond (false start)—]
 [[kú tú̀̀] gá [à tú̀̀] nī] [[kú tú̀̀] gá [à tú̀̀] nī],
 [[Dem owner] be.Cop [3Sg owner] it.is] (phrase repeated),
 A: ‘It would happen that the pond—. So-and-so is its owner, So-and-so was its owner.’
 [the names of the owners of the various ponds; kú tú̀̀ ‘So-and-so’, §5.1.6.1]

(05:32) A ɲkàà [ā tò̀̀ ród] gá [à xúmà] dè,
 but [3Sg name Foc] be.Loc [3Sg on] Emph,
 [kī [ɲū̀̀n tòmò] sè] [kí ná á [xò̀̀-nà]-nī],
 [1PlIn.Hort [DemDef too] say.Pfv] [1PlIn Sbjn 3Sg [white]-Caus]
 A: ‘But his (=owner’s) name [focus] was on it (=pond). Let’s say that too, and clarify it.’
 [kī 1PlIn hortative, §10.4.2; subjunctive add-on to hortative, §17.4.1.1]

(05:35) A [[nód ʃièⁿ nód] fùó] nī, lāwāl, [áj kóóⁿ]
 [[village all Foc] possession] it.is, the.past, [2Sg alone]
 [yè gá yè̀̀] [kú gá [àⁿ fááwò] nī],
 [3Pl Ipfv say.Ipfv] [Dem be.Cop [2Sg pond] it.is],
 A: ‘It belonged to all the villages. In the past, you-Sg by yourself, they would say “this is your-Sg pond.” ’

(05:40) A [áj kóón] dí màà jóò fièw,
 [2Sg alone] IpfvNeg be.able.Ipfv go.Ipfv at.all,
 áŋ gá jóò [áj gá fááwò fùléè],
 2Sg Ipfv go.Ipfv [2Sg Ipfv pond fish.Ipfv],
 A: ‘You-Sg (=the owner) would never be able to go (there) alone, (as in) you-Sg
 would go and fish the pond.’
 [māā ; ‘go and fish the pond’ is under the scope of ‘you could not’; can be emended as
 ... dí màà jóò [bì fááwò fùlè]]]

(05:43) A [yá= àⁿ ná á fùlè] [xééré dà= à jíelāā],
 [if 2Sg if.Pfv 3Sg fish(v).Pfv] [well.being IpfvNeg 3Sg bear.Ipfv],
 ŋkàà, [yē tòmò] dí màà jóò [á fùlè] fièw,
 but, [3Pl too] IpfvNeg be.able.Ipfv go.Ipfv [3Sg fish(v).Pfv] at.all,
 A: ‘If you-Sg (=the owner) fished it (=pond), (your) well-being would be at risk.
 But neither could they (=villagers) ever go and fish it (=pond).’
 [“your well-being won’t bear (young)”, formulaic for ‘your future well-being is at
 risk’; variant < jíélè ‘bear young’, which is elsewhere intransitive; xééré]

(05:48) A yá= [àⁿ nóò] dí sàrdí lōō,
 if [2Sg Foc] PfvNeg scheduled.date give.Pfv,
 yá= [àⁿ nóò] dì sólòⁿ fànáàⁿ,
 if [2Sg Foc] PfvNeg descend.Pfv firstly,
 A: ‘If it wasn’t you-Sg [focus] who gave (=scheduled) the date (for the fishfest), if
 it wasn’t you-Sg [focus] who went down (to the pond) first, ...’
 [sárdí]

(05:50) A [ŋūòñ sáàⁿ]— [ŋūòñ sáàⁿ]
 [DemDef time]— [DemDef time]
 [yá= à ná ìm búdi [báy [bólò mā]]],
 [if 3Sg if.Pfv Refl cut.Pfv [exit.Ipfv [Recip against]]],
 A: ‘... then, if it (=pond) hadn’t been cut off (from other ponds), ...’

(05:52) A [yá= àⁿ ná àn sàrdí lōō],
 [if 2Sg if.Pfv 2Sg scheduled.date give.Pfv,
 [ŋūòñ sáàⁿ] [yá= àŋ gá bì sólò]
 [DemDef time] [if 2Sg Ipfv Fut descend.Pfv]
 A: ‘... when you-Sg (=owner) had given (=scheduled) your day, then, when you-Sg
 were going to (=were ready to) go down (to the pond), ...’

(05:55) A [ŋūà = = á bààràá fàààⁿ],
 [DemDef Ipfv happen.Ipfv firstly],
 [kíéŋè rá =] à sólōōⁿ,
 [fishtrap Foc] Ipfv descend.Ipfv,
 kíéŋé, [yè [xóy-xóy]-fùòⁿ],
 fishtrap.&, [and [Iter-jab.VblN]-point],

S: ‘... then it would happen in the old days that fishtraps would go down (to the pond). Fishtraps and jabbing spears.’

[kíéŋè, here with left conjunct tones, §7.1.2; xóy antipassive and verbal noun < verb xòò ‘jab, weave’; fishtraps are plunged downward into shallow open water to catch any unseen fish; jabbing spears with multiple points are stabbed downward into very shallow water covered with vegetation, generally to catch any unseen fish]

(06:01) A ŋōrò twⁿá = = à bō, ŋūòm bààrà sár-séw—
 DemDef Past be.Loc there.Def, DemDef happen.Pfv (hesitation)—
 [sár-séw túùn dì gōⁿ fàààⁿ],
 [cast.VblN-net Past not.be.Loc there.Def firstly],

A: ‘That [focus] is what was there. It happens that there weren’t any casting nets there in the old days.’

[sár-séw, a net that is cast from shore or from inside a boat, then pulled back in; cf. verb sári]

(06:06) A á = à fáàmúⁿ nà, fénúúŋ jààdà—
 2Sg 3Sg understand.Pfv Q, (hesitation) —
 [fénúúŋ jààdà-nà kà-rèè] gá gō,
 [long.fishnet huge-Ppl a.certain-Pl] be.Loc there.Def,

A: ‘Did you-Sg understand it? There are (nowadays) some enormous long fishnets.’

[fénúúⁿ is a very long fishnet that is set across a small river or pond]

(06:10) A ŋūòⁿ-yè túùn dì gō, á = à fáàmúⁿ nà,
 DemDef-Pl Past not.be.Loc there.Def, 2Sg 3Sg understand.Pfv Q,
 [ŋ gáánà [fòⁿ fèndèèⁿ máàn] sè gù]
 [1Sg Pfv [thing two Rel] say.Pfv Def]

A: ‘Those (enormous fishnets) were not there (in the old days). Did you-Sg understand it? The two things that I (already) mentioned,’

(06:13) A [ŋ xáy biè [káwàà mā], ŋūðm bààrà
 [1Sg Prsnt come.Ipfv [sweep.net against], DemDef happen.Pfv
 [[káwàà máàⁿ], yē gà á yàà kíénàáŋ gù,
 [[sweep.net Rel]. 3Pl Ipfv 3Sg put.Ipfv like.this Def,
 A: ‘Here I’m coming to (the topic of) sweep-net. It happened that the sweep-net
 that they use like this (gesturing),’
*[káwàà fishnet with wooden handles swept in shallow water by one person then closed
 up; relative head preposed with prosodic break and resumed by a pronoun; yāā (Ipfv);
 kíénāāⁿ, §4.4.2.2.1]*

(06:17) A wálàà, [kú-yé ród] túùŋ gá gōⁿ fànáàⁿ,
 voilà, [Dem-Pl Foc] Past be.Loc there.Def firstly,
 ŋkàà sàw xùbì-séw bè kū-ŋūðⁿ—
 but now flip.VblN-net come.Pfv whatchamacallit—
 A: ‘There! It was these (fishing devices)[focus] that were there in the old days. But
 now, the flip net has come, whatchamacallit—
*[xúbì-séw, a long net, one end of which is held by several people, the other of which is
 swept to catch fish]]*

(06:22) A yē ŋūðⁿ-yè lò— yē ŋūðⁿ-yè lò [fùlè-gìè níŋī],
 (hesitation)—3Pl DemDef-Pl put.in.Pfv [fish.VblN-Pl inside],
 yè =é nà sò [kúù ŋ-kóðⁿ],
 if 3Pl if.Pfv go.Pfv [day Link-one],
 A: ‘They have introduced those into fishing (methods). If they go (to the pond) for
 one (full) day, ...’

(06:27) A [yà = =á [ŋòò ʃìèŋ] kíélūū]
 [3Pl Ipfv [fish all] entrap.Ipfv]
 [yē gà á tà-nì [báy yēē]],
 [3Pl Ipfv 3Sg ascend-Caus.Pfv [exit.Ipfv therein]],
 A: ‘... they trap all the fish (and) they take it (=fish) up and out from there.’

(06:30) A àywà [ŋōròò gà
 well [DemDef.Foc be.Loc
 [[fànáàⁿ-fùlè-gíé, [yè [wáy fùlè-gíé]] nāāⁿ
 [[firstly-fish.VblN-Pl.&, [and [today fish.VblN-Pl]]] between],
 A: ‘Well, that [focus] is (the difference) between traditional fishing methods and
 current fishing methods.’

(06:33) A [fúlé-gíé túⁿà = = á [kìénààⁿ nóð]], ðⁿhóⁿ
 [fish.VblN-Pl Past Ipfv [like.this Foc]] uh.huh
 S káwàà húnúⁿ, yè [xóy-xóy]-fùsⁿ, yè kíéjè,
 sweep.net Top.&, and [Iter-jab.VblN]-point.&, and fishtrap,
 A: ‘Fishing methods used to be (done) like this [focus]. Uh-huh.
 S: ‘As for sweep nets, and jabbing spears, and fishtraps, ...’
[cf. 05:55-06:13 above; some mike feedback here, and A echoes S’s words almost synchronously; ‘like this’ used like a verb]

(06:40) A [kú-yé ród] túùŋ gà sólòðⁿ [fááwò-giè níŋī]
 [Dem-Pl Foc] Past Ipfv descend.Ipfv [pond-Pl inside]
 S [kú-yé ród] túùŋ gà sólòóⁿ fànáàⁿ
 [Dem-Pl Foc] Past Ipfv descend.Ipfv firstly
 A: ‘These [focus] used to go down to the pond.’
 S: ‘... these [focus] used to go down in the old days.’
[here S echoes A’s words almost synchronously]

(06:42) A fááwò-giè níŋī, ðⁿhóⁿ
 pond-Pl inside inside, uh.huh
 S *mais*, áŋ xāy, [fénúúm bòlò máàⁿ] sèé sāw gù,
 but, 2Sg Prsntv, [long.fishnet other Rel] say.Ipfv now Def,
 A: ‘To the pond.’
 S: ‘But, the long fishnet that you-Sg here were talking about now,’
[fénùùⁿ, cf. @ 06:06 above]

(06:47) S xúbí-séw-gù
 flip.VblN-net
 A xúbí-séw-gù húnù, ŋūá = à sóló-nà sāw
 flip.VblN-net Top, DemDef be.Loc descend-Ppl now
 S: ‘The flip-net.’
 A: ‘As for the flip-net, that one has (already) gone down (there) now.’
[cf. 06:17 above]

(06:51) S yá = àⁿ ná ŋūðn sóló-nì [àl [dígè níŋī]],
 if 2Ssg if.Pfv DemDef descend-Caus.Pfv [until [river inside]],
 A dígè níŋī
 river inside
 S: ‘If you-Sg take that one (=long fishnet) down all the way to the river, ...’
 A: ‘To the river.’

(06:53) S ā dī [ɲòò ʃí] tǒy yēē
 3Sg IpfvNeg [fish any] leave.Ipfv therein

A ā dà = á tǒy gǒ,
 3Sg IpfvNeg 3Sg leave.Ipfv there.Def

S: ‘... it (=long fishnet) doesn’t leave any fish therein.’

A: ‘It doesn’t leave it there.’

(06:56) A [ā gā [á ʃìɛŋ] kíélūū]
 [3Sg Ipfv [3Sg all] entrap.Ipfv]

ā gā á tà-nî, ðⁿhóⁿ
 3Sg Ipfv 3Sg ascend-Caus.Ipfv, uh.huh

A: ‘It entraps all of it (=fish) (and) it lifts them up. Uh-huh.’

[i.e. the people pull the fish up with the long net]

(06:58) S [ɲūðŋ túròò] gā dépassé
 [DemDef remainder] Ipfv excessive

A parce que yá = àⁿ ná à tónò [àl wáy],
 because if 2Sg if.Pfv 3Sg look.at.Pfv [until today],

S: ‘The remainder of that (=fishing techniques) is overdone.’

A: ‘Because, if you-Sg look at it even nowadays,’

[tūròò ; French dépassé pronounced dépàsé (Ipfv)]

(06:59) A [géré gá [gèrè-yé nāāⁿ], [ɲūðⁿ-yà = á interdit]
 [place be.Loc [place-Pl between], [DemDef-Pl 3Sg prohibit]

ā dī sólòóⁿ [[yè fááwò] níŋī], ðⁿhóⁿ
 3Sg IpfvNeg descend.Ipfv [[3Pl pond] inside], uh.huh

A: ‘In some places, those ones (=some pond owners) have prohibited it (flip-net).
 It doesn’t (=can’t) go down to their pond(s). Uh-huh.’

[lit. “a place is among the places”]

(07:01) A ā dī sólòóⁿ [[ɲūðⁿ-yè fááwò] níŋī],
 3Sg IpfvNeg descend.Ipfv [[3Pl pond] inside],

séw dī sólòóⁿ [[yè fááwò] níŋī], ðⁿhóⁿ
 net IpfvNeg descend.Ipfv [[3Pl pond] inside], uh.huh

A: ‘It doesn’t go down to those ones’ ponds. A (flip-)net doesn’t go down to their
 pond(s). Uh-huh.’

(07:08) A [ɲūðⁿ-yè gèrè-yè tòmò] ɲūðⁿ-yè interdit
 [DemDef-Pl place-Pl too] DemDef-Pl prohibit

A: ‘Their (=owners’) places for their part, they (=nets) are prohibited.’

recorded in Dia, 2022

file 180103_0039

duration 04:44

transcribable portion 00:19 - 04:44

speakers and their abbreviations in order of appearance:

Seni Yalouta (S), male

Alfa Boubacar Karabenta (A), male, main narrator

(00:22) S àywà ālfāā sàláámùàlèèkúm
well A peace.to.you

A wáléékúmsàlām
to.you.peace

S: ‘Well, Alfa, peace to you.’

A: ‘To you peace.’

[*formal Arabic greetings*]

(00:23) S [ɲ xáy] [ɲ ʃíégè biè xwáà]
[1Sg Prsntv] [1Sg return.Pfv come.Ipfv again]

A ìnfáàláàw
if.God.wills

S: ‘Here I have come back again.’

A: ‘If God wills.’

[ʃíégè ; Arabic ‘if God wills’]

(00:27) S [xáy ɲá] [xáy xày] [sòð máàⁿ] sòð sāw,
[1PlIn QTop] [1PlIn Prsntv] [farm.VblN Rel] farm(v).Ipfv now,
est-ce que [xáy fànáàn-sòð-w] [yé sāw sòð-w],
Q [1PlIn firstly-cultivate.VblN-Def.&] [and now cultivate.VblN-Def],
S: ‘As for us (inclusive), the farming that we here are doing now. Our old-time farming and (our) modern farming ...’

[*presentative as progressive, §10.2.2.3; tones of conjuncts, §7.1*]

(00:32) S gá kòðⁿ ní nà
be.Cop same it.is Q

A [xáy [fànáàn sòð→]] [yé [sāw sòð-giè]],
[1PlIn [firstly farm.VblN.&]] [and [now farm.VblN-Pl]]

S: ‘... are the same?’

A: ‘Our old-time farming and (our) modern farming methods, ...’

[‘be the same’, §4.6.1.1;]

(00:37) A ā dī [sós-béénáá ŋ-kósòⁿ] nī
 3Sg not.be.Cop [farm.VblN-manner Link-one] it.is
 S (unintelligible)

A: ‘... it isn’t the same farming method.’

S: (unintelligible)

[sós, béénāā]

(00:39) A ā dī [sós-béénáá ŋ-kósòⁿ] nī
 3Sg not.be.Cop [farm.VblN-manner Link-one] it.is
parce que, yá= àⁿ ná à tónò, fánááⁿ,
 because, if 2Sg if.Pfv 3Sg look.at.Pfv, firstly,

A: ‘It isn’t the same farming method. Because if you-Sg look at it, in the old days, ...’

(00:45) A áŋ gá à tóò [xáy fáà] bō, [ká-réé rósò]
 2Sg Ipfv 3Sg know.Ipfv [1PlIn by] here, [a.certain-Pl Foc]
 twⁿá= =á gō, ŋūòⁿ-yè twⁿá= =á sōō,
 Past be.Loc there.Def, DemDef-Pl Past Ipfv farm(v).Ipfv,

A: ‘... you-Sg know (that) among us here, there were certain (people), those (people) used to farm.’

(00:50) A à =á bàáràá [ŋūòⁿ-yè rósò] twⁿá= =à yéé-nà
 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv [DemDef-Pl Foc] Past be.Loc be.put-Ppl
 [dé [yè sós-yá xòló-yè] nī],
 [for [3Pl farm(v)-Agent big-Pl] it.is],

A: ‘It would happen that those (people) used to be their big farmers.’

[cf. yâà dē ‘become (sth)’, §11.2.4.2]

(00:53) A a→ cíè— [fánááŋ-cíé-gíé témé-yōⁿ]
 ah! (hesitation)— [firstly-field-Pl too]
 [cíé-ŋúòⁿ-yè cíé-ŋúòⁿ-yè rósò] nī,
 [field-Dimin-Pl field-Dimin-Pl Foc] it.is,

A: ‘Ah, the old-time fields for their part, it was (just) small fields.’

[témé-yōⁿ, §19.1.3; ‘small fields’ iterated for distributivity]

(00:57) A ŋkàà bá= á yè [táár ŋ-kósòⁿ]
 but Seq 3Sg say.Pfv [hectare Link-one]
 [táár pèndèèⁿ] [tààr]ííyòⁿ
 [hectare two] [hectare three]

A: ‘But (let’s) say one hectare, two hectares, three hectares, ...’

[tāār ‘hectare’]

(00:59) A àlí [tààr náàⁿ] [tààr kólòⁿ],
 until [hectare four] [hectare five],
 ηūðñ túùn dì gōⁿ fàⁿààⁿ,
 DemDef Past not.be.Loc there.Def firstly,

A: ‘... up to four hectares (or five) hectares. That wasn’t there in the old days.
[i.e. the fields were less than one hectare]

(01:03) A fàⁿááⁿ [cìé-ñúóη kòòrì-nà] [cìé-ñúóη kòòrì-nà],
 firstly [field-Dimin round-Ppl] [field-Dimin round-Ppl],
 à =á bàáràá [yē gà á yēē]
 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv [3Pl Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv]

A: ‘In the old days (it was just) small circular fields. It would happen that they would say (=call it), ...’

(01:07) A [[sáál-kóðⁿ] sós-n-tō], [sáál pèndèèⁿ]
 [[dry.measure-one] farm.VbIN-Link-place], [dry.measure two]
 àlí kà-rèè, [cìé xòló] túù—
 even a.certain-Pl, [field big] owner—

A: ‘... a one- or two-*saawal* farming plot. Even certain ones (=people), owner(s) of big field(s), ...’

[a plot that can be seeded with one or two saáwâl dry measure (a few kilos of rice seed); saáwâl abbreviated to sáál with a following numeral]

(01:11) A [cìé xòló] túù-yè ród], [ηūðⁿ-yè ród] gà á yēē a→
 [field big owner-Pl Foc], [DemDef-Pl Foc] Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv ah!
 [ñ húnù] [[yórðð-yórðó-w húnù] gáánà sód [[ñ sùù] gā]]
 [1Sg Top] [[Iter-self-Def Top] Pfv cultivate.Pfv [[1Sg hand] Inst]]

A: ‘It’s owners of big field(s) [focus], it’s those ones (=owners) [focus] who say, “Ah, I myself have cultivated with my own hand(s).” ’

(01:15) A [ñ nà [sáál kìèrmà-tàⁿàà-kíéni], ñ nà
 [1Sg Sbj/Obj [dry.measure seventy], 1Sg Sbj/Obj
 ηōrò fááⁿyà, bon ηōrò twⁿá= =á gō,
 DemDef.Foc sow.Pfv, okay DemDef.Foc Past be.Loc there.Def,

S: ‘ “I (used) seventy *saawal*. That [focus] is what I planted.’ Well, that (situation) [focus] was there.’

[‘seventy’, §4.6.1.4]

(01:20) A *bon* másíŋ-gìè só bāy [wààdù máàn] sà,
 okay machine-Pl go.Pfv exit.Ipfv [time Rel] Emph,
 [ŋūðn sáàⁿ] yē gà [cíé xòlól] lēē,
 [DemDef time] 3Pl Ipfv [field big] take.Ipfv
 A: ‘Okay, when the machines (=plows) went and came out, then they would take a
 big field.’
 [másiⁿ ; wáádū]

(01:24) A [táár ñ-kóðⁿ] [táár pèndèèⁿ],
 [hectare Link-one] [hectare two],
 ŋūðⁿ ìn sìnídí [ŋṛò níŋī],
 DemDef Refl begin.Pfv [DemDef.Foc inside],
 A: ‘One or two hectares, that (situation) [focus] began in that (way).’
 [sìnídí]

(01:28) A á= à fáàmú, [ŋūðm bààrà
 2Sg 3Sg understand.Pfv, [DemDef happen.Pfv
 [[fánááⁿ→ júó-gíé témé-yóⁿ], [yé [sāw jùð-gìè]]] dí kòóⁿ nī
 [[firstly rice-Pl too.&], [and [now rice-Pl]]] not.be.Cop one it.is
 A: ‘You understood it? It happened that the old-time rice varieties and the modern
 rice varieties are not the same.’

(01:32) S à dí kòóⁿ nī
 3Sg not.be.Cop one it.is
 A fánáám bógóntōō→, e→ yē wō [yé gòròbàlí-yè→],
 firstly rice.cultivar, eh! 3Pl said [and rice.cultivar-Pl],
 S: ‘It isn’t the same.’
 A: ‘In the old days (there were) *bogonto*, (what) they called *gorobali*, ...’
 [bógóntōō, góróbàlí, álbā (*cultivars of rice*), with list intonation]

(01:38) A [yé àlbá-yè], fánááⁿ [ŋūðⁿ-yè róð] túùŋ gá
 [and rice.cultivar-Pl], firstly [DemDef-Pl Foc] Past Ipfv
 ñ xáyⁿ [xáy fáà] bō, ðⁿhóⁿ
 Refl work.Ipfv [1PlIn by] here, uh.huh
 S: ‘... and *alba*. In the old days, those [focus] were what was worked (=cultivated)
 here among us. Uh-huh.’

(01:42) A [fánáán-sóó-gíé [yé [wáy sóó-gìè]]]
 [firstly-cultivate.VblN-Pl.& [and [today cultivate.VblN-Pl]]]
 à dí [bèènáà-yà ñ-kóðⁿ] nī,
 3Sg not.be.Cop [manner Link-one] it.is,
 A: ‘Old-time farming and today’s farming, it isn’t the same system.’

(01:45) A ñhúⁿ à dí [bèènáà-yà ñ-kóòⁿ] nī,
 uh.huh 3Sg not.be.Cop [manner Link-one] it.is,
 fánááⁿ yè tú= a—, twⁿá= =á sòò [[sùú ròò] gā],
 firstly 3Pl (hesitation), Past Ipfv cultivate.Ipfv [[hand Foc] Inst],
 A: ‘Uh-huh. It isn’t the same system. In the old days they used to cultivate by hand.’

(01:50) A ñkàà ā ñ gòbí, māsím bè,
 but 3Sg Repl flip.Pfv, machine come.Pfv,
 [māsím bè] [ñòrò bè [[cìé xòlò-giè]—
 [machine come.Pfv] [DemDef come.Pfv (hesitation)—
 A: ‘But it has changed. The machine (=plow) came. The machine came and that [focus] (=machine) brought ...’

(01:55) A [[cìé xòlò-giè] tīⁿ]]
 [[field big-Pl] under]]
 S wáy, náá-màsíñ gá sòò, mótóókíltéér gá sòò,
 today, cow-machine Ipfv cultivate.Ipfv, motor.plow Ipfv cultivate.Ipfv,
 A: ‘... big fields.’

S: ‘Today, the ox-drawn plow does farming, the self-propelled plow does farming.’
[French motoculture, a plow that is pulled forward by a motor, while the farmer steers it with handles from behind; here and just below A echoes S’s segments almost synchronously (not transcribed)]

(02:03) S kátóróⁿfílaàn gá biè sòò,
 Caterpillar Ipfv come.Pfv cultivate.Pfv
 [ā]ièñ] gá sòò wáy,
 [3Sg all] Ipfv cultivate.Ipfv today,
 S: ‘Caterpillar (agricultural machine) comes and does farming. All of it (=them) does farming nowadays.’

(02:06) A àywà ñòrò bè [[cìé xòlò] tīⁿ],
 well DemDef.Foc come.Pfv [field big] under],
 fánááⁿ [cìé-ñúòⁿ-yè cìé-ñúòⁿ-yè ròò] nī, òⁿhóⁿ
 firstly [field-Dimin-Pl field-Dimin-Pl Foc] it.is, uh.huh
 A: ‘Well, that [focus] is what brought big field(s). In the old days it was (just) little fields. Uh-huh.’

(02:12) S [ŋ yōròò] dâr [bì sód-yè wàlè [xáy fáà] bō],
 [1Sg self] ExpPf [Seq cultivate.VblN-Pl do.Pfv [1PlIn by] here],
 A ŋōrò [xáy sód] yìrìwà-nì kienāāⁿ
 DemDef.Foc [1PlIn cultivate.VblN] expand-Caus.Pfv like.this,
 S: ‘I myself have done the farming systems here among us (inclusive).’
 A: ‘That [focus] is what has expanded our (inclusive) farming like this.’
[experiential perfect, §10.2.1.2; here and in the next segment S and A overlap (partially transcribed)]

(02:16) S bà= á kùyé-nì
 Seq 3Sg be.many-Caus.Pfv
 A bà= á kùyé-nì
 Seq 3Sg be.many-Caus.Pfv
 S: ‘And increased it.’
 A: ‘And increased it.’

(02:17) S bí bè [pèrìmètìrí tīⁿ]
 Seq come.Pfv [perimeter under]
 A bí bè [pèrìmètìrí tīⁿ]
 Seq come.Pfv [perimeter under]
 S: ‘And brought irrigated fields.’
 A: ‘And brought irrigated fields.’

[local French périmètre, here denoting fields irrigated by mechanized sprinklers]

(02:19) S bí bè [[láámá-níjǐ]-sòò-giè tīⁿ]
 Seq come.Pfv [[the.bush-inside]-cultivate.VblN-Pl under]
 A bí bè [[láámá-níjǐ]-sòò-giè tīⁿ]
 Seq come.Pfv [[the.bush-inside]-cultivate.VblN-Pl under]
 S: ‘And brought bush farming.’
 A: ‘And brought bush farming.’

[farming out in the bush, away from settlements and water sources]

(02:21) S jààtí
 exactly
 A ǎl [ŋōrò níjǐ] [[wáxádí kà] níjǐ],
 until [DemDef.Foc inside] [tie a.certain] inside],
 S: ‘Exactly.’
 A: ‘Until in that (situation) [focus], at a certain time, ...’

(02:24) A \bar{n} $n\grave{a}$ \grave{a} $x\acute{a}y\rightarrow$, [$m\acute{u}\grave{d}$ $l\acute{a}a\grave{m}\grave{a}$ $k\grave{a}-r\grave{e}\grave{e}$] $n\acute{\eta}\eta\bar{i}$,
 1Sg Sbj/Obj 3Sg see.Pfv, [1PIEx the.bush a.certain-Pl] inside,
 $k\acute{a}-r\acute{e}\acute{e}$ $b\acute{e}$, $y\bar{e}$ $w\bar{o}$ [$y\grave{e}$ $b\grave{e}$],
 a.certain-Pl come.Pfv, 3Pl said [LogoPl come.Pfv],
 A: ‘... I saw it, in some of our bushlands, some (people) came, they said “we have
 come.” ’

(02:29) A [[$y\acute{e}$ $k\grave{a}$] $c\acute{\eta}\acute{e}$ $s\grave{i}r\grave{e}$] $t\acute{u}\eta\eta$ $g\acute{a}$ $g\bar{o}$,
 [[LogoPl father] field former] Past be.Loc there.Def,
 [[\bar{a} $t\bar{u}\grave{u}$] [$f\acute{u}$ $m\acute{a}\grave{a}\eta\eta$] $x\grave{a}\grave{a}y\grave{i}$]
 [[3Sg owner] [thing Rel] show.Pfv]
 A: ‘(they said:) “Our father’s original field is there. What the fellow showed, ...’
 [$f\acute{u}$ $m\acute{a}\grave{a}^n$, §14.1.1]

(02:33) A $\bar{a}\eta$ $k\bar{o}\bar{o}$ [[$t\grave{a}\grave{a}r$ $n\acute{a}\acute{a}r\grave{a}n$] $t\bar{e}$],
 3Sg be.many.Stat [[hectare four] Dat],
 [$\eta\bar{o}r\bar{o}$ $n\acute{\eta}\eta\bar{i}$] [[$m\acute{u}\grave{d}$ $x\acute{o}n\acute{o}m\grave{o}n\grave{o}-g\grave{u}$] $b\grave{e}$]
 [DemDef.Foc inside] [[1PIEx old.person-Def] come.Pfv]
 A: ‘It was more than four hectares. At that point an old man of ours (exclusive)
 came.’
 [3Sg \bar{a}^n in clause linkage; $k\bar{o}\bar{o}$ [X $t\bar{e}$] ‘be more than X’, §12.1.2]

(02:35) A \bar{a} $w\bar{o}$ [$k\grave{u}$ $t\bar{u}\grave{u}$ $fil\grave{a}\grave{a}n\grave{a}$]
 3Sg said [Dem owner so.and.so]
 \bar{a} $w\bar{o}$ [$\acute{a}n$ $d\acute{\eta}$ $t\acute{e}\acute{e}n\grave{e}$ $s\grave{e}$],
 3Sg said [2Sg PfvNeg truth say.Pfv],
 A: ‘He (=old man) said, “So-and-so (vocative),” he said, “you-Sg didn’t tell the
 truth.” ’

(02:37) A \bar{a} $w\bar{o}$ [$n\bar{o}\bar{d}$ [$y\acute{e}$ [$\grave{a}\eta$ $x\acute{o}n\acute{o}m\grave{o}n\grave{o}-g\grave{u}$]]]
 3Sg said [1Sg.Foc [and [2Sg old.person-Def]]]
 $m\acute{u}\grave{d}$ $t\acute{u}\eta\eta$ $g\acute{a}$ $s\bar{o}\bar{o}$ [[$\grave{\eta}n$ $s\grave{u}\acute{u}$ $r\bar{o}\bar{d}$] $g\bar{a}$],
 1PIEx Past Ipfv cultivate.Ipfv [[Refl hand Foc] Inst],
 A: ‘He (the other) said, “I and your father, we used to do farming with our own
hands [focus].”
 [1PIEx $m\acute{u}\grave{d}$ coindexed by ReflPl $y\acute{e}$, §18.1]

(02:40) A \bar{a} $w\bar{o}$ $h\grave{a}y\grave{w}\grave{a}$, \bar{a} $w\bar{o}$ $\eta\bar{u}\bar{o}m$ $b\acute{a}\acute{a}r\grave{a}$,
 3Sg said well, 3Sg said DemDef happen.Pfv,
 \bar{a} $w\bar{o}$ $m\acute{u}$ — \bar{a} $w\bar{o}$ $y\bar{e}$ —, $n\bar{o}\bar{d}$, $k\acute{u}r\acute{u}b\grave{a}l\grave{a}$,
 3Sg said (hesitation)— 3Sg said (hesitation), me, K,
 A: ‘He said, “well,” he said, “(as) it happened,” he said, “I, Kouroubala, ...”

(02:47) A ā wō [yé ród lámà] túùŋ gá
 3Sg said [LogoPl Foc only] Past Ipfv
 [sáál kìèrmà-tàŋààkièni] [yé ród] túùŋ gá—
 [dry.measure seventy] [LogoPl Foc] Past Ipfv—
 A: ‘... he said, “we [focus] alone used to (use) seventy *saawal*—, we [focus] used to—” ’

(02:49) A [[bá= à sód [sùù gā]]
 [[Seq 3Sg cultivate.Pfv [hand Inst]]
 [yé ród] túùŋ gá à sód [sùù gā],
 [LogoPl Foc] Past Ipfv 3Sg cultivate.Ipfv [hand Inst],
 A: ‘ “To cultivate it (=field) by hand. We [focus] used to cultivate it by hand.” ’
[after hesitation pause (end of preceding segment), imperfective VP is repaired as a sequential VP; the whole is then repeated without a hesitation pause]

(02:53) A [ŋōrò níŋi] ā wō hàywà [áŋ xónómòndò-gù],
 [DemDef.Foc inside] 3Sg said well [2Sg old.person-Def],
 ā wō àlá= à túùn dí mǎā
 3Sg said [even 3Sg Past IpfvNeg be.able.Ipfv]
 A: ‘At that point he said, “well, your-Sg old man (=father),” he said, “he could not even ...” ’

(02:55) A [sáál tàⁿ], [bá= à sód-n-tò sód]
 [dry.measure ten], [Seq 3Sg cultivate.VblN-Link-place cultivate.Pfv]
 [bá= à fááⁿyà] ā wō [ā túùn dí mǎā],
 [Seq 3Sg strew.Pfv] 3Sg said [3Sg Past IpfvNeg be.able.Ipfv],
 A: ‘... have cultivated its farming plot with ten *saawal*, to strew it (=seeds). He couldn’t have.’
[i.e. ten saawal would be too little seedstock for four hectares; restarts with bá= à ..., can be rephrased more smoothly as ... [sáál tàⁿ] sōō ; place nominal sód-n-tō, §4.2.1.8]

(02:59) A ðⁿhóⁿ [ŋūòŋ tòmò] ná bày yēē
 uh.huh [DemDef too] if.Pfv exit.Pfv therein
 [xày ród] xày fáⁿ— jùà fááⁿyāā
 [1PlIn Foc] Prsntv (hesitation)— rice strew.Ipfv
 A: ‘Uh-huh. When that has gone out (=aside from that), we (inclusive) here strew the rice (seedstock) ...’

(03:02) A [bá= à tómbò [bólò xúmà],
 [Seq 3Sg concentrate.Pfv [Recip on]],
 [yá= àⁿ ná fàⁿàⁿ-mù^ò-gì^è tèle]
 [if 2Sg if.Pfv firstly-person-Pl ask.Pfv]
 A: ‘... to concentrate it together (in a few spots). If you-Sg asked the old-time people, ...’
 [fánááⁿ-mú^ó]

(03:05) A yē wō [ŋū= =á [bàⁿyìⁿ nò^ò] nī],
 3Pl said [DemDef be.Cop [ruin.VblN Foc] it.is],
 yē wō [yé jù^à ná ìn tómbò lámà],
 3Pl said [if rice if.Pfv Refl concentrate.Pfv only],
 A: ‘... they (=old-timers) said, “that is a waste,” they said, “as long as rice (seed) is concentrated (rather than evenly dispersed), ...” ’

(03:08) A ā dà= à kírè [bí ìŋ kàlà],
 3Sg IpfvNeg 3Sg get.Pfv [Seq Refl shatter.Pfv],
 ā dà= à kírè [bí tòmó bààrì],
 3Sg IpfvNeg 3Sg get.Pfv [Seq head take.out.Pfv],
 A: ‘(they said) “... it (=growing rice) doesn’t get enough room to break out; it doesn’t get room to get its head (=grain spike) out.” ’
 [i.e. the rice stems will be too densely packed together and won’t develop well]

(03:11) A ðⁿhóⁿ [ŋū^òⁿ-yè fì^èŋ] gá lè-ná yēē,
 uh.huh [DemDef-Pl all] be.Loc enter-Ppl therein,
 xá [yè bólò]—,
 2Pl.& [and other]—,
 A: ‘Uh-huh. Those ones (=rice plants) are all entered therein (=clumped together). You-Pl and other(s)—.’

(03:14) A [[fánáán sód] [yé [sāw sód]]] nāⁿ
 [[firstly cultivate.VblN] [and [now cultivate.VblN]]] between
 S fánáán sód-fò, [néfēē máàn] tú^ùŋ gá yēē,
 firstly cultivate.VblN-thing, [value Rel] Past be.Loc therein,
 A: ‘Between old-time farming and modern farming.’
 S: ‘The crop(s) of the old days, the value that was therein, ...’
 [sód-fò, §3.9.3.5.1; néfēē]

(03:21) S [yé [sāw sós-fò], [máⁿ nèfèè ród] gá yèé
 [and [now cultivate.VblN-thing], [which? value Foc] be.Loc therein
 sāw, [míndèéⁿ nóð] gá [[im bóló] kíēⁿ]
 now, [where? Foc] be.Loc [[Refl Recip] before]
 S: ‘... and modern crops, what value is therein? Where (=which one) is in front of
 (=better than) the other?’
 [‘which?’, §13.2.2.8 (tones §3.6.3.3.1); néfèè ; ‘where?’, §13.2.2.4; ‘be before’ = ‘be
 better than’, §12.1.4]

(03:25) A yá= àⁿ ná à tónò,
 if 2Sg if.Pfv 3Sg look.at.Pfv,
 yè gá yèè [fànààn sós-fò],
 3Pl Ipfv say.Ipfv [firstly cultivate.VblN-thing],
 A: ‘If you-Sg look at it, (what) they call old-time crop(s), ...’

(03:29) A yē tū̀̀n̄̀ gá á sṑ̀,
 3Pl Past Ipfv 3Sg cultivate.Ipfv,
 dé [jìè-ménè ród lámà] nī,
 for [food-look.for.VblN Foc only] it.is,
 A: ‘... they used to cultivate it only for food-seeking (=subsistence).’
 [as opposed to cash crops; dē X nī, §8.3.3]

(03:33) A yē tū̀̀n̄̀ gá á sṑ̀ [bí [yè jìé rṑ̀] mánà]
 3Pl Past Ipfv 3Sg cultivate.Ipfv [Seq [ReflPl food Foc] look.for.Pfv]
 [fànàànⁿ yá= àⁿ ná à tónò],
 [firstly if 2Sg if.Pfv 3Sg look.at.Pfv],
 A: ‘They used to do farming to seek their food [focus]. In the old days, if you-Sg
 look at it, ...’

(03:37) A yá= àⁿ ná sṑ̀→,
 if 2Sg if.Pfv go.Pfv,
 [yá= àⁿ ná nàfàà sò̀̀ sāw̄̀]
 [if 2Sg if.Pfv crops cultivate.Pfv now]
 A: ‘... if you-Sg go, (and) if you-Sg cultivate crops now,’
 [náfáā]

(03:39) A yá= àⁿ ná bà= [á tī̀̀],
 if 2Sg if.Pfv come.Pfv [3Sg under],
 à =á bàárāā, [yáálù-gìè =á bāy]
 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv, [woman-Pl Ipfv exit(v).Ipfv]
 A: ‘When you-Sg bring it (=crops), it happens that the women go out (into the
 bush).’

(03:43) A [ŋūðⁿ-yà = =à yòò xððnð-ñ-tó],
 [DemDef-Pl Ipfv go.Ipfv water.lily.tuber-Link-place],
 yà = á byà = [á tīⁿ],
 3Pl Ipfv come.Ipfv [3Sg under],
 A: ‘Those ones (=women) go to the water-lily-tuber harvesting place. They bring it
 (=water lily root tubers, to the village).’
 [a shallow pond; xóónó-n-tō, place nominal, §4.2.1.8; < bíé]

(03:46) A ŋūðn sáàⁿ, yè = =é nà fííⁿ-núðn lèè,
 DemDef time, if 3Pl if.Pfv shelled.rice-Dimin take.Pfv,
 [yè ná xððnð-núðn lèè]
 [3Pl if.Pfv water.lily.tuber-Dimin take.Pfv]
 A: ‘Then, when they take a little shelled rice (and) they take a few water lily tubers,
 ...’
 [fííⁿ ‘shelled rice’ (stored in sacks in houses); xóónó]

(03:49) A yè gá yè sólòò bólēē,
 3Pl Ipfv 3Pl cook.Ipfv together,
 yá = àⁿ wáy [fðŋ kà] jìà [ŋūðⁿ ý],
 if 2Sg as.soon.as [thing a.certain] eat.Pfv [DemDef Loc],
 A: ... they cook them (tubers and rice) together. As soon as you-Sg have eaten
 something from that, ...’
 [wáy, §17.2.2.1; partitive, §6.3.2.1]

(03:52) A [ŋūðm bààrà] [[ŋóó tómó] gà kírēē],
 [DemDef happen.Pfv] [[fish too] Ipfv be.gotten.Ipfv],
 [[áⁿ wáy] [fðŋ kà] jìà]
 [[2Sg as.soon.as] [thing a.certain] eat.Pfv]
 A: ‘... it (may) happen that (some) fish too can be gotten. As soon as you-Sg have
 eaten something (of it),’

(03:56) A [à =á bààràà] [kúù sìrèèⁿ]
 [3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv] [day day.be.spent.Pfv]
 [á = =á jì mèénēē],
 [2Sg Ipfv water drink.Ipfv],
 A: ‘It happens that the whole day passes (while) you-Sg drink water.’

(03:58) A [à =á bàáràá [áŋ gá làá-cìègè-nà],
 [3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv] [2Sg be.Loc sated-Ppl],
 wáy-wáy-gì [áŋ gá àm búómááyāā]
 nowadays [2Sg Ipfv 2Sg eat.breakfast.Ipfv]

A: 'It happens that you-Sg are full. Nowadays you-Sg eat breakfast.'

[làá-cìègè-nà 'sated, full (of food and drink)', mutated from ... gá àlà cíégè (lāā)
 'praise(s) God']

(04:01) A [láákélé fáà] =à síŋēē [ā =à yéé-nà] ñgàáyèè
 [lunch by] Ipfv arrive.Ipfv] [3Sg be.Loc put.Antip-Ppl] like
 [áⁿ fǒrò ród] gá bì ìm búdi,
 [2Sg intestine Foc] Ipfv Fut Refl cut.Pfv,

A: '(By the time) lunchtime is arriving, it has become like your-Sg intestines [focus]
 are going to be cut open.'

[*'like/as though' expressions, §8.4.1*]

(04:04) A bon ŋū = =á lè-nà [[yé [kù ñá]] nāāⁿ,
 okay DemDef be.Loc enter-Ppl [[and [Dem QTop] between],
 [wáy sóð tòmò] [jágò ród] nī, [múð-giè fáà]
 [today cultivate.VblN too] [commerce Foc] it.is, [person-Pl by]

A: 'Okay, that (situation) has gone in between (the past) and this (=the present).
 Today's farming for its part is commerce, among the people.'

[*can be repaired as ñòrò gá lè-nà [kú [yè kú]] nāā 'that [focus] has gone in between
 that and this' (i.e. distinguishes the past versus the present)*]

(04:08) A [yé [fànààn sóð] dí [bèènáà ŋ-kódⁿ] nī, òⁿhóⁿ
 [and [firstly cultivate.VblN] not.be.Cop [manner Link-one] it.is, uh.huh
 S [táár tàŋ] gá tàwáà [múð-yè síⁿ],
 [hectare ten] Ipfv be.found.Ipfv [person-Pl in.hand],

A: '(It) and old-time farming are not the same system. Uh-huh.'

S: 'Some people have ten hectares.'

[bèénnāā]

(04:15) S [táár tà-m-èndèŋ] gá tàwáà [múð-yè síⁿ],
 [hectare twenty] Ipfv be.found.Ipfv [person-Pl in.hand],
 [périméétírí fú máàn] gá [àn síⁿ] [á ŋ-kōō],
 [perimeter thing Rel] be.Loc [2Sg in.hand] [3Sg Link-be.many.Stat],

S: 'Some people have twenty hectares. The irrigated fields that you-Sg have are
 many.'

[*optional ŋ- linker with kōō; here again speaker A echoes S's phrases, not all of it
 transcribed*]

(04:20) S [ā ʃìèŋ] [jágò ròò] nì wáy
 [3Sg all] [commerce Foc] it.is today
 A [ā ʃìèŋ] [jágò ròò] nì wáy
 [3Sg all] [commerce Foc] it.is today

S: 'All that is (for) commerce.'

A: 'All that is (for) commerce.'

(04:22) S màá [sāw húnù] ò ná à mánà
 Dubit [now Top] 1Sg Sbj/Obj 3Sg look.for.Pfv
 [dè [lǎá-jìé ròò] nī]
 [for [mouth-food Foc] it.is]

S: 'It would be unusual that nowadays I would seek it (=rice) for subsistence [focus].'

[*dubitative* màá, §17.3.2; dē, §8.3.3; lǎá-jìè]

(04:24) S [kyá= =á bì kì súurdáⁿ yèè [xóò-g= ì]
 [1PlIn Ipfv Fut 1PlIn hush.up.Pfv therein [house-Def Loc],
 [ŋūòñ ò ò gòⁿ wáy]
 [DemDef not.be.Loc there.Def today]

S: 'We (inclusive) would keep quiet about it (=rice) in the house. That (=farming for subsistence) is not (done) there nowadays.'

(04:27) S [fánááⁿ nòò] [ŋūòñ twⁿá= =á bō],
 [firstly Foc] [DemDef Past be.Loc here],
 ŋkàà wáy yá= à yáà [dè jágò nī],
 but today 3Pl 3Sg put.Pfv [for commerce it.is],

S: 'In the old days [focus] that was (done) here. But nowadays they have turned it into commerce.'

(04:29) A [jíé ròò] nī, [kí fáà] jíà bō fànààⁿ,
 [food Foc] it.is, [1PlIn by] Dia here long.ago,
 [jíé ròò] nī,
 [food Foc] it.is,

A: 'It was (staple) food, among us here in Dia (village) in the old days. It was food.'

(04:32) A [wáy húnù] sòò bè [dè [jágò ròò] nī]
 [today Top] cultivate.VblN come.Pfv [for [commerce Foc] it.is]
 á= à xáy rà
 2Sg 3Sg see.Pfv Q

A: 'As for nowadays, farming has come to be commerce. Did you-Sg see it?'

recorded in Dia, 2022

file 180103_0041

duration 08:08

transcribable portion 00:18 - 08:08

light mike feedback in first third, then worse @ 06:30-50, but transcribable throughout

topics: organization of circumcision and excision (00:00); circumcision as requirement for marriage (00:56) and for going to war (01:06); group circumcision of agemates (01:22); circumcision/excision organized by Malinke (02:20); guidance of an unmarried young woman by a specific young man (02:40); marriage (05:48); kíéńú wáń rite

speakers and their abbreviations in order of appearance:

Seni Yalouta (S), male, interviewer

Alfa Boubacar Karabenta (A), male, main speaker

(00:18) S àywà álfáá bòkâr, [àl wáy] kî à [bólò gā],
 well A B, [until today] 1Pl be.Loc [Recip Inst],
 ā wō *est-ce que*, fànààⁿ→, [bí múò lò [sàńj-jiì gā],
 3Sg said Q firstly, [Seq person give.Pfv [prayer-water Dat],
 S: ‘Well, Alfa Bocar, so far we are (still) jointly involved. So, is it (the case), formerly, to have someone undergo cision.’

[glosses use “cision” as cover term for circum- and excision; “give X to ablutions” = ‘have X undergo cision’; ló is ambiguous between ‘give/be given’ and ‘enter/be put in’, but dative gā points to ‘give/be given’ while locative PP (as @ 01:52 below) points to ‘enter/be put in’]

(00:28) S [fánááⁿ-fánááⁿ]-[sánj-jiì], yé sàw-[sàńj-jiì] *est-ce que* kòóⁿ nī,
 [Iter-firstly]-[prayer-water]&, and now-[prayer-water] Q one it.is,
 A [fánááⁿ-fánááⁿ]-[sánj-jiì] yé sàw-[sàńj-jiì]
 [Iter-firstly]-[prayer-water]& and now-[prayer-water]
 à dí kòóⁿ nī,
 3Sg not.be.Cop oneit.is,

S: ‘Old-time cision and today’s cision, are they the same?’

A: ‘Old-time cision and today’s cision, it is not the same.’

[“give(sb) prayer-water (for ablutions)” = ‘circumcise/excise (sb)’; ‘be one’ = ‘be identical’, §4.6.1.1]

(00:36) A *parce que*, yé nà= á sè [à dí kòóⁿ nī] *parce que*,
 because, if 1Sg.Pfv 3Sg say.Pfv [3Sg not.be.Cop one it.is] because,
 fánááⁿ-fánáán lówāl, [jáà yóròò] làwàl-làwāl,
 Iter-firstly long.ago, [Dia self] Iter-long.ago,
 A: ‘Because, if I say that it is not the same, because, (in) the old days, Dia (village)
 itself (in) the old days.’
 [yóròò, §18.2]

(00:42) A á= à fáàmúⁿ nà, *parce que*,
 2Sg 3Sg understand.Pfv Q, because,
 [kév àlmààmí] nà gáxé tò,
 [uncle imam Sbjn infraction let.Pfv,
 A: ‘Did you-Sg understand it? Because, may Uncle imam excuse me!’
 [kév ‘mother’s brother’; àlmààmí ; gáxé variant of xáxé ; tó variant of tóy in this
 formula; A excuses himself for using an indelicate word]

(00:50) A *bon*, múò, á= =á lóò [sàniŋ-jì gà] júrūū→,
 okay, person, 2Sg Ipfv be.given.Ipfv [prayer-water Dat] this.year,
 kónósē→, ā xūmā-sāā→,
 next.year, 3Sg successor,
 A: ‘Okay, (suppose) someone (=you), you-Sg are being circumcised this year, next
 year, (or) its successor (=the following year), ...’
 [júrùù ; xúmá-sāā ‘successor, deputy (of sth)’, structurally xúmá-sāā ; list intonation,
 §7.1.12]

(00:56) A à =á bàárà= [á= =á bì—]
 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv [2Sg Ipfv Fut—],
 [á= =á bì lò [[xóò róò] y],
 [2Sg Ipfv Fut enter.Pfv [[house Foc] Loc],
 A: ‘(Suppose) it happens that you-Sg are— you-Sg are going to get married.’
traditionally timed to occur one year before marriage]

(00:58) A fánááⁿ à =á ŋīēⁿnāāⁿ, *parce que*
 firstly 3Sg Ipfv thus.Def, because
 bá= [á sàbàbú] yáà [dé [fòŋ kóòⁿ] nī],
 Seq [3Sg reason] put.Pfv [for [thing one] it.is],
 A: ‘In the old days it was like that (just described). Because, for the cause of it to
 be the same, ...’
 [ŋīēⁿnāāⁿ, §4.4.2.2.2]

(01:02) A fánááⁿ, [kúnùⁿ nódò] túùŋ gá gā,
 firstly, [war Foc] Past be.Loc there.Def,
 á= à fáàmúⁿ nà,
 2Sg 3Sg understand.Pfv Q,
 A: ‘In the old days, there used to be warfare. Did you-Sg understand it?’
 [for kúnùŋ-gù nà ...]

(01:06) A [kúnùⁿ-ùⁿ nà] níŋī,
 [war-Def QTop] inside,
 bíláákòró dī jóò,
 uncircumcised IpfvNeg go.Ipfv
 A: ‘In war, an uncircumcised boy did not go.’
 [< kúnùŋ-gù ; bíláákòró < Bambara, Tigemaxo synonym [sáníŋ-jíí-m]-bári]

(01:09) A [máàn dí lò [sàŋŋ-jìì gā]]
 [Rel PfvNeg be.given.Pfv [prayer-water Dat]]
 [ŋūòŋ dī jóò [kúnùⁿ níŋī], bon [ŋūòŋ lāā]
 [DemDef IpfvNeg go.Ipfv [war inside], okay [DemDef Purp]
 A: ‘Anyone who had not been circumcised, that one did not go to war. Okay,
 because of that, ...’
 [lāā ‘because of’, §8.3.1; correlative relative structure, §14.1.9]

(01:12) A [yá= àⁿ wáy lò [sàŋŋ-jìì gā]],
 [if 2Sg as.soon.as be.given.Pfv [prayer-water Dat]],
 á= =à jóò [[kúnùⁿ nódò] níŋī]],
 2Sg Ipfv go.Ipfv [[war Foc] inside]],
 A: ‘... once you-Sg had undergone circumcision, you-Sg would go to war.’
 [wáy, §17.2.2.1]

(01:15) A bon [ŋōròò lāā] [yè túùⁿ—]
 okay [DemDef Purp] (false start)
 [yā= =à [kóyn-lòy]-gù yààŋxàr-nî]
 [3Pl Ipfv [circumcision]-Def postpone-Caus.Ipfv]
 A: ‘Okay, for that reason, they would postpone the circumcision rite.’

(01:18) A [àlà= á nà yáà [dé jùòl-kòdòbòòrì nī],
 [until 3Sg Sbjn become.Pfv [for young.man-bull it.is],
 yē wáy bì yé lò [sàŋŋ-jìì gā],
 3Pl before Fut 3Pl give.Pfv [prayer-water Dat],
 A: ‘... until he (=boy) became a sturdy young man, before they (=parents) have
 circumcised them.’
 [‘until’ subjunctive clause, §17.4.2; ‘become’, §11.2.4.2; ‘before ...’ with wáy bì,
 §17.2.5.1]

(01:22) A àywà [ŋũðn sáàⁿ] yē nè= é l̀ [sà̀nìj-jì gā]
 well [DemDef time] 3Pl if.Pfv 3Pl give.Pfv [prayer-water Dat],
 yà= á bààrà
 if 3Sg happen.Pfv
 [[máàj ʃìèŋ] gá [kà̀tègòrì-kà̀tègòrì kóòⁿ] nī],
 [[Rel all] be.Cop [Iter-category one] it.is],
 A: ‘Well, at that point, when they have circumcised them, if it happens that all those
 who are of the same age-grade, ...’
 [< yá = à ná bààrà]

(01:28) A yè xá yēē→, sáá-xóõ
 3Pl Ipfv say.Pfv, lie.down.VblN-house
 [yá= àⁿ ná= à tóǹ wáy-wáy-gì]
 [if 2Sg if.Pfv 3Sg look.at.Pfv nowadays]
 A: ‘They call it bedroom. If you-Sg look at (=consider) it nowadays, ...’
 [xá dialectal (and Tieyaxo) for Ipfv gá]

(01:30) A xálámééⁿ jíní-j̀d̀d̀ⁿ, xálámééⁿ jíní-j̀d̀d̀ⁿ,
 child little, child little
 fánááⁿ ŋũðn tú̀n d̀ì g̀d̀,
 firstly DemDef Past not.be.Loc there.Def,
 A: ‘A small child, a small child, in the old days that (=small child) was not there
 (=in war).’
 [jíní-j̀d̀d̀ⁿ ‘little’, more diminutive than míyóóⁿ ‘small’, §5.1.5.3]

(01:34) A á= =à síŋèé [j̀ù̀n tàⁿ], [júún táⁿ-ỳŋ-kól̀ⁿ] ỳ,
 2Sg Ipfv arrive.Ipfv [year ten], [year ten-and-five] Loc,
 S ăl tàm-ə̀ndèèⁿ
 even twenty
 A: ‘You-Sg would attain ten years, (or) fifteen years.’
 S: ‘Up to twenty.’
 [‘fifteen’, §4.6.1.4]

(01:37) A júún [tám-ə̀ndé= èŋ xú má-f̀d̀] ỳ,
 year [twenty and extra] Loc,
 áⁿ wáy bì l̀ [sà̀nìj-jì gā],
 2Sg before Fut be.given.Pfv [prayer-water Dat],
 A: ‘, (or) twenty-plus years, before you-Sg were circumcised.’
 [‘twenty’, §4.6.1.4; xú má-f̀d̀ ‘supplement’ (in counting), cf. xú má ‘on’; ‘before’,
 §17.2.5.1]

(01:40) A [ɲū = à bàáràà [ɲúó-ní kòdòbòòrì-kòdòbòòrì]
 [DemDef Ipfv happen.Ipfv [DemDef-Link Iter-bull]
 [ɲūòṃ bàárà
 [DemDef happen.Pfv
 [sáá-xóó [=é sàà-xóó] ròò] túùŋ gá gō],
 [bedroom.& [and bedroom] Foc] Past be.Loc there.Def]],

A: ‘That (=situation) would happen (to find) that each bull (=sturdy young man), that one (=bull) would happen to have a bedroom [focus].’

[iterated ‘bull’ and ‘bedroom’ are paired in a distributive (“each”) relation; in the old days, a grown young man would have his own bedroom, whereas nowadays even little children have bedrooms]

(01:45) A [yá = á ðì ɲūòⁿ nī]
 [if 3Sg not.be.Cop DemDef it.is]
 wáy-wáy-gì [yá = àⁿ ná = à tónò],
 nowadays [if 2Sg if.Pfv 3Sg look.at.Pfv],

A: ‘By contrast, these days, if you-Sg look at (=consider) it, ...’

[wáy-wáy-gì, §8.4.5.1]

(01:47) A [kíéŋé fíéré] xày bìè [[múò-gìé [=è bólò]] nāāⁿ],
 [debate many] Prsntv come.Ipfv [[person-Pl.& [and Recip]] between],
 fánááⁿ [ɲúó-ní kìèŋè-gù] túùn ðì gō,
 firstly [DemDef-Link debate-Def] Past not.be.Loc there.Def,

A: ‘... look at the many disputes that have come (=arisen) between people and others. In the old days that dispute wasn’t there.’

(01:52) A [máàŋ fìèŋ] túùŋ gà [wàlndè kóòⁿ] nī,
 [Rel all] Past be.Cop [age.class one] it.is,
 [ɲūòⁿ-yé róò] =á lóó [sàŋŋ-jì níŋì] bólēē,
 [DemDef-Pl Foc] Ipfv enter.Ipfv [prayer-water inside] together,

A: ‘Everyone who is of the same age class, those (boys) undergo circumcision together.’

[wàlndē (< Fulfulde) ‘age class’ (e.g., group who are circumcised together); ló glossed ‘enter’ with locative PP]

(01:56) A [yē rō =] =á sàá sàà-xòò— [sáá-xóó níŋì] bólēē,
 [3Pl Foc] Ipfv lie.down.Ipfv (hesitation) [bedroom inside] together,
 [ɲūòⁿ sàáⁿ] [ɲūòⁿ-yè xúmá-sàá-gìè],
 [DemDef time] [DemDef-Pl successor-Pl],

A: ‘They [focus] sleep together in the (same) bedroom. Then their successors, ...’

[yē rōò, §13.1.2; sáá-xóó ; xúmá-sāā ; ‘successor’: the next cohort of boys to be circumcised together]

(02:00) A [ŋũðⁿ-yè tèmè] gá biè lò, [ŋũðⁿ níŋĩ],
 [DemDef-Pl too] Ipfv come.Ipfv enter.Pfv, [DemDef inside],
bon, [yáál-ńúóⁿ mỳdòđ-ğìè] twⁿá = = á ñĩè⁺nāāⁿ,
 okay, [woman-Dimin small-Pl] Past be.Loc thus.Def
 S: ‘Those ones (=the next cohort) too come and enter into that (bedroom). Okay,
 young girls were that way, ...’
[lò in added perfective VP after motion verb, §15.1.2; túùŋ gá ; yáál(ú)-ńúóⁿ and (just below) xál(ú)-ńúóⁿ, §5.1.5.2]

(02:05) A [xál-ńúóⁿ míyóóŋ] túùŋ gá ñĩè⁺nāāⁿ,
 [man-Dimin small] Past be.Loc thus.Def
 ñkàà wáy-wáy-ğì ñũðⁿ ìŋ gòbí, àywà [ŋũðⁿ sáàⁿ],
 but nowadays DemDef Refl flip.Pfv, well [DemDef time],
 A: ‘... (and) young boys were that way. But nowadays that has changed. Well, at
 that time, ...’
[góbì]

(02:11) A [ŋũðŋ gá bàárāā], [[xál-ńúóⁿ míyóóŋ] gá gō]
 [DemDef Ipfv happen.Ipfv], [[man-Dimin small] be.Loc there.Def]
 [[yáál-ńúóⁿ mỳdòđŋ] gá gō],
 [[woman-Dimin small] be.Loc there.Def],
 A: ‘It happened that there were the young boys, (and) there were the young girls.’

(02:16) A [ŋũðŋ sáàⁿ] yé =è gá bì lò, sáŋĩⁿ—
 [DemDef time] if 3Pl Ipfv Fut be.given.Pfv, prayer—
 à = á bàáràà [áⁿ nòđ]— [[áⁿ nòđ] jùðⁿ],
 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv (hesitation) [[2Sg Foc] child],
 A: ‘Then when they (=boys and girls) were cised, it would happen that your-Sg
 [focus] child (=son), ...’
[cut off from sáŋĩŋ-jí gā]

(02:20) A [áŋ júóŋ] gá máníŋá-jùðⁿ nĩ,
 [2Sg child] be.Cop Malinke-child it.is,
 [nòđ jùðŋ] gá tígé-jùðⁿ nĩ, [ŋũðŋ sáàⁿ],
 [1Sg.Foc child] be.Cop Bozo-child it.is, [DemDef time],
 A: ‘(Suppose) your-Sg child was a Malinke, (and) my [focus] child was a Bozo. At
 that time, ...’
[máníŋà ‘Malinke (ethnicity)’]

(02:24) A [án tíŋàà] [máàŋ ʃìèⁿ] [máàŋ ʃìèŋ] gá sàgá-nà [à mā],
 [2Sg possession] [Rel all] [Rel all] be.Loc connect-Ppl [3Sg against],
 à =á bàáràá [án [tíŋáá xò̀nò̀mò̀nò̀]]
 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv [2Sg [possession old]]

A: ‘Yours (=your-Sg son), each one who would hang out with him. It would happen that your-Sg old one (=father) ...’

[tíŋāā ‘possession’ (generic), §6.2.2.2, here replacing ‘child’; máàⁿ ʃìèⁿ iterated for distributivity; participle sàgá-nà from reflexive verb sàgà ‘stick to, hang out with’]

(02:29) A à =á [ŋū̀ò̀ŋ ʃìè̀m] búómbáà [iⁿ fáà],
 3Sg Ipfv [DemDef all] call.over.Ipfv [Refl by],
 [jíà bó] ā gá [yé ʃìè̀n] ló̀ò̀ bó̀lè̀è̀,
 [Dia here] 3Sg Ipfv [3Pl all] put.in.Ipfv together,

A: ‘He (=your father) would invite all those (=boys) over to his place. Here in Dia (village), he (=father) puts them all in (=has them circumcised) together.’

(02:33) A à =á bàáràà
 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv
 [tígé-jù̀ò̀n tú̀ùn dì [ìŋ jù̀ò̀n] ló̀ò̀ [sà̀nìŋ-jì̀ gā̀]]
 [Bozo-child Past IpfvNeg [Refl child] give.Ipfv [prayer-water Dat]]

A: ‘It would happen that a Bozo didn’t use to have his child circumcised, ...’

[“Bozo-child” etc. can denote individuals of any age; the point here is that Malinke rather than Bozo or griot men used to organize and run circumcision events for all ethnicities]

(02:35) A [kóŋáá-jù̀ò̀n dì ìŋ jù̀ò̀n ló̀ò̀ [sà̀nìŋ-jì̀ gā̀]],
 [griot-child IpfvNeg [Refl child] give.Pfv [prayer-water Dat]],
 mais wáy-wáy-gì, ŋū̀ò̀ⁿ-yè̀ bàý yè̀è̀,
 but nowadays, DemDef-Pl exit(v).Pfv therein,

A: ‘... (and) a griot didn’t use to have his child circumcised. But nowadays, those ones have gone away from there (=that practice).’

(02:40) A bon [ŋū̀ò̀n sáàⁿ] à =á bàárāā juoⁿ—
 okay [DemDef time] 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv (hesitation)
 [áŋ júóⁿ-yáálú] wáy ʃî→,
 [2Sg child-female] as.soon.as get.up.Pfv,

A: ‘Okay, then, it would happen that as soon as your-Sg daughter had grown up, ...’

(02:43) A à =á bàárāā [jùòŋ-xàlù kóòŋ] gá gō,
 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv [child-male one] be.Loc there.Def,
 ńkàà wáy-wáy-gì yè [ŋūòŋ ʃièm] bààⁿyìⁿ,
 but nowadays 3Pl [DemDef all] ruin.Pfv,
 A: ‘It would happen that there was one boy—. But nowadays they have ruined all that.’

[here begins a segment on the relationship between an unmarried young woman and a young man (not her lover or future husband) as her friend and guide]

(02:48) A [ŋūòŋ sáàⁿ], [kév àlmààmí] nà gáxé tò gòy, *parce que*
 [DemDef time], [uncle imam Sbjn infraction let.Pfv Emph, because
 [bááⁿyíŋ-gú ròò] bà= [[á tòò-[níŋá-yà] tìⁿ]] wáy-wáy-gì,
 [ruin(n)-Def Foc] come.Pfv [[3Sg name-[bad-Abstr] under]] nowadays],
 A: ‘Then, may Uncle imam excuse me! Ruin (=bad behavior) [focus] is what has brought its getting a bad name these days.’

[formula before saying something indelicate; ‘bring’, §11.1.1.4; tóò ‘name’]

(02:53) A fánááⁿ yē gá á yèè
 first 3Pl Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv
 [[kú túù] gá [kù sùŋgùrù-ù] nī,
 [[Dem owner] be.Cop [Dem young.woman-Def] it.is,
 [kú túù] gá [kù júólì] nī,
 [Dem owner] be.Cop [Dem young.man] it.is,
 S: ‘In the old days they would say, “So-and-so is the young woman of this one (=young man), (and) So-and-so is the young man of this one (=young woman).” ’

[< sùŋgùrù-gù]

(02:57) A [sùŋgùrù yé júólì] wáy [ŋòrà= á bààⁿyìⁿ],
 [young.woman.& [and young.man] today [DemDef 3Sg ruin.Pfv],
 [yá= à dí ŋòòⁿ nī]
 [if 3Sg not.be.Cop DemDef it.is] §
 A: ‘(The relationship of) a young woman and a young man, today that [focus] (=bad behavior) is what has ruined it. By contrast, ...’

(02:99) A fánááⁿ, [bá= [àŋ jùòŋ] kùⁿ]
 firstly, [Seq [2Sg child] catch.Pfv]
 [bá= à xálifá [múò mā]],
 [Seq 3Sg entrust.Pfv [person against]],
 A: ‘... in the old days, to catch (=take) your child (=daughter), (and) to entrust her to someone (=a young man), ...’

[sequential VPs without main clause, §15.2.17; mā with ‘entrust (to)’, §8.2.7.2]

(03:03) A η̄r̀d̀d̀ túùⁿ nī, máá-xàl̀ù—
 DemDef.Foc Past it.is, (hesitation)
 máá-xàl̀ù túùn ò máá-yààl̀ù kór̀d̀s̀f̀i ẁ,
 brother Past IpfvNeg sister watch.over.Ipfv Ø,

A: ‘... that [focus] was it. A brother didn’t use to watch over a sister.’

[final ẁ sometimes added to a prepausal verb as in ā b̀è (w) ‘he/she came’, perhaps reduced from clause-final definite gú]

(03:06) A fánááⁿ yē gá á yèè
 firstly 3Pl Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv
 [kú túùŋ gá [kù júólì] nī],
 [Dem Past be.Cop [Dem young.man] it.is],

A: ‘In the old days they would say, this one was the young man of that one (=young woman), ...’

(03:08) A [kú túùŋ gá [kù kũ-ŋũd̀ⁿ] nī],
 [Dem Past be.Cop [Dem whatchamacallit] it.is],
 [ŋũd̀n sáàⁿ] yè gá à xá—
 [DemDef time] 3Pl Ipfv 3Sg en[trust.Ipfv]—

A: ‘... and this one was the whatchamacallit of that one. Then they would en[trust] her—’

[kũ-ŋũd̀ⁿ ‘whatchamacallit’; cut off from xálifáà ‘entrust.Ipfv’]

(03:10) A yè =é nà sò ŋónómín-tò,
 if 3Pl if.Pfv go.Pfv dance(n)-place,
 [ā r̀d̀d̀] gá j̀ògá= [à fáà],
 [3Sg Foc] Ipfv follow.Ipfv [3Sg by],

A: ‘When they went to the dancing ground, it was he [focus] who followed (=accompanied) her.’

[place nominal with -tò, §4.2.1.8; j̀ògá (here [postL] Ipfv j̀ògá)]

(03:13) A yè =é nà só [gèr̀è máàŋ f̀ìèⁿ],
 if 3Pl if.Pfv go.Pfv [place Rel all],
 [ā r̀d̀d̀] gá j̀ògá= [à fáà],
 [3Sg Foc] Ipfv follow.Ipfv [3Sg by],

A: ‘Wherever they went, it was he [focus] who followed (=accompanied) her.’

(03:16) A [ŋũd̀n sáàⁿ] à gá à kór̀d̀s̀f̀i,
 [DemDef time] 3Sg Ipfv 3Sg watch.over.Ipfv,
 á= à fáàmúⁿ nà,
 2Sg 3Sg understand.Pfv Q,

A: ‘So then he would watch over her. Did you-Sg understand it?’

(03:19) A [ŋũðn sáàⁿ] yá= à ná= à kórðsí [míní-míní-tõ],
 [DemDef time] if 3Sg if.Pfv 3Sg watch.over.Pfv [dance(n)-place],
 [yē kù-ŋúðⁿ [fèŋè níŋĩ]]
 [3Pl do.whatchamacallit?.Ipfv [whatchamacallit? inside]]
 A: ‘Then when he watched over her at the dancing ground, they would (do)
 whatchamacallit, in whatchamacallit.’
 [kũ-ŋúðⁿ as verb ‘do whatchamacallit?’ combined with noun féŋé ‘whatchamacallit’
 < Bambara]

(03:23) A [àlé= =è gá bì ìn sàà]
 [even 3Pl Ipfv Fut Repl lie.down.Pfv]
 [yé ñ gá bà= á sè]
 [if 1Sg Ipfv Fut 3Sg say.Pfv]
 A: ‘Even if they are going to lie down (=spend the night), if I will (=may) say it, ...’
 [< àli yé/]

(03:25) A [wáxádí-yè xèlè] [à dí [wàxàdù lààⁿ nĩ]—
 [time-Pl pass.Pfv] [3Sg not.be.Cop [time distant] it.is]—
 [ā dī xélèè [jùùŋ kíèⁿ-fèndèèŋ] [jùùŋ síláámbe-kìèrmà]]
 [3Sg IpfvNeg pass.Ipfv [year hundred-two] [year Muslim-hundred]]
 A: ‘... the times have passed. It isn’t a (very) far-off time. It doesn’t exceed two
 hundred years (or) one hundred years.’
 [kíèⁿ-fèndèèⁿ and síláámbe-kìèrmà, §/4.6.1.5]

(03:29) A [ā dī xélèè [à gā]],
 [3Sg IpfvNeg pass.Ipfv [3Sg Dat]],
 múð-yè nódŋ-gù jêⁿ [[á xòò] gā],
 person-Pl village-Def abandon.Pfv [[3Sg talk(n)] Dat],
 A: ‘It (=distance in time) doesn’t exceed it. (Some) people have left the village on
 account of it.’
 [‘(sur)pass’ with dative gā in comparatives, §12.1.1.1; xóó gā, §8.3.2]

(03:31) A [àlí ñièn-sààntè] yè dí bè [nódŋ-g= ì],
 [even tomorrow] 3Pl PfvNeg come.Pfv [village-Def Loc],
 yè= é gí yá— [àli yá= àŋ gá bì túláá-yà]
 (hesitation) [even if 2Sg Ipfv Fut short-Inch.Pfv]
 A: ‘Even tomorrow (=ever since then) they haven’t come (back) to the village. Even
 if you-Sg (=young man) got close (to the young woman), ...’
 [ñièn-sààntè, §8.4.5.1]

(03:33) A káw gá màá [sààndèèŋ kóòⁿ] [sààndèèm pèndèèⁿ]
 certain.ones Ipfv be.able.Ipfv [pants one] [pants two]
 [sààn-dèèŋ jíyò] [yē gà [á fìèⁿ] sòró-sòróò [bólò xúmà]],
 [pants three] [3Pl Ipfv [3Sg all] Iter-pull.on.Ipfv [Recip on]],
 A: ‘Some (young men) could (pull on) one, two, three pairs of pants, they would
 keep pulling them (=pants) on, one on top of the other.’
*[i.e. the young male guide would be heavily clothed while spending the night with the
 young woman; clause restarted (yē gà á ...) after heavy object NP; sáándééⁿ ‘pants,
 shorts’; sórō]*

(03:38) A [ŋūòñ sáàⁿ] [[múò máàⁿ] nà á bààⁿyìⁿ],
 [DemDef time] [[person Rel] if.Pfv 3Sg ruin.Pfv],
 fánááⁿ yē gà á yèè→ sómókóró-jùòñ sómókóró-jùòⁿ,
 firstly 3Pl Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv bastard-child bastard-child,
 A: ‘Then, the person who has spoiled it (=custom), in the old days, they would call
 it a bastard child.’
*[i.e. if the young male guide impregnated the young woman who then gave birth to a
 child out of wedlock]*

(03:42) A [à tìn] ò ò sómókóró-jùòⁿ nī]
 [3Sg meaning] not.be.Cop bastard-child it.is]
 [yē gà á yèè [tííná-xúmá]-jùòⁿ nóò]
 [3Pl Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv [garbage.pile-on]-child Foc]
 A: ‘Its meaning (=the correct word) isn’t bastard child, they call it “garbage-child”
 [focus].’
*[sómókóró-jùòⁿ specifically denotes a child born out of wedlock to a married woman,
 which isn’t precisely correct in the present context; tīíná]*

(03:45) A [fánááⁿ yē tūùŋ gà yé xèéñî ñjèñú],
 [firstly 3Pl Past Ipfv 3Pl call.Ipfv thus.Def],
 [lāá-[[máá-gúlá]-yà] yē wō sómókóró-jùòⁿ],
 [mouth-[[rapid]-Abstr] 3Pl said bastard-child],
 A: ‘In the old days they used to call them thus. Speaking rapidly (=loosely) they
 say bastard child.’
[máá-gúlá-yà ‘speed’ and related forms, §4.5.1.3.1]

(03:48) A á= à xáy rà, ā wō [ŋūòñ sáàⁿ],
 2Sg 3Sg see.Pfv Q, 3Sg said [DemDef time],
 fánááⁿ [[ŋúó-ní xàlámbeé-yà tábìyá] gá ñjèñú]
 firstly [[DemDef-Link child-Abstr system] be.Loc thus.Def]
 A: ‘You-Sg see? He said, at that time, that childhood practice was thus.’
[lit. “did you see it?”; tábìyá ‘system, way of doing things’]

(03:53) A [ŋũðn sáàⁿ] yè =é nà= á lèè [ŋũðⁿ mā],
 [DemDef time] if 3Pl if.Pfv 3Sg pick.up.Pfv [DemDef against],
 [yé =è ná lò [kóyn-lòy níŋĩ],
 [if 3Pl if.Pfv enter.Pfv [cision inside],

A: ‘Then, if they picked up (=started) from that point on, when they entered in (=underwent) cision, ...’

[mā ‘from (time)’, §8.2.7.2]

(03:57) A àywà yè= é nà [[kóyn-lòy— wààdù] mā],
 well if 3Pl if.Pfv [[cision— time] against],
 [ŋũðn sáàⁿ] yè =é gà bà= á [jàn-sígé]-nì,
 [DemDef time] if 3Pl Ipfv Fut 3Sg [marry]-Caus.Pfv,

A: ‘... well, from the time they (underwent) cision, at (=from) that time if they (=parents) would have her get married,’

[a verb like ‘enter’ seems to be missing after the interruption at kóyn-lòy unless the latter is treated here as a verb; wáádũ]

(04:00) A yá= à =á ŋõnðð xéení bíè fànáàⁿ,
 if 3Sg Ipfv DemDef.Foc call.Ipfv come.Ipfv firstly,
 àywà [kú túù fílààná] [[kú túù] gá bì ján-sìgè],
 well [Dem owner so-and-so] [[Dem owner] Ipfv Fut get.married.Pfv],

A: ‘When they would call that one (=her young male guide) to come (and tell him:) “well, So-and-so (vocative)! So-and-so (=the young woman) will get married.’

[kú túù and (Arabic) fílààná are interchangeable ‘so-and-so’ expressions, i.e. variables over personal names]

(04:04) A [ŋũðn sáàⁿ] [yè =é nà= á lèè]
 [DemDef time] [if 3Pl if.Pfv 3Sg pick.up.Pfv]
 [yé =é nà= á là [xàl gā]],
 [if 3Pl if.Pfv 3Sg give.Pfv [man Dat]],

A: ‘Then, when they took her, (and) when they gave her to a man, ...’

(04:06) A [ŋũðn sáàⁿ] yè =é nà bàára
 [DemDef time] if 3Pl if.Pfv happen.Pfv
 [à =á gõ— xàlàmbèèⁿ ní]ìèⁿ],
 [3Sg be.Loc there.Def— child it.is all],

A: ‘... then, if they happened to find that she was a child (=a virgin), ...’

[gõ can be edited out to leave à gá xàlàmbèè nī ; an alternative phrasing is à gá [[iⁿ xàlàmbéé-nà] níŋĩ] ‘she was in her childhood’;]íéⁿ ‘all’ as right-edge marker in conditional antecedents, §16.1.2]

(04:09) A [ŋũðn sáàⁿ] [yè gá bà= [[á ròð] tóð] xēⁿ]
 [DemDef time] [3Pl Ipfv Fut [[3Sg Foc] name(n)] call.Pfv]
 [yè gá [à tóð] xèè^{nī}],
 [3Pl Ipfv [3Sg name] call.Ipfv],

A: ‘... then they would call out her name (=sing her praises). They would call out her name.’

[logically should be tóð ‘name’, but when phrased with ‘call’ (denoting the griots’ praise-naming) this noun is replaced by tóð ‘foot’]

(04:12) A [ŋũðn sáàⁿ], [á= =à yéé-nà [iŋ gá á yēē]],
 [DemDef time], [2Sg Ipfv put.Antip-Ppl [2Sg Ipfv 3Sg say.Ipfv]],
 kójò→, [yē gá á yèè]
 textile, [3Pl Ipfv 3Sg say.Pfv]

A: ‘Then, it was as though, *kojo*, they call it.’

[lit. “you-Sg put [Logo says it]” meaning ‘it looks like...’ or ‘it’s as though’, cf. French on dirait que ...; < xày à gá]

(04:16) A [kójò tóð] xà= à =á bàý [[ñ nómāā],
 [fabric name] Prsntv 3Sg Ipfv exit.Ipfv [[1Sg out.from],
 [ŋũðn sáàⁿ] yá= à túùⁿ nà ján-sìgè ÿìèⁿ,
 [DemDef time] if 3Sg Past if.Pfv get.married all,

A: ‘Look I am (almost) forgetting the name of *kojo*. At that time, when they used to get married, ...’

[kójò is a fabric presented by the bride’s family to the young man who had guided the young woman; “X exit from [Y’s interior]” means ‘Y forget X’; nómāā, §8.2.4.4]

(04:20) A [ŋúó-ní kòjò-gù] túùŋ gá fódò [[jàn-sìgè]-jùù-gù fáà],
 [DemDef-Link fabric-Def] Past Ipfv go.Ipfv [[marriage]-garment-Def by],
 [ŋúó-ní [jàn-sìgè]-jùù] túùⁿ—,
 [DefDef-Link [marriage]-garment] Past—,

A: ‘... that *kojo* used to go with (=be included in) the marriage clothing. That marriage clothing used to—’

[the fabric is part of the set of garments presented to the bride by the bridegroom]

(04:23) A yà= á bààrà [kú túùŋ gá [kù júól] nī]
 if 3Sg happen.Pfv [Dem Past be.Cop [Dem young.man] it.is]
 yà= á bààrà [[fó níŋáá] nī,
 if 3Sg happen.Pfv [[thing bad] it.is],

A: ‘If he happened to be her young man, if it happened to be a bad thing, ...’

(04:26) A [ɲúó-ní [kòjò-yà]-jùù] [DemDef-Link [textile-Abstr]-garment]
 [[nà-w [yè ká-w]] túùŋ gá ɲòròs lēē]
 [[mother-Def.& [and father-Def]] Past Ipfv DemDef pick.up.Ipfv]
 A: ‘... that fabric, the mother and father (of the bride) would take that (*kojo*) ...’
 [< nàŋ-gú [yè ká-gù]/

(04:28) A yā= à= á lāā— yē gā á lāā—
 3Pl Ipfv 3Sg give.Ipfv—, 3Pl Ipfv 3Sg give.Ipfv—
 [ā= à xálifá-nà [máàⁿ má] gù]
 [3Sg be.Loc entrust-Ppl [Rel against] Def]
 A: ‘... (and) they (=bride’s parents) would give it (*kojo*)— They would give it—.
 The one (=young man) to whom she was (=had been) entrusted, ...’
 [relativization on complement of postposition, §14.2.4; definite morpheme at end of
 relative clause, §14.1.2]

(04:30) A yā= à= =á làá [ɲòrò gā],
 3Pl Ipfv 3Sg give.Ipfv [DemDef Dat],
 ɲkàà wáy-wáy-gì yà= á bààⁿyìⁿ fièw,
 but nowadays 3Pl 3Sg ruin.Pfv totally,
 A: ‘... they would give it (*kojo*) to that one (=young man). But nowadays they have
 completely ruined it.’
 [fièw, §6.3.2.5]

(04:34) A ɔⁿhón séwè-gù túùŋ gá ɲīēⁿōō,
 uh.huh matter-Def Past be.Loc thus.Def,
 [yá= á ðì ɲūòⁿ nī] [kóyn-lòy]-gù gá gòbí-nà],
 [if 3Sg not.be.Cop DemDef it.is] [cision]-Def be.Loc flip-Ppl],
 A: ‘Uh-huh. That [focus] is how the matter (=custom) used to be. By contrast,
 (nowadays) cision is changed.’
 [gá ɲīēⁿōō, §4.4.2.2.2]

(04:38) A [ɲúó-ní jùòŋò-gù tòmò] [á tòmà=] á gòbí-nà, àⁿháⁿ
 [DemDef-Link marriage-Def too] [3Sg too] be.Loc flip-Ppl, uh.huh
 S bon, [áŋ xày] [áⁿ [fóⁿ máàn] sè gù],
 okay, [2Sg Prsntv] [2Sg [thing Rel] say.Pfv Def],
 A: ‘That (system of) marriage too, it too has changed. Uh-huh.’
 S: ‘Okay, the thing that you-Sg have said here, ...’
 [presentative with attached perfective clause, §4.4.3.3]

(04:42) S ɲũ̀ðŋ gá yēē mais, ē→
 DemDef be.Loc therein but, uh
 bí jámàá lò [sà̀nìŋ-jìì gà] bó̀lēē,
 Seq crowd give.Pfv [prayer-water Dat] together,
 S: ‘... that (=what you said) is therein. But, uh, to circumcise a large group
 together,’
 [jámāā (/HLH/)]

(04:48) S [mú̀dò síláám̀bè-kìèrmá] wà̀là [mú̀dò léwé-én-tà̀n]
 [person Muslim-hundred.&] or [person fifty]
 [[ā xà̀lú] [yè yáá̀lù-yè]] níŋī,
 [[3Sg man] [and woman-Pl]] inside,
 S: ‘(say) one hundred people or fifty people, including its men and women.’
 [‘hundred’, §4.6.1.5; ‘fifty’, §4.6.1.4; ‘men and women’ marks plural only on ‘women’
 to avoid adjacent ye syllables]

(04:51) S fánááⁿ ɲũ̀ðn twⁿá = = á gō
 firstly DemDef Past be.Loc there.Def
 A ɲũ̀ðn twⁿá = = á gō
 DemDef Past be.Loc there.Def
 S: ‘In the old days, that was there.’
 A: ‘That was there.’
 [for tú̀ùŋ gá gō]

(04:53) S mais wáy [á lò̀d] ìŋ jêŋ gù,
 but today [3Sg mouth] Refl abandon.Pfv Def,
 est-ce que [xó̀ró-yà rò̀d] dí bà = [á tī̀n]
 Q [hard-Abstr Foc] PfvNeg come.Pfv [3Sg under]
 S: ‘But the fact that today (=nowadays) it has stopped, is it not hardship (=poverty)
 [focus] that brought it (about)?’
 [ló̀ó ‘mouth’ in collocation, §9.5.1; clause-final gù in factive clause, §17.3.1]

(04:56) A bon [yá = àⁿ nà ní tèlè]
 okay [if 2Sg if.Pfv 1Sg ask.Pfv]
 [ŋ gá yèè [[xó̀ró-yà tòm̀d] bà = [á tī̀n]],
 [1Sg Ipfv say.Ipfv [[hard-Abstr too] come.Pfv [3Sg under]],
 A: ‘Okay, if you-Sg ask me, I (would) say that hardship too brought it.’

(04:59) A [xó̀ró-yà tòm̀d] bà = [á tī̀n] , *parce que*
 [hard-Abstr too] come.Pfv [3Sg under], because
 à = á bàárāā, fáná = [ā tú̀ùŋ gá ìⁿ wáléè]
 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv, firstly [3Sg Past Ipfv Refl do.Ipfv]
 A: ‘Hardship too brought it. Because, it happened that in the old days it was done.’

(05:04) A wáy-wáy-gì à =á bààràà [múò gà [múò-yé nāāⁿ],
 nowadays 3Sg Ipfv happen.Ipfv [person 3be.Loc [person-Pl between]],
 fánááⁿ [ā dépense] túùn dí kōōⁿ,
 firstly [3Sg expense] Past IpfvNeg be.much.Stat,
 A: ‘Nowadays, it happens that someone among the people—. In the old days its
 expense was not great.’
 [pronounced [dépààⁿsí], synonym músààxá ‘expense’]

(05:07) A wáy dépense-gù kùyé-yà, [ŋūòñ tòmò]—
 today expense-Def much-Inch.Pfv, (hesitation)
 [ŋūòñ tòmò] bè [séwè-giè tííⁿ],
 [DemDef too] come.Pfv [matter-Pl under],
 A: ‘Today (=nowadays) the expense has increased. That too has brought some
 issues.’
 [kúyé-yà inchoative ‘become much/many, grow’, §9.4.4, cf. modifying adjective kíérē
 or kúyé, stative predicate kōōⁿ]

(05:13) A [yá= á dī ŋūòⁿ nī] fànáàⁿ
 [if 3Sg not.be.Cop DemDef it.is] firstly
 [jámáá yè jámāā], [máàⁿ-yà= =á [wàxàdì kóòⁿ] níŋ gù]
 [crowd and crowd], [Rel-Pl be.Cop [time one] it.is Def]
 A: ‘By contrast, in the old days, crowds and crowds (=by large groups), those who
 were of the same time (=age group), ...’

(05:17) A [yē rà=] =á lòò bóléē,
 [3Pl Foc] Ipfv enter.Ipfv together,
 [ŋūòñ sààⁿ] ŋūòⁿ-yè lóólòⁿ-yè,
 [DemDef time] DemDef-Pl younger.sib-Pl,
 A: ‘... they [focus] would enter (=undergo circumcision) together. Then (later),
 their younger brothers, ...’
 [< yē rōò gá]

(05:20) A ŋūòⁿ-yà= =á lòò bóléē, [àlí ñièn-sààntè],
 DemDef-Pl Ipfv enter.Ipfv together, [until tomorrow],
 [xáy nóòŋ kà-rèè] gá gō,
 [1PlIn village certain-Pl] be.Loc there.Def,
 A: ‘... those ones would enter together. Until tomorrow (=even now), there are
 some villages of ours (inclusive), ...’

(05:24) A yà = áⁿ nà só [ɲūðⁿ-yè níɲī],
 if 2Sg if.Pfv go.Pfv [DemDef-Pl inside],
 yà = áⁿ nà = á yè [kù túù fílààná],
 if 2Sg if.Pfv 3Sg say.Pfv [Dem owner so-and-so],
 A: ‘... if you-Sg go into those ones (=villages), (and) if you-Sg call (someone) So-and-So, ...’

(05:27) A yè gé = è [bólò tèt] t̂ⁿ,
 3Pl Ipfv 3Pl [Recip Dat] elder.sib
 àlà = á dì síɲè [kū-ɲūðⁿ mā],
 even 3Sg PfvNeg arrive.Pfv [whatchamacallit? against],
 A: ‘... they call each other elder brother. Even if it hasn’t reached whatchamacallit?, ...’

(05:30) A [yá = àⁿ nà sò jáá-xòlò] [à = á ɲīèⁿ],
 [if 2Sg if.Pfv go.Pfv Diakouri] [3Sg be.Loc thus.Def],
 [yá = àⁿ nà sò tóy] [àlí ɲién-sààntè]
 [if 2Sg if.Pfv go.Pfv Tiali] [even tomorrow]
 A: ‘... if you-Sg go to Diakouri (village), it is thus. If you-Sg to to Tiali (village), even tomorrow ...’
 [ɲīèⁿ truncated variant of ɲīèⁿ nāⁿ ‘thus.Def’]

(05:33) A [ɲúó-ní lààndá-giè] gè = [é fāⁿ]
 [DemDef-Link custom-Pl] be.Loc [3Pl chez]
 [ɲūðⁿ-yè húnù] dí [yè tíɲáá-gù] bààⁿyìⁿ yóròó-gù,
 [DemDef-Pl Top] PfvNeg [ReflPl possession-Def] ruin.Pfv self-Def,
 A: ‘... those customs are at their place. Those (villages) have certainly not ruined theirs (=customs).’
 [lààndá ; fāⁿ ‘chez’, §8.2.4.6; yóròó as emphatic, §18.2]

(05:36) A àli bóló-kìèɲè dì [ɲūðⁿ níɲī],
 even Refl-debate not.be.Loc [DemDef inside],
 [kwá = á [kù t̂ⁿ] nī]
 [Dem be.Cop [Dem elder.sib] it.is]
 [kwá = á [kù t̂ⁿ] nī]
 [Dem be.Cop [Dem elder.sib] it.is]
 A: ‘There is not even a contradiction in that. This one is the elder brother of that one, (and) this one is the elder brother of that one.’
 [< kú gá ; deictic demonstrative kú repeated for varying referents]

- (05:39) A [ŋũðn sááⁿ], *catégorie-catégorie*,
 [DemDef time], Iter-category,
 [yē rà=] = á lòò bólèè [kóyn-lòy níŋĩĩ],
 [3Pl Foc] Ipfv enter.Ipfv together [cision inside],
 A: ‘Then by age classes (in turn), they [focus] undergo circumcision together.’
- (05:43) A ðⁿhóⁿ, [ŋũðm bàárà fànààⁿ, ā gù yááⁿxàrá (??)
 uh.huh, [DemDef happen.Pfv firstly, (unintelligible),
 à ná lò [kóyn-lòy níŋĩĩ],
 3Sg if.Pfv enter.Pfv [cision inside],
 A: ‘Uh-huh. In the old days it happened If he underwent circumcision, ...’
- (05:48) A ā =à yóò kúnùⁿ [ŋũðⁿ níŋĩĩ]
 3Sg Ipfv go.Ipfv war [DemDef inside]
 S kyá= = á bì f̄-ńúðn sè [[[ján-sìgè]-gù tèmè] níŋĩĩ]
 1PlIn Ipfv Fut thing-Dimin say.Pfv [[[marriage]-Def too] inside]
 A: ‘He would go to war at that point.’
 S: ‘We (inclusive) will also say a little about marriage as well.’
[yóò variant of jóò ‘go.Ipfv’; f̄ⁿ-ńúðⁿ, §6.4.2.5; beginning here, the sometimes low-volume discussion between A and S ranges from clearly or barely audible (transcribed) to inaudible (not transcribed)]
- (05:52) S kyá= á bì [ìn làá] lò
 1PlIn Ipfv Fut [Refl mouth] put.in.Pfv
 [[júóŋè-gù tèmè] níŋĩĩ]
 [[marriage-Def too] inside]
 S: ‘We will put our mouth in (=discuss) marriage also.’
[làā ‘mouth’]
- (05:56) A ñ wā= [ā gà jóò lò [júóŋè-gù níŋĩĩ]]
 1Sg said [3Sg Ipfv go.Ipfv enter.Pfv [marriage-Def inside]]
parce que, yē gà bì lò [júóŋè-gù níŋĩĩ],
 because, 3Pl Ipfv Fut enter.Pfv [marriage-Def inside],
 A: ‘I said, it (=recording) goes into marriage. Because, they would enter into marriage.’
[< ñ wō]
- (06:01) A *parce que*, [yè ná bày [kóyn-lòy níŋĩĩ] lámà t̀n]
 because, [3Pl if.Pfv exit.Pfv [cision inside] only only]
 [yā= à jóò lò [ján-sìgè níŋĩĩ]],
 [3Pl Ipfv go.Ipfv enter.Pfv [marriage inside]],
 A: ‘Because, once they had been cised, they would go and enter into marriage.’
[lámà t̀n, §17.2.2.2]

(06:04) A [ɲɔ̄rɔ̄ð ò láá] ɲ wà= á—
 [DemDef Purp] 1Sg said 3Sg—
 [ká tú= òn sè [ɲũðⁿ níɲĩĩ]]
 [a.certain Past Refl be.said.Pfv [DemDef inside]]
 A: ‘For that reason I said that it—. Something had (already) been said in (=about) that.’
 [túũⁿ ; i.e. marriage as a follow-up to circumcision has already been mentioned above, e.g. @ 03:57]

(06:07) A ɲkàà ā= =à ʃòò lò [[júóɲð-gú ròð] níɲĩĩ],
 but 3Sg Ipfv go.Ipfv enter.Pfv [[marriage-Def Foc] inside],
 ðⁿhóⁿ, ɲɔ̄rɔ̄ð gá→, [ā kũũⁿ] níɲ quoi, ðⁿhóⁿ
 uh-huh, DemDef be, [3Sg cause] it.is Ø, uh.huh
 A: ‘But it (=discussion) goes into marriage [focus]. Uh-huh. That is its cause.’

(06:13) S àywà, òlá àlá kì lòð-nì [xééré ò],
 well, hopefully God 1PlIn enter-Caus.Pfv [well.being Loc],
 [ā fààmù-m-bèènáá màyⁿ]
 [3Sg understand.VblN-Link-manner good]
 S: ‘Well, may God lead us (inclusive) into well-being! A good way of understanding it, ...’
 [‘may God ...’, §10.4.3.1.1; xééré ; béènáá ‘way’ as compound final, §9.3.1.2]

(06:16) òlá àlá ɲínà á ʃwàá-nì [kì tē],
 hopefully God Sbjn 3Sg grant.Pfv [1PlIn Dat],
 àywà [yè xáy] [yé bè [[xáy húnùn] tèle]],
 well [3Pl Prsntv] [3Pl come.Pfv [[1PlIn Top] ask.Pfv]],
 S: ‘... may God grant it to us (inclusive)! Well, here they have come to ask us (inclusive).’
 [ɲínà, §10.4.3.1.1; ʃwàá-nì, used with ‘God’ as subject; topic húnùn⁽ⁿ⁾ in object NP]

(06:20) S [xáy húnùn] dá= à tóò
 [1PlIn Top] IpfvNeg 3Sg know.Ipfv
 [[xáy tèle-kũ] gá [fðⁿ máàⁿ] ní],
 [[1PlIn ask.VblN-cause] be.Cop [thing Rel] it.is],
 A: ‘We (inclusive) don’t know it, the thing that is the reason of our being asked.’

(06:23) S [xáy húnùn] dá= à tóò,
 [1PlIn Top] IpfvNeg 3Sg know.Ipfv,
 [xáy fáy-nà gú ròð] níɲĩĩ,
 [1PlIn sit-Ppf Def Foc] inside,
 S: ‘We (inclusive) don’t know. Among us (inclusive) being seated [focus].’

(06:25) S [yē bà= à yáà]
 [3Pl come.PPfv 3Sg put.Pfv]
 [yē wō] [xáy nà jíémù]
 [3Pl said [1PlIn Sbjn speak.Pfv]
 S: ‘They came and proposed it, they asked us (inclusive) to speak.’

(06:26) S àywà [kí xày] [kí jíémù],
 well [1PlIn Prsntv] [1PlIn speak.Pfv],
 àywà jíémù-gù, [jíémù-gù xòòró] y] xèèré,
 well talk(n)-Def, [talk(n)-Def back] Loc&] well.being.&,
 S: ‘Well, here we have spoken. Well, the talk, after the talk (hopefully) well-being.’
[cf. [jíémù-gù xóòrò] y ‘after the talk’, xéérē ‘well-being’; pseudo-conjunction with paired LH-toned forms, §7.1.13]

(06:32) S ilá àlà á là [kì gā],
 hopefully God 3Sg give.Pfv [1PlIn Dat],
 xáy gá xèèré mánàá yēē
 1PlIn Ipfv well.being look.for.Ipfv therein
 S: ‘May God give it to us! We (inclusive) seek well-being therein.’

(06:35) A áámínà= áámínà
 amen! amen!
 S [yà= á bàárà [tóréeⁿ nóò] gá yēē]
 [if 3Sg happen.Pfv [annoyance Foc] be.Loc therein]
 A: ‘Amen! Amen!’
 S: ‘If it happened that there is anything annoying (=problematic) [focus] therein, ...’
[tóréeⁿ; starting around here, speaker A repeats much of what S says in a low, almost unintelligible voice (not transcribed)]

(06:36) A [ilá àlà ñínà á tàbí]
 [hopefully God Sbjn 3Sg push.Pfv]
 [ā ñínà swà= [á tīⁿ] [gèrè níñī]]
 [3Sg Sbjn go.Pfv [3Sg under] [place inside]]
 S: ‘May God push it away, may He take it to a place, ...’
[tábi ; sò á tīⁿ]

(06:38) S àlí [[àlá [yé [ìṅ xéénè-è]]] tòó]
 until [[God.& [and [Refl messenger-Def]]] name]
 dì ìn séè [gèrè máàⁿ],
 IpfvNeg Refl say.Ipfv [place Rel],
 S: ‘... all the way (to) a place (where) the name(s) of God and His Prophet are not said.’

[conjoined NP as possessor of ‘name’; reflexive possessor in right conjunct, §7.1.7]

(06:40) S ṅkàà kóṅṅ gá yēē, yè =é nà sô,
 but one be.Loc therein, if 3Pl if.Pfv go.Pfv,
 [xáy [fààwò xòló kóṅṅ]] gá gō,
 [1PlIn [pond big one]] be.Loc there.Def,
 S: ‘But there is one (thing) therein. When they go, there is one big pond of ours (inclusive).’

[fààwò ‘pond’, fààwó xòló ‘big pond’, here as possessum]

(06:44) S [kyá= =á mí-nà [á [nàà-làà]-[[xòò-nà]-nì]] wàlè]
 [1PlIn be.Loc accustomed-Ppl [3Sg [face]-[[white]-Caus.VbIN]] do.Pfv]
 yé kì gá bà= á fùlè,
 if 1PlIn Ipfv Fut 3Sg fish(v).Pfv,
 S: ‘We have a custom of holding its festivity. When we are going to fish it (=pond), ...’

[mí-nà ‘accustomed’, isolated but here parsed as a participle, §15.1.2.2; “face-whitening” = ‘festivity, celebration (of a place)’]

(06:47) S yé ṅūṅṅ gá kìèṅṅ nī,
 if DemDef be.Cop K it.is,
 [fɔⁿ máàⁿ] sólòⁿ [[ṅ ṅàxèlè] ṽ] wáy,
 [thing Rel] descend.Pfv [1Sg attention] Loc] today,
 S: ‘If that is Kiengou (name of pond). The thing that has come (down) to my mind today,’

[this pond is the site of an annual community one-day fishfest; sólòⁿ ‘descend’, variant of jólòⁿ; ṅàxèlè variant of háxèlè ‘attention’]

(06:53) S yè =é nà sô, yè =é nà só [à tónò],
 if 3Pl if.Pfv go.Pfv, if 3Pl if.Pfv go.Pfv [3Sg look.at.Pfv],
 yē nà [xáy nìmbòró-yè] lèè,
 3Pl Sbjn [1PlIn number-Pl] take.Pfv,
 S: ‘If they go, if they go and look at it, let them take our (telephone) number.’

(06:59) S yà= [á wàxàdú] nà síjè,
 if [3Sg time] if.Pfv arrive.Pfv,
 kyá= á màà yé xèéniī,
 1PlIn Ipfv be.able.Ipfv 3Pl call.Ipfv,
 S: ‘When its (=festivity’s) time has arrived, we can call them.’
 [wáxádū]

(07:01) S yà= á bààrà
 if 3Sg happen.Pfv
 [yà= á màà [biè [kì fáà] bō]],
 [3Pl Ipfv be.able.Ipfv [come.Ipfv [1PlIn by] here]],
 S: ‘If it happens that they can come to us (=inclusive) here,’

(07:04) S [kyá= =á]óò]
 [1PlIn Ipfv go.Ipfv]
 [kyá= =á yóò] [kì tá= [à xúmà]]
 [1PlIn Ipfv go.Ipfv] [1PlIn stop.Pfv [3Sg on]]
 S: ‘We (will) go, we (will) go and stop on it (=pond).’
 [táà]

(07:06) A [ā rōò] tágà-máyⁿ
 [3Sg Foc] pretty
 S yē =è ná= à xáy,
 if 3Pl if.Pfv 3Sg see.Pfv,
 A: ‘It [focus] is pretty.’
 S: ‘If they see it, ...’

(07:08) S [yē tēmè] fáà =á bí [fòⁿ máàⁿ] wàlè [xáy té] yēē],
 [3Pl also] as Ipfv Fut [thing Rel] do.Pfv [1PlIn Dat] therein],
 yē wà= á wàlè [xáy tē],
 3Pl Fut 3Sg do.Pfv [1PlIn Dat],
 S: ‘The thing that they for their part plan to do for us (inclusive) therein, they will do it for us.’
 [post-subject fáà with sequential VP, §15.2.17; < yē gù á]

(07:12) S yē =è ná hìni-yà [bá= à sááyì]
 if 3Pl if.Pfv be.able-Inch.Pfv [Seq 3Sg dig.Pfv]
 [bá= à kúúlá-nì [xáy tē]],
 [Seq 3Sg deep-Caus.Pfv [1PlIn Dat]],
 S: ‘If they can manage to dig (=dredge) it, to deepen it for us.’

(07:15) S [ā rṑ] gà [xáy [fááwó xòlól]] nī,
 [3Sg Foc] be.Cop [1PIIn [pond big]] it.is,
 [ā rṑ] gà [xáy láámá-fààwò] ní,
 [3Sg Foc] be.Cop [1PIIn the.bush-pond] it.is,

S: ‘It [focus] is our (inclusive) big(gest) pond. It [focus] is our bush pond.’

[i.e. out in the bush, not next to the village]

(07:18) S [ā rṑ] gá [kì [[nàà-làà]- [[xòò-nà]-nì]] fááwò] nī,
 [3Sg Foc] be.Cop [1PIIn [face]- [[white]-Caus.VblN]] pond] it.is,
 àywà= [á rṑ] gà [[jáá-ṅà tèmè]ìèⁿ] nùṅṅ] xúmà],
 well [3Sg Foc] be.Loc [[Dia-Gen also all] soul] on],

S: ‘It [focus] is our festival pond. Well, it [focus] is on the soul of (=is revered by) every resident of Dia (village)’.

[long compound ‘festival pond’, §5.1 (i.e. where the fishfest is held); gentilic -ṅá, §4.2.4; nùṅṅⁿ ‘soul, vital spirit’; tèmé can precede or follow]ìèⁿ]

(07:24) S jíí ná lò [[béénàà máàṅ]ìèⁿ] níṅṅī],
 water if.Pfv enter.Pfv [[manner Rel all] inside],
 jáá-ṅà gú xèni [jíí síṅè kìèṅù nà]
 Dia-Gent Fut call.Antip.Pfv [water arrive.Pfv K Q]

S: ‘(If there is) any situation in which water enters, Dia people will call (to ask), “has water arrived at Kiengou (pond)?”’

[floodwaters from the Niger R. reach Kiengou pond by September except in drought years; béénāā ; < gú xèni, with xèni ‘call, make a call’ (antipassive), §9.3.5]

(07:27) A jíí síṅè kìèṅùⁿ nà, [yé jìì ò síṅè gō]
 water arrive.Pfv K Q, [if water PfvNeg arrive.Pfv there.Def]
 ṅū̀ḡ gá á xààyî [jìì ò síṅè bō]
 DemDef Ipfv 3Sg show.Ipfv [water PfvNeg arrive.Pfv here]

A: ‘“Has water arrived at Kiemou?” If water hasn’t arrived there, that indicates (=implies) that water has not arrived here (in Dia).’

(07:31) S wála
 voilà!

A némèⁿ-némèⁿ, yé jìì ò síṅè—
 entirely, if water PfvNeg arrive.Pfv—

S: ‘There it is!’

A: ‘Absolutely. If water hasn’t arrived—’

[iterated from némēēⁿ ‘a lot’]

(07:00) S yé kyà= á bì só gōⁿ fùlè
 if 1PlIn Ipfv Fut go.Pfv there.Def fish(v).Pfv

A jíí síṅè gōⁿ nà
 water arrive.Pfv there.Def Q

S: 'If we (inclusive) will go there to fish.'

A: 'Has water arrived there?'

[speakers S and A are overlapping here]

(07:35) S júrùù yē wō [ā síṅè],
 this.year 3Pl said [3Sg arrive.Pfv],
 ṅkàà á ṅà— [fááwò ṅà] =à tésèé-nà,
 but 3Sg Top— [pond QTop] be.Loc flat-Ppl,

S: 'This year they said it has arrived, but it—, the pond is flat.'

[as sediment has increasingly filled the pond bed]

(07:38) A ā =à tésèé-nà, [jíí-gú xāy], [ā síṅè gō],
 3Sg be.Loc flat-Ppl, [water-Def Prsntv], [3Sg arrive.Pfv there.Def],
 ṅkàà à dí kōō
 but 3Sg IpfvNeg be.much

A: 'It is flat. Look, the water has arrived there, but it isn't much.'

(07:43) A [yé jì— à ná xòlò-yà gōⁿ]ìèⁿ],
 [if water— 3Sg if.Pfv big-Inch.Pfv there.Def all],
 à =á kòrî [[múò mààṅ]ìèⁿ-táá] jì] mǎ,
 3Sg Ipfv be.added.Ipfv [[1PlEx over.by-side] water] against],

A: 'If water—, if it becomes abundant (=fills up) there, it adds to (=complements) the water of (=over on) our (exclusive) side.'

[]ìèⁿ 'all' as right-edge marker in conditional antecedent, §16.1.2; mààṅ]ìèⁿ, §8.2.5.2; táá 'side'; plural exclusive since the reference is to another pond owned by A's clan]

(07:47) A ṅūòṅ lāā, yà= á nà— yá= [à tíṅāā]—
 DemDef Purp, if 3Sg if.Pfv— if [3Sg possession]—

S à gá ìṅ fùléè rà
 3Sg Ipfv Refl fish(v).Ipfv Q,

A: 'For that reason, if it—. If its (=pond's)—.

S: 'Is it (=pond) fished (=fishable)?'

[speaker overlap here]

(07:50) A hááⁿ, à gá ìn fùlèè, à gá ìn fùlèè,
 huh?, 3Sg Ipfv Refl fish(v).Ipfv, 3Sg Ipfv Refl fish(v).Ipfv,

S ìṅfá?àlàà
 if.God.wills

A: ‘Huh? It is fished (=fishable), it is fished (=fishable).’

S: ‘Hopefully.’

[< Arabic ‘if God wills’]

(07:54) A *comme* [jíí xálú-gú ròdò] bè *quoi*,
 like [water male-Def Foc] come.Pfv Ø,
 yé [jìì xàlù] ná bè [sáàⁿ máàṅ jìèⁿ],
 if [water male] if.Pfv come.Pfv [time Rel all],

A: ‘Like, it’s the male (=soiled) water that has come. Whenever the male water has come, ...’

[‘male’ water, §5.1.3.7]

(07:59) A múd gà gáṅgāā
 1PIEx Ipfv fish.by.sweeping.Ipfv

S ìṅfá?àlàà
 if.God.wills

A: ‘... we (exclusive) fish by sweeping nets.’

S: ‘Hopefully.’

[gáṅgà (noun and verb)]

(08:01) S ilá àlá kòrì [xáy gā],
 hopefully God help.Pfv [1PIIn Dat],
 [ilá àlá à míé-nì] [à á là [kì gā]]
 hopefully God 3Sg good-Caus.Pfv [3Sg 3Sg give.Pfv [1PIIn Dat]],

S: ‘May God help us (inclusive)! May God make it good and may He give it to us (inclusive)!’

[kóri [X gā] with dative PP ‘help X’, compare kóri [X mā] ‘join X, be added to X’ @ 07:43 above]

(08:00) S [xā wāā] [xá [yé xàyⁿ]]
 [2Pl (greeting)] [2Pl [and work(n)]]
 wāā [xá [yè bārāy]]
 (greeting) [2Pl [and reward]]

S: ‘Greetings to you-Pl! You-Pl and work! Greetings, you-Pl and (divine) reward!’

[greetings, §19.5]

(08:05) S *d'accord*
all.right

A yáâltá
Yalouta (name)

S: 'All right.'

A: 'Yalouta!'

[the interlocutor's name is uttered to conclude a greeting cycle]